

Final Report:
**Solid Oxide Fuel Cells for Combined Cooling and Power in
Data Centers**

Submitted to: **Joe Leiva**
Advanced Technologies
Southern California Gas Company
555 West 5th Street,
Los Angeles, CA 90013

Submitted by: **Alejandro Lavernia, Maryam Asghari**
Prof. Jacob (Jack) Brouwer, Director
Clean Energy Institute
University of California, Irvine
221 Engineering Laboratory Facility
Irvine, California 92697-3550
Tel: (949) 338-5953
[jbrouwer@ uci.edu](mailto:jbrouwer@uci.edu)

CLEAN ENERGY
INSTITUTE
UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, IRVINE

July 31, 2023

Contents

LIST OF FIGURES.....	4
ACRONYMS.....	9
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	12
1. INTRODUCTION.....	13
1.1 MOTIVATION.....	13
1.2 DATA CENTER COMPONENTS	15
1.3 DATA CENTER POWER INFRASTRUCTURE	16
1.4 DATA CENTER COOLING.....	17
1.5 SOFC DRIVEN DATA CENTER.....	21
1.6 OVERVIEW	22
1.7 OVERALL PROJECT GOAL	24
2. DATA CENTER COOLING DEMAND	25
2.1 DATA CENTER MODELING.....	26
2.2 DATA CENTER COOLING DEMAND RESULTS	28
2.3 SUMMARY.....	35
3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP.....	36
3.1 BLUEGEN SOFC SYSTEMS	36
3.2 BLUEGEN SOFC OPERATION.....	36
3.3 SOFC SYSTEM	38
3.4 INTERNET CONNECTION	42
3.5 SERVER RACK	42
3.6 ABSORPTION CHILLER SYSTEM.....	46
3.6.1 ABSORPTION CHILLER.....	46
3.6.2 HOT WATER LOOP	47
3.6.3 COLD WATER LOOP	49
3.6.4 COOLING WATER LOOP	52
3.7 SIMULATED EXHAUST SYSTEM	57
3.7.1 ELECTRICAL AIR HEATER.....	57
3.7.2 BLOWER	61
3.8 DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM AND VIRTUAL INTERFACE	63
3.9 SENSOR ARRAY.....	67
3.10 DATA ANALYSIS	69
4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.....	71
4.1 SOFC DYNAMIC EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.....	71
4.2 SOFC DEGRADATION RESULTS	75
4.3 ABSORPTION CHILLER PRIMARY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS	77
4.4 SUMMARY.....	81
5. MODEL DEVELOPMENT	83
5.1 INTEGRATED ABSORPTION CHILLER MODELING – ROW LEVEL	83
5.1.1 SOLID OXIDE FUEL CELL MODEL.....	83
5.1.2 ABSORPTION CHILLER MODEL.....	86
5.1.3 ECONOMIC MODEL.....	87
5.2 DYNAMIC SOFC STACK MODEL	88
5.2.1 GOVERNING EQUATIONS	92
5.3 DYNAMIC SOFC SYSTEM DESIGN & CONTROL	99
5.3.1 BALANCE OF PLANT MODEL:	100
5.3.2 CONTROL STRATEGY	102
5.4 LIQUID DESICCANT DEHUMIDIFIER MODELING.....	103

5.4.1	LIQUID DESICCANT TECHNOLOGY AND SYSTEM	103
5.4.2	LIQUID DESICCANT COMPONENT MODELING	122
5.4.3	INDIRECT EVAPORATIVE COOLING MODELING	125
5.4.4	REGENERATOR MODELING	127
5.4.5	CONTROL STRATEGY FOR THE LIQUID DESICCANT SYSTEM	129
5.4.6	LIQUID DESICCANT SYSTEM MODEL VERIFICATION	130
5.4.7	SUMMARY	134
6.	MODELING RESULTS.....	134
6.1	LIQUID DESICCANT DEHUMIDIFICATION.....	134
6.2	STEADY STATE SOFC MODEL RESULTS	140
6.2.1	INTEGRATED MODEL RESULTS.....	142
6.2.2	ECONOMIC MODEL RESULTS	147
6.3	SOFC STACK RESULTS.....	148
6.3.1	STEADY STATE RESULTS	152
6.3.2	SOFC SYSTEM DYNAMIC MODELING RESULTS	153
6.3.3	SUMMARY	158
6.4	INTEGRATED SYSTEM DESIGN.....	158
6.4.1	SPONTANEOUS INTEGRATED SYSTEM PERFORMANCE	159
6.4.2	LiCl DAILY STORAGE.....	164
6.4.3	LiCl YEARLY STORAGE	168
6.4.4	SUMMARY	189
7.	CONCLUSION.....	189
8.	REFERENCES.....	192

List of Figures

Figure 1. Global electricity demand of data centers 2010-2030 [2].	13
Figure 2: Traditional data center system losses [7].	14
Figure 3: Electricity consumption for data centers [8].	15
Figure 4. Simplified heat removal methods in data centers [18].	17
Figure 5. Indirect adiabatic cooler [21].	19
Figure 6. Proposed SOFC trigeneration system, consisting of three subsystems: SOFC-CHP system, adsorption refrigeration system, and water tank equipped with a temperature controller [32].	21
Figure 7: Schematics of CCHP systems considered in this work: (a) SOFC paired with an absorption chiller, and (b) SOFC paired with a liquid desiccant dehumidification system.	23
Figure 8. Integrated SOFC- Absorption-Chilling and/or Liquid Desiccant Air Conditioning (LDAC) concept for servers in data centers.	25
Figure 9. Cooling system type for 7 locations based on ASHRAE recommended (left bar) & allowable (right bar) range.	29
Figure 10. Load profile for the RSF data center over the first 11 months of operations. Illustration by Chad Lobato, NREL[41].	30
Figure 11. TMY data for California and Texas throughout the year.	31
Figure 12. Data Center power demand breakdown throughout a year for California and Texas.	32
Figure 13. Data Center power demand percentage for California and Texas.	32
Figure 14. PUE for California and Texas for the entire year.	33
Figure 15. Data center energy usage for a 50MW data center.	34
Figure 16. Energy consumed by different part of data center for various combinations.	35
Figure 17. BlueGEN System.	36
Figure 18. Experiment set up concept schematic.	37
Figure 19. BlueGEN system in NFCRC laboratory.	38
Figure 20. Water connections schematic.	40
Figure 21. Pump used for fuel cell water rejection connection.	40
Figure 22. Manifold and valves for fuel cell supply water.	41
Figure 23. BlueGEN exhaust manifold.	42
Figure 24. Server rack at NFCRC laboratory.	43
Figure 25. Custom Process Air Ducting.	44
Figure 26. Process Air Ducting Installed on Absorption Chiller Test Stand.	45
Figure 27. Process Air Duct Fan.	45
Figure 28. Yazaki WFC-SC5 LiBr Absorption Chiller.	47
Figure 29. Hot Water Loop with Exhaust Heat Exchanger.	48
Figure 30. Hot Water Loop Pump.	49
Figure 31. Cold Water Loop and Duct Heat Exchanger.	50
Figure 32. Process Air Heat Exchanger.	51
Figure 33. Cold Water Pump.	51
Figure 34: Exterior Cooling Water Loop with Cooling Tower.	53
Figure 35: Cooling Tower Internal Structure Schematic.	54
Figure 36: First Cooling Tower Pump.	55
Figure 37: New Cooling Water Pump with VFD.	56
Figure 38: Electrical Heater: Flow Torch 800.	57
Figure 39: Electric Heater with Custom Flanges.	58

Figure 40: Heater Controller.....	58
Figure 41: Electric Heater Block Diagram.....	59
Figure 42. Heater Grid Connection Wiring Diagram.....	60
Figure 43. 480 V Disconnect, Distribution Block, and Fuse Blocks.....	60
Figure 44. Electrical Failure in Heater Fuse Enclosure.....	61
Figure 45. Blower Fan Curve.....	62
Figure 46. Simulated Exhaust Blower.....	63
Figure 47. LabVIEW Virtual Interface for the Absorption Chiller Test Stand.....	64
Figure 48. Low Voltage Control Box with DAQ.....	65
Figure 49. Low Voltage Control Wiring Diagram.....	66
Figure 50. Vortex Shedding Flow Schematic.....	67
Figure 51. Hot Water Flow Meter.....	68
Figure 52. Differential Pressure Transducer with Pitot Tube.....	69
Figure 53. BlueGEN dynamic operation data.....	71
Figure 54. BlueGEN stack power cycle- 24h.....	72
Figure 55. BlueGEN current density and voltage on a 24h cycle.....	72
Figure 56. BlueGEN stack temperature on a 24h cycle.....	73
Figure 57. BlueGEN performance.....	73
Figure 58. BlueGEN stack power cycle- one week.....	74
Figure 59. BlueGEN voltage on a one week cycle.....	74
Figure 60. BlueGEN stack temperature on a one week cycle.....	75
Figure 61. BlueGEN V-J characteristics curve for a 24h power cycle for 42 days.....	75
Figure 62. BlueGEN power profile over 6000h operation.....	76
Figure 63. BlueGEN stack voltage (V) during 6000h operation.....	76
Figure 64. Exhaust Temperature Transient Step.....	77
Figure 65. Hot Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.....	78
Figure 66. Cooling Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.....	78
Figure 67. Cold Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.....	78
Figure 68. Preliminary Sweep Chiller Performance Results.....	79
Figure 69. Multi-Parameter Sweep COP Results.....	80
Figure 70. Multi-Parameter Sweep Capacity Results.....	81
Figure 71. SOFC Balance of Plant Schematic.....	83
Figure 72. Triple Effect Absorption Chiller System Schematic.....	86
Figure 73. Absorption Chiller Coefficient of Performance at varying temperature constraints. [9]	87
Figure 74. Planar fuel cell model.....	89
Figure 75. Geometric parameters of a fuel cell.....	91
Figure 76. SOFC system configuration.....	100
Figure 77. Liquid desiccant comparison to conventional air conditioning system.....	104
Figure 78. Conceptual layout of industrial liquid-desiccant system [51]......	106
Figure 79. Equilibrium relative humidity for lithium chloride.....	108
Figure 80. Major components and packaging of the AILR LDAC [59]......	111
Figure 81. Physical DEVap Concept description[59]......	112
Figure 82. DEVap air conditioner schematic. (a) four stack channel pairs (b) top view, one channel pair[59]......	114
Figure 83. DEVap airstreams on a psychrometric chart [73]......	115

Figure 84. Heat pump driven liquid desiccant air handling devices [51].	117
Figure 85. Configuration of the LLD system.	122
Figure 86. Dehumidifier unit schematic.	123
Figure 87. Indirect evaporative cooler schematic.	126
Figure 88. Regenerator unit schematic.	128
Figure 89. Model-experiment comparison of dehumidifier. (top) Change in supply-side air, temperature (bottom) change in relative humidity.	131
Figure 90. Model-experiment comparison of indirect evaporative cooler. (top) Change in supply-side air, temperature (bottom) change in relative humidity.	133
Figure 91. System configuration for server rack level power and cooling	134
Figure 92. SOFC polarization curve for the BlueGEN data compared to the current physical SOFC system model.	135
Figure 93. Integrated SOFC- LDD system model schematic.	137
Figure 94. Airstream at 25 °C and 70% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.	138
Figure 95. Airstream at 35 °C and 45% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.	139
Figure 96. Airstream at 40 °C and 20% RH process on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.	139
Figure 97. Mass flow rate of fuel (a) and air into the SOFC system (b).	140
Figure 98. Cell voltage within SOFC stack (a) and Post-anode oxidizer outlet temperature (b).	141
Figure 99. SOFC system efficiency over operational domain.	141
Figure 100. Carbon dioxide emissions from SOFC system.	142
Figure 101. SOFC system exhaust temperature (a) and mass flow rate (b).	143
Figure 102. SOFC system exhaust heat capacity.	144
Figure 103. Triple-effect absorption chiller chilling capacity from SOFC exhaust heat.	144
Figure 104. Primary energy savings ratio of integrated SOFC and absorption system.	145
Figure 105. Operational envelope superimposed on primary energy savings ratio.	146
Figure 106. Levelized costs of electricity (a) and chilling for the integrated system (b).	147
Figure 107. Levelized cost of utility (electricity & chilling) from the integrated SOFC and absorption chiller.	148
Figure 108. State spatial distribution of temperature.	149
Figure 109. Steady-state spatial distribution of Nernst voltage.	149
Figure 110. Steady-state spatial distribution of losses.	150
Figure 111. Steady-state spatial distribution of voltage.	151
Figure 112. Steady-state spatial distribution of current density.	151
Figure 113. SOFC polarization curve for the BlueGEN data compared to the current physical SOFC system model.	152
Figure 114. SOFC model power output following the residential electricity demand	154
Figure 115. Variation of electrical efficiency versus time.	154
Figure 116. Exhaust gas temperature of the SOFC system.	155
Figure 117. Exhaust gas mass flow rate of the SOFC system.	156
Figure 118. PEN average temperature.	157
Figure 119. Stack temperature difference.	158
Figure 120. System configuration for server rack level power and cooling.	159
Figure 121. Integrated SOFC-LDD system model schematic.	160

Figure 122. Airstream at 25°C and 70% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.....	162
Figure 123. Airstream at 35°C and 45%RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.....	163
Figure 124. Airstream at 40°C and 20% RH process on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.	164
Figure 125. Microsoft data center location in the US.	165
Figure 126. Temperature of 7 different location for 24 hours on July 20, 2018.	165
Figure 127. Dew point temperature of 7 different locations for 24 hours on July 20, 2018.....	166
Figure 128. SOFC-LDD schematic for considering storage capacity.....	167
Figure 129. Dew point for the seven locations of the study for the entire year.	169
Figure 130. Schematic of row level server cooling.	170
Figure 131. Mixture air temperature before and after regeneration process for the entire year..	171
Figure 132. Mixture air humidity before and after regeneration process for the entire year.	171
Figure 133. Return air percentages for regeneration process.	172
Figure 134. Rate of regenerated desiccant flow for the entire year.	172
Figure 135. Desiccant inlet and outlet concentration in regenerator.	173
Figure 136. Hot water inlet and outlet from regenerator.....	173
Figure 137. Supply air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier for the entire year.	174
Figure 138. Cooling air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier for the entire year.....	174
Figure 139. Return air percentages for dehumidifier process for the entire year.	175
Figure 140. Humidity ratio of inlet and outlet supply air for the entire year.	175
Figure 141. Desiccant flow that is needed for the entire year to dehumidify the air for the servers.	176
Figure 142. Desiccant inlet and outlet concentration in dehumidifier.....	176
Figure 143. Net desiccant consumption and production for the entire year for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois.....	177
Figure 144. State of storage (charge) of strong desiccant for all four locations.....	178
Figure 145. Mixture air temperature before and after regeneration process.	180
Figure 146. Mixture air humidity before and after regeneration process.....	181
Figure 147. Return air percentage for regenerator.....	181
Figure 148. Regenerated desiccant flow rate throughout the year.....	182
Figure 149. Desiccant concentration inlet and outlet in regenerator.	182
Figure 150. Hot water inlet and outlet temperature before and after regenerator.	183
Figure 151. Supply air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier.....	183
Figure 152. Cooling air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier.	184
Figure 153. Return air percentage in dehumidifier.....	184
Figure 154. cooling air inlet and outlet humidity ratio in dehumidifier.....	185
Figure 155. Desiccant flow rate in dehumidifier for the entire rate.....	185
Figure 156. desiccant inlet and outlet desiccant concentration.	186
Figure 157. Net desiccant consumption and production for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois in row level storage.	187
Figure 158. the state of storage of strong desiccant for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois in row level storage.	188

List of Tables

Table 1. ASHRAE 2016 Thermal Guidelines [17].	26
Table 2. Zone Boundaries for Recommended Environmental Envelope for IT Equipment.	26
Table 3. effect of dry bulb temperature on air cooled chillers efficiency.	28
Table 4. effect of dry bulb temperature on water cooled chillers efficiency.	28
Table 5. Average PUE for 7 data center target location.	34
Table 6. percentage of energy consumed by different part of data center for various combinations.	35
Table 7: Simulated Exhaust Pressure Drops.	62
Table 8: VI Safety Shutdown Conditions.	64
Table 9. Data Acquisition Channels and Units.	70
Table 10. BlueGEN degradation analysis	76
Table 11. Initial Sweep Parameters.	77
Table 12. Exhaust Temperature and Flow Sweep Parameters.	80
Table 13. SOFC Model Assumptions and Inputs.	85
Table 14. Economic Model Inputs. [5],[16]	88
Table 15. Fuel cell material properties.	90
Table 16. Fuel cell geometrical parameters.	92
Table 17. Comparison between liquid desiccant and vapor compression cooling [57].	105
Table 18. Dehumidifier unit verification input and output parameter.	130
Table 19. Indirect evaporative cooler verification input and output parameter.	132
Table 20. SOFC Parameters and Design Operating Conditions.	135
Table 21. SOFC Steady State Performance Parameters.	136
Table 22. Inlet and outlet conditions of the regenerator stage.	137
Table 23. Inlet and outlet conditions of the dehumidifier stage.	137
Table 24. Inlet and outlet conditions of the IEC stage.	138
Table 25. SOFC Parameters and Design Operating Conditions.	153
Table 26. SOFC steady state performance parameters.	153
Table 27. Inlet and outlet conditions of the regenerator stage.	160
Table 28. Inlet and outlet conditions of the dehumidifier stage.	161
Table 29. Inlet and outlet conditions of the IEC stage.	161
Table 30. 24-hour average weather data on July 20, 2018.	167
Table 31. Daily storage capacity for 7 data center locations during July 20 th .	168
Table 32. Rack level storage results for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois.	180
Table 33. Rack level storage results for the four locations.	188
Table 34. Rack and Row level storage comparison.	189

Acronyms

AC	Alternating Current or Absorption Chiller
A/C	Air Conditioning
ADR	Ammonia Decomposition Reaction
APEP	Advanced Power and Energy Program
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-conditioning Engineers
CaCl ₂	Calcium Chloride
CCHP	Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power
CFCL	Ceramic Fuel Cells Ltd
CFM	Cubic Feet per Minute
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CRAC	Computer Room Air Conditioners
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRAH	Computer Room Air Handling
COP	Coefficient of Performance
DC	Direct Current
DEVap	Desiccant enhanced EVaporative air-conditioning
DOE	Department of Energy
DRT	Distribution of Relaxation Times
DX	Direct eXpansion cooling
EAGERS	Efficient Allocation of Grid Energy Resources including Storage
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-Ray
EES	Engineering Equation Solver
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
GDC	Gadolinium Doped Ceria
GEM	Group of Energy Material
GHG	Green House Gas
GT	Gas Turbine
HMX	Heat and Mass eXchanger
HP	Heat Pump

HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IDCS	Integrated Desiccant air Conditioning System
IEC	Indirect Evaporative Cooler
IHX	interchange Heat eXchanger
IT	Information Technology
KCOOH	Potassium Formate
KK	Kramer Kronig
LD	Liquid Desiccant
LDAC	Liquid Desiccant Air Conditioning
LDD	Liquid Desiccant Dehumidifier
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LiBr	Lithium Bromide
LiCl	Lithium Chloride
NFCRC	National Fuel Cell Research Center
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
ODE	Ordinary Differential Equation
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PEN	Positive electrode, Electrolyte, Negative electrode
PUE	Power Usage Efficiency
PVC	PolyVinyl Chloride
R&D	Research & Development
RH	Relative Humidity
RIEC	Regenerative Indirect Evaporative Cooling
SEM	Scan Electron Microscopy
S2C	Steam to (2) Carbon
SDCS	Separated Liquid Desiccant air Conditioning System
SHR	Sensible Heat Ratio
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
TMY	Typical Meteorological Year

TPB	Triple-Phase Boundary
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Sources
VC	Vapor Compression
VCS	Vapor Compression Systems
VFD	Variable Frequency Drive
WGS	Water Gas Shift
YSZ	Yttria-Stabilized Zirconia

Executive Summary

Data center operation uses roughly 200 TWh of electricity per year, or 1% of global electricity consumption. Data center electricity usage is expected to grow, accounting for up to 13% of global electricity demand in 2030. Up to 40% of this demand is due to cooling requirements necessary for safe and secure data center operation. The vast majority of data centers use centrally generated electricity with onsite diesel backup. Shifting from a central electricity paradigm to distributed could allow for the capture of heat from onsite generators to power thermally activated cooling cycles, or combined cooling, heat, and power (CCHP). A solid oxide fuel cell based CCHP system is attractive since the base fuel cell system has high fuel to electricity conversion efficiency, and the system can produce a high temperature exhaust gas stream.

This report summarizes our work on examining the SOFC based CCHP system. We consider a SOFC system coupled with either an absorption chiller or a liquid desiccant cooling and dehumidification system. This includes physical experimentation with SOFC and absorption chiller systems, and the development and testing of physics based SOFC, absorption chiller, and desiccant dehumidification system models.

Experimental results show that a real SOFC system surpasses over 60% fuel to electricity conversion efficiency when operated at full load. We calculated system performance degradation by determining fuel consumption increase at full load, showing that system efficiency decreases by 0.05% to 0.4% percentage points per 1000 operating hours. Higher degradation was observed during more dynamic operation. Although fuel cell stack performance improves at SOFC part load, balance of plant component performance suffers, resulting in a net decrease in efficiency at part load operation. Experiments also showed that the SOFC can operate dynamically while maintaining a consistent stack temperature. However, faster responding electric supplies are likely necessary to handle extremely fast data center load dynamics, such as the start up/shut down of a data server. Absorption chiller experiments showed that chilling power peaks at higher temperature SOFC exhaust temperatures, but highest conversion of fuel cell exhaust energy to cooling power occurs at between 190 and 210°C. Experimental results were used to validate and tune physics-based models.

These models suggest that a SOFC system paired with a multiple-effect absorption chiller can meet data center electricity and cooling loads while also reducing primary energy consumption by up to 25%. Using conventional natural gas, the combined cost of a SOFC and triple effect absorption chiller is projected to be between \$70 and \$88 per kWh. These values represent a cost floor – switching to renewable natural gas or energy will increase fuel cost, ultimately increasing these cost values.

Modeling results also show that the current SOFC system paired with a liquid desiccant system meets only 7% of data center cooling requirements. The main challenge is temporal mismatch between heat production from the SOFC and cooling demand. If regenerated desiccant can be stored after being heated by the SOFC, the SOFC-desiccant system can meet up to 80% of cooling loads in warm/hot climates (Texas), and up to 90% in more mild climates (Virginia). Regardless, in both instances, backup cooling systems are required to meet cooling requirements.

In total, the SOFC based CCHP system can be used to reduce primary energy use at data centers. When cooling is provided through an absorption chiller, there is potential to meet most electricity and cooling loads using the CCHP. The SOFC-desiccant system can meet up to 80% to 90% of cooling requirements, but only when regenerated desiccant storage is implemented at the data center.

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The rapid growth of internet use, cloud computing and data-driven machines and services is increasing the electric power consumption and carbon footprint of data centers. Data center electricity demand was around 200TWh (1% of global electricity consumption) in 2018 [1]. However, due to the expected growth in the production and use of electronic devices, cloud services, and computer networks, electricity consumption projections place data centers at up to 13% of global electricity demand in 2030 [2]. As shown in

Figure 1 in the best-case scenario data center electricity consumption doubles in the next 10 years. Associated with this massive electricity consumption are greenhouse gas (GHG) and criteria pollutant emissions due to the use of conventional fossil energy resources to power data center electric loads. In 2020, the information and communications technology sector represented 2.3% of global GHG emissions, 28.8% of which were associated with data centers [3]. In addition, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, dependency upon internet technology, and cloud services, data center demands are only increased further. Data centers will use around 3–13% of global electricity in 2030 compared to 1% in 2010 [2]. To meet the emissions reduction targets imposed by many IT companies like Microsoft, data center electricity must be reduced through energy efficiency, and remaining loads must be met by renewable sources. It is impossible to eliminate all data center loads, but the combination of efficiency and renewable energy sources will reduce GHG and pollutant emissions.

Figure 1. Global electricity demand of data centers 2010-2030 [2].

In a traditional data center connected to the electric grid, less than 35% of the energy from the fuel source that is supplied to the power plant is delivered to the data center. Power plant generation

losses and transmission and distribution losses are the most significant inefficiencies in data center [6]. Figure 2 shows the process of power loss through the transportation and distribution network of the electric grid starting from the fuel source up to the power supplied to the consumer. It is evident that the largest inefficiency is from the power generated at the power plant level with additional losses associated with the transmission and distribution to the data center, where the data center receives roughly 30% of the total energy that could have been supplied ideally from the fuel source. There are additional loads associated with the infrastructure required for daily reliable operation (i.e., cooling, lighting, and Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) systems). The additional power consumed by the cooling, lighting, and energy storage, means approximately less than 17.5% of the energy supplied to the power plant is ultimately delivered to the servers [7].

(A) Traditional Data Center
(with U.S. Grid Average Efficiency, 2011)

Figure 2: Traditional data center system losses [7].

Information Technology (IT) equipment (e.g., servers, networks, storage, etc.) and cooling infrastructure are the two major power consumers. As shown in Figure 3 cooling infrastructure is a large electricity consumer in the data center and can account for up to 40% of the total energy delivered to the data center [8]. Cooling also represents the biggest slice of the total cost in a data center. With more capacity and higher density there is an increased need for energy-efficient cooling of the IT equipment. While data centers need cooling to protect servers and other equipment, an additional challenge is humidity control. Too much humidity can cause corrosion of metal parts of the servers leading to short circuiting of electronics. On the other hand, low humidity allows the servers to develop electrostatic charges that can cause damage to sensitive equipment.

Figure 3: Electricity consumption for data centers [8].

According to Uptime Institute [9], electric power outages are the main causes of the increasing outage trend in data centers. According to the Eaton Blackout Tracker [10], the US experienced more than 3,500 utility power outages in 2017, the vast majority of which were attributed to faults in the transmission and distribution system. This number represents a 62% increase in outages from a decade ago. In 2018, a storm interrupted grid power to Microsoft's San Antonio Azure data center, knocking cooling systems offline, damaging a significant amount of equipment, and bringing down Active Directory and Visual Studio Team Services for almost 24 hours [11]. In some areas, rising temperatures are driving up the cost of data centers. In other areas, extreme rainfall and flooding have damaged equipment, and prevented the fuel deliveries which are so critical to the traditional back-up power solutions. And power costs continuously increase. The global cost of power for data centers is expected to increase 80% in the next five years. At 35% of total costs, electric power continues to represent the largest portion of data center operating costs [12]. Every power generation system that supplies a data center must comply with stringent reliability and availability constraints to ensure 99.9999% server uptime. With business and society relying so much on data centers, and data centers growing more and more, there is a greater need for reliable and clean electric power for data centers.

1.2 Data Center Components

Data centers are centralized locations with computing and networking equipment for collecting, storing, processing, distributing, or allowing access to large amounts of data. Because of their high concentrations of computer servers, often stacked in racks that are placed in rows, data centers are sometimes called server farms. Data centers provide services such as data storage, backup and recovery, data management and networking. These centers can run e-mail and instant messaging services, store and serve up web sites, provide cloud storage and applications, enable e-commerce transactions, power online gaming communities, etc.

Some components for supporting data center infrastructure include:

- Uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) – battery banks, fueled generators, and redundant power sources.
- Environmental Control – Computer Room Air Conditioners (CRAC), Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems, and exhaust systems.
- Security Systems – biometrics and video surveillance systems.
- IT equipment – actual equipment for IT operations and storage of the organization’s data. This includes servers, storage hardware, cables, and racks [13].
- Backup Power – a set of fueled combustion-based power generators usually powered by natural gas or diesel.

1.3 Data center power infrastructure

Most traditional data centers get their primary electricity from utility electric grid. The facility will then either have one or several transformers in place to take in the energy, while also ensuring the power coming in is of the right voltage and the right type of current (converted from AC to Direct Current (DC) typically). Some data centers supplement their energy from the grid or completely remove it by on-site electrical generation equipment - either in the form of combustion-based generators or with alternative energy sources such as solar photovoltaic panels and wind-powered turbines. The power then gets transferred to the main distribution boards which house fuses, circuit breakers, and ground leakage protection units, take the low-voltage electricity and distribute it to a number of UPS systems. UPS are responsible for supplying power to a number of racks while helping clean up the electricity pulsing through by ensuring that issues like surges don’t impact equipment. UPS systems also serve as an initial backup, in case of a power outage or similar issue. In a nutshell, a UPS battery turns on after the system senses a loss of power. Their purpose is to maintain the infrastructure until consistent power returns, or if needed, until longer-term emergency power backup systems kick in. A typical UPS can provide power to servers and breakers for up to five minutes; that way, there’s enough time to get a backup generator going immediately following an outage or similar issue with the wider electric grid. In order to ensure continuous uptime and minimize outages as much as possible, most data centers have a backup power source on site or nearby. Often backup power supply comes from a fuel generator powered by gasoline or diesel [14].

In a data center, not only servers and other critical pieces of IT equipment require a lot of electricity to operate, but also all of the ancillary equipment. Lights, cooling systems, monitors, humidifiers, etc. also need electricity. The amount of electricity that goes towards servers versus non-IT equipment is called Power Usage Efficiency (PUE) score which measures usage effectiveness. A score of 1 means that all the energy in a data center goes towards servers, while a score of 2 means that ancillary equipment uses just as much electricity as servers and other IT components [14]. The Uptime Institute survey shows that the average PUE of a data center stands at 1.58. The average PUE for a Google data center is 1.12, but its facility in Oklahoma had a score of just 1.08 during the last three months of 2018 [15].

Today, the average power consumption for a rack is around 7kW depending upon the data center. However, almost two-thirds of data centers in the US experience higher peak demands, with a power density of around 15kW to 16kW per rack. Some data centers may hit 20kW or

more per rack at times [16]. The Uptime Institute's latest survey found that around one in five have a density of 30kW or higher, indicating the growing presence of high-density computing. Half said their current rack density was between 10kW and 29kW [15]. One of the most critical challenges associated with increasing power density within data centers is cooling. Alternative cooling technologies and methodologies such as liquid cooling, use of solar and wind for power cooling systems are being developed against that need.

1.4 Data center cooling

One of the largest operational expenses of data centers is the cost of energy. Cooling power consumption accounts for up to 40% of data center energy use [10]. The original American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) air temperature envelope was 20-25°C in 2004 based on reliability and uptime as the primary concern. Nowadays, changes to data center environmental conditions are being driven by the need to save energy and reduce operational expenses. From 2016, ASHRAE recommended range of temperature and humidity is 18°C to 28°C dry bulb temperature, 9°C to 15°C dew point and 60% relative humidity [17]. The Uptime Institute, however, recommends an upper limit of 25°C [15].

There are different common ways of to remove excess heat in data centers as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Simplified heat removal methods in data centers [18].

A Computer Room Air Handling (CRAH) is similar to a chilled water air handling system. In this system, the cooling is accomplished by blowing air over the cooling coil filled with the chilled water. The chilled water is typically supplied to the CRAHs by an electric powered chiller. The chiller then removes the heat from the warmer chilled water and transfers it to

another stream of circulating water called condenser water which flows through a cooling tower. These CRAHs can have Variable Frequency Drives (VFD) that modulate fan speed to maintain a set static pressure either under floor or in the overhead ducts. Heat removed from the returning chilled water can be rejected to a condenser water loop for transport to the outside atmosphere or to an air-cooled condenser, or to a glycol cooled chiller.

A CRAC unit works like an air conditioner which has an in-built direct expansion refrigeration cycle. The compressors which are required to power the refrigeration cycle is also located within the CRAC unit. Thus, the cooling is accomplished by blowing the air over the cooling coil filled with refrigerant. Heat from the IT environment is pumped to the outdoor environment using this circulating flow of refrigerant. New CRAC units are developed that can vary the airflow with the help of multistage compressors. However, most of the existing ones have on/off control only.

Modern data centers try to use adiabatic direct air cooling whenever the weather conditions allow. The common types of cooling are as follows:

Free Cooling: Free cooling is an approach for cooling the air temperature in the target environment by using ambient cool air or water from the local environment instead of mechanical refrigeration. In this method, pumps, fans, and other air/water-handling equipment are needed. Cooling systems that use this approach are also called air-side economizers. The primary method is evaporative cooling, where ambient air is passed through a wet filter that cools it. The air then enters the cooling system at a lower temperature, which allows for more efficient operation. Evaporative assist is most beneficial in dry climates. Alternatively, in water side economizer a source of cold water from local rivers, lakes or oceans is circulated into a data center and used instead of refrigerating a closed water loop with a chiller [19]. Evaporative assist is an adiabatic cooling system which does not have heat exchange to the environment. Adiabatic cooling incorporates both evaporative and air cooling into a single system [20].

An indirect ambient air cooling system uses outdoor air to indirectly cool data center air when the temperature outside is lower than the temperature set point of the IT inlet air, resulting in significant energy savings. Fans blow cold outside air through an air-to-air heat exchanger which in turn cools the hot data center air on the other side of the heat exchanger, thereby completely isolating the data center air from the outside air. Heat exchangers can be of the plate or rotating type. Heat removal method normally uses evaporative assist whereby the outside of the air-to-air heat exchanger is sprayed with water which further lowers the temperature of the outside air and thus the hot data center air [18].

Indirect adiabatic data center cooling: The indirect adiabatic cooling consists of two different airflows named primary and secondary airflow as shown Figure 5.

Figure 5. Indirect adiabatic cooler [21].

Primary airflow is the airflow that is used to cool the IT load. The secondary airflow is the outside or the ambient air which is used to discharge the IT load of the primary airflow. The primary airflow and secondary airflow are completely separated from each other because mixing them will create pollution and inconsistencies. During warm days water is sprayed on the heat exchanger to increase the cooling capacity of the secondary airflow according to the physical laws of psychrometrics. The water also provides a better conductivity between the two airflows by optimizing the energy transfer. Most units require a basic water softening system to produce the required water. A water storage tank is required to store a certain amount of water in case of water outage from the main water connection. There are basically two operating modes, Summer/wet: If conditions are not met for the secondary airflow, the air is humidified by adding a specific amount of water to the secondary air flow to increase its cooling capacity.

In addition to these adiabatic cooling systems, direct expansion (DX) cooling systems (i.e., those that use the vapor compression thermodynamic cycle), powered by electricity, may be required in specific locations to reach the cooling demand of the data center. Winter/dry: Primary airflow transfers its heat towards the cooler secondary airflow without the requirement of water. The indirect adiabatic cooler is known for its high energy efficiency reaching a cooling PUE of 1.05 at a single moment [21].

There are three basic approaches for distributing air in a data center: flooded, targeted, and contained. In a flooded supply and return air distribution system, the only constraints to the supply and return air flow are the walls, ceiling, and floor of the room. This leads to heavy mixing of the hot and cold air flows. In a targeted supply and return air distribution system, a mechanism (e.g., duct, perforated tile, cooling unit placed within IT rows) directs the supply and return airflow within 3m (10ft) of the IT equipment intake and exhaust. In a contained supply and return air distribution system, the IT equipment supply and return air flow is completely enclosed to eliminate air mixing between the supply and the return air streams [22]. Hot aisle/cold aisle arrangements lower cooling costs by better managing airflow, thereby accommodating lower fan speeds and increasing the use of air-side or water-side economizers. When used in combination with containment, Department of Energy (DOE) estimates reduction in fan energy use of 20% to 25% [23].

Another data center cooling technique is open bath immersion cooling which implies fully submerging IT equipment in a dielectric liquid. These baths allow the coolant fluid to be moved through the hardware components or servers submerged in it. Single phase immersion requires circulation of the dielectric liquids by pumps or by natural convection flow. These liquids always remain in the liquid state while operating. The dielectric coolant is either pumped through an external heat exchanger where it is cooled with any facility coolant, or the facility coolant is pumped through an immersed heat exchanger, which facilitates heat transfer within the dielectric liquid. In two-phase immersion systems, heat is removed through the phase change that the coolant undergoes at its operating temperature. The server heat literally boils the dielectric fluid that has an appropriate boiling point temperature. This two-phase immersion system takes advantage of the dielectric fluid latent heat of vaporization. This occurs when the two-phase coolant comes in contact with the heated electronics in the bath that are above the coolants boiling point. Once the two-phase coolant enters its gas phase it must be cooled or condensed, typically through the use of water-cooled coils placed in the top of the tank. Once condensed the two-phase coolant drips back into the primary cooling tank. The two-phase coolant in the tank generally remains at its “saturation temperature”. Energy transferred from the servers into the two-phase coolant will cause a portion of it to boil off into a gas. The gas rises above the liquid level where it contacts a condenser which is cooler than the saturation temperature. This causes the gaseous state coolant to condense back into a liquid form and fall back into the bath [24]. In order to safely submerge an electronic device in a liquid, the liquid must be nonconductive to avoid short-circuit electronic signals or change in the signal characteristics of sensitive, high-speed electronic devices, such as Central Processing Unit (CPU)s and memory modules. The liquid must also be completely noncorrosive and avoid any sort of damage to electronic packaging, contacts, or printed wet or dry circuit layouts. The liquid must be nonflammable, nontoxic, and easy to clean up if there is a spill. Immersion cooling mainly work in baths of mineral oil, and companies that have developed liquids such as Novec, which meet the criteria for electronic immersion cooling [25].

Mehpoya et al. [26] investigated optimal design of solid oxide fuel cell-gas turbine power plant, Rankine steam cycle and ammonia-water absorption refrigeration. Results indicate that electrical efficiency of the combined system is 62.4% Lower Heating Value (LHV). Produced refrigeration (at 10°C) and heat recovery are 101kW and 22.1kW respectively. In [27], Rokni studied solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) system integrated with an absorption chiller for special applications such as hotels, resorts, hospitals, etc. with a focus on plant design and performance. The proposal system is based on the idea of gasifying the municipal waste, producing syngas serving as fuel for the trigeneration system. It is shown that the energy efficiency of such small tri-generation system is more than 83% with net power of 170kW and district energy of about 250W. Tian et al. [28] proposed and investigated an integrated SOFC system, an ORC, and an ammonia water absorption chiller with a CO₂ capture system is proposed and investigated. The results show that the net electrical efficiency and the exergy efficiency of the integrated system can reach 52.83% and 59.96%, respectively. The trigeneration efficiencies of the combined system without and with CO₂ capture are 74.28% and 72.23%, respectively.

output of a fuel cell stack for the first time at the NFCRC in University of California, Irvine [36]. Etemadieh [37] looked into using SOFC system for data center application. Later, Microsoft started a new Advanced Energy Lab in Seattle, Washington to power 20 data center racks directly from DC power of SOFC systems [38]. Direct highly efficient power generation at the rack level removes the need for complex power distribution systems, reduces costs significantly, and allows decentralized architecture. Having shown [39] that the desired reliability is achievable through well-designed distributed fuel cell power systems, backup power sources are no longer required. National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [40] recently have started looking at rack level powered data centers using PEM fuel cells while producing hydrogen fuel for fuel cells by on site electrolysis using renewable resources.

1.6 Overview

Combined cooling heat and power systems are most effective when used in applications with positively correlated electric and thermal loads and when the combination of generator and ancillary thermal equipment have high individual efficiency ratings. Of all distributed level generators, the SOFC is arguably the most efficient generator that is commercially available. SOFC exhaust gas temperatures are sufficient to drive ancillary absorption chilling or liquid desiccant dehumidification systems, providing electricity, cooling, and dehumidification when powered by a SOFC system. Two potential configurations (SOFC + absorption chiller or SOFC + liquid desiccant dehumidification system) could potentially reduce the total energy intensity of data center operations, reducing carbon and pollutant emissions.

Figure 7: Schematics of CCHP systems considered in this work: (a) SOFC paired with an absorption chiller, and (b) SOFC paired with a liquid desiccant dehumidification system

Our solution for reducing the energy intensity of data center operations is using small scale SOFCs for rack level power generation, which is capable of delivering uninterrupted, 24×7 power that is resilient and clean and eliminates the need for back up generation (due to the limited failure domain associated with a single rack) and is also able to provide high quality heat to run an absorption chiller that replaces a conventional electrical chiller, or a liquid desiccant dehumidification system to provide cooled and dehumidified air for servers. Generating power on-site, at the point of consumption, rather than centrally, eliminate the cost, complexity, interdependencies, and inefficiencies associated with electrical transmission and distribution. Providing the required cooling for servers through absorption chilling (AC) or liquid desiccant dehumidification (LDD) run by high quality exhaust of SOFC has the potential to decrease the power consumption of data centers by up to 40%.

In this research, we experimentally investigate the pairing of a SOFC with an absorption chiller to evaluate the physical performance of both systems. Then we model the integration of rack level fuel cell powered servers with an absorption chiller or liquid desiccant dehumidifier

technology that can be dynamically dispatched to produce electricity and cooling in various amounts to meet power and air conditioning demands of data centers. This modeling work focusses first on evaluating the integrated system concept and to assess the achievable air conditioning from SOFC waste heat with a high efficiency AC. First, simplified SOFC models are paired with a triple-effect AC to explore the techno-economic viability of this design. Then, to explore the feasibility of thermally integrating SOFC with LDD, a spatially resolved physical model developed in Matlab is used to simulate the operating characteristics of this SOFC system. A corresponding physical model is developed to simulate the liquid desiccant air conditioner for dehumidification. This study considers SOFC systems capable of powering a 1. single server rack (~12kW) and the operation of an LDD for cooling and dehumidification of that same rack, and 2. SOFC and LDD systems designed for a row of 20 servers. The LDD operation is based on distributed waste heat from SOFC that powers the servers. The analysis will indicate whether waste-heat based cooling and dehumidification is capable of powering the servers and maintaining server operating temperatures and humidity in the safe range for different weather conditions. LDD modeling receives more attention in this work since there is an existing body of SOFC + AC integration literature already available.

Even though SOFC technology offers several advantages such as fuel flexibility, high efficiency, and zero criteria pollutant emissions, cost and durability are major challenges associated with current SOFC technology. Durability of SOFC technology is a key aspect for its commercialization and long-lasting deployment in different applications. Dynamic operating conditions have considerable effects on the long-term performance and durability of SOFC systems. On the other hand, while many studies have focused on green hydrogen produced through electrolysis from sun and wind, as a clean fuel for fuel cells, the biggest challenge for using hydrogen as an energy carrier is the very high pressure or very low temperature required for its storage, transmission and distribution, which makes the need for a more dense liquid energy carrier like ammonia inevitable. We propose that ammonia made in a sustainable way (e.g., from renewable electricity that powers electrolyzers to produce hydrogen that is reacted with nitrogen to produce ammonia) can serve as a sustainable, low-cost, and high-density energy carrier and the fuel for SOFC systems in the future.

1.7 Overall Project Goal

The goal of this work is to evaluate the integration of SOFC with Absorption Chilling (AC) or with Liquid Desiccant Air Conditioning (LDAC) for efficient, reliable, and grid-independent data center power and cooling. The integrated system will supply electricity and cooling to data center applications. This configuration offers the potential for high energy efficiency, environmental and economic benefits. The integrated concept is shown in Figure 8. The SOFC generates electricity from natural gas which is used directly for powering a rack of servers. The SOFC thermal exhaust will be used to produce hot water which is used for regenerating the liquid desiccant. Concentrated liquid desiccant will be stored and is used for dehumidifying the air when there is a cooling demand. The integrated system is expected to have high efficiency, low emission and provide reliable power and cooling for data center applications. This integrated configuration

eliminates grid connection and any transmission line for powering servers as well as significantly decreasing the electric power used for providing cooling to servers.

Figure 8. integrated SOFC- Absorption-Chilling and/or Liquid Desiccant Air Conditioning (LDAC) concept for servers in data centers.

2. Data Center Cooling Demand

Modern data centers try to use adiabatic cooling whenever the weather condition allows. However, adiabatic cooling is not possible in all locations. Different types of common data center cooling were presented in chapter 2. This chapter presents the method for calculating the cooling demand of data center at various locations. Also, the cooling demand for seven different data center location that are the case study of this research are analyzed.

In order to calculate the amount of cooling required for data center a MATLAB model has been developed which calculates the amount of cooling required by data center. The inputs of the model are weather data associated with data center locations including temperature, pressure, and relative humidity. The weather data are obtained from Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) from 2006 to 2016. Another model comprises of multiple functions has been developed for calculating

thermodynamic parameters such as saturated temperature, wet bulb, and dew point based on the knowns weather data.

In order to calculate the load, the acceptable weather condition for data center is required. ASHRAE is the association that updates and releases this standard every couple of years, based on industry technology improvements. Table 1 shows the boundaries that define the ASHRAE recommended and allowable environmental envelopes [17].

Table 1. ASHRAE 2016 Thermal Guidelines [17].

	Recommended Envelope	Allowable Envelope
Max Dry Bulb	27°C	32°C
Dew Point	5.5 – 15°C	5.5 – 18°C
Relative Humidity	60%	80%

Based on outside weather data, cooling zones for data center is defined in 4 regions based on ASHRAE recommendations [41], [42] as presented in Table 2. The model calculates the number of hours that the system needs mechanical cooling for each of the location using the weather data.

Table 2. Zone Boundaries for Recommended Environmental Envelope for IT Equipment.

	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4
Cooling Strategy	Economizer	Economizer+ Evap. Cooling	Evap. Cooling	Mechanical Cooling
Low end Temperature	NA	NA	If DP < 5.5°C DP Then 10.8°C WB (51.4°F) and 18°C DP (64.4°F) Else 32°C	18.7°C WB
High end Temperature	32°C WB	10.8°C WB	18.7°C WB (65.6°F)	NA
Low end Moisture	5.5°C DP	NA	Na	18°C DP
High end Moisture	18°C DP	5.5°C DP	If DB < 32°C DB Then DB < 5.5°C DP Else 18°C DP	NA

2.1 Data Center modeling

In order to calculate the power consumption of the data center first the IT equipment's power consumption is calculated by the model presented by [43]. For a homogeneous server cluster:

$$U = 1/N \sum_{i=1}^N u_i \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where U is utilization, N number of servers, u_i each server utilization. The server utilization can be given to the model either as a constant number or utilization profile if

available. Servers use half of the rated power in idle model and linearly increase with utilization [43], server power consumption is calculated by:

$$P_i = P_i^{idle} + (p_i^{peak} - P_i^{idle}) \cdot u_i \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The total power consumption is:

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

It is not practical to measure the actual power consumption of each server rack continuously. As a result, the impact of task consolidation (L) for the running servers is modelled as:

$L=0$: perfect consolidation, meaning that workload is packed onto the minimum number of running servers.

$L=1$: workload is distributed uniformly so $U = u_i$

$$u_i = \frac{U}{L(1 - U) + U} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

The main components are power loss are the UPS and the PDUs which can be calculated as follows:

$$P_{PDU} = P_{PDU}^{idle} + \lambda_{PDY} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N p_i \right)^2 \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$P_{UPS} = P_{UPS}^{idle} + \lambda_{UPS} \sum_{PDU_s} P_{PDU} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

Where λ_{PDY} and λ_{UPS} are the loss coefficients for UPS and Power Distribution Unit (PDU) respectively. In power supply equipment of a data center the power loss can be up to 15% of the total power consumption at peak [43]. The air flow needed for server cooling is calculated based on the following equation:

$$F_{air} = \frac{DC_{size} \times Util}{C_{p\ air} \times \Delta T \times \eta_{heat}} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

DC_{size} represent the capacity of data center, $Util$ is utilization factor for data center, $C_{p,air}$ is the air specific heat, ΔT is the temperature difference for the air inlet and outlet from the server, η_{heat} is efficiency of heat removal.

Data center total power demand is defined in the following equation. Miscellaneous power is around 4% of data center designed capacity.

$$P_{tot} = P_{cooling} + P_{server} + P_{PDU} + P_{UPS} + P_{fans} + P_{miscellaneous} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

In cooling zone 4, cooling power can be calculated either for a water-cooled chiller or an air-cooled chiller. For air cooled chiller, the chiller presented at [44] is used as the reference chiller for calculating the chiller's power demand. Table 3 shows the effect of dry bulb temperature on chillers efficiency.

Table 3. effect of dry bulb temperature on air cooled chillers efficiency.

DB [°F]	75	85	95	105
Efficiency [kW/Ton]	0.952	1.069	1.208	1.384

For water cooled chiller, the chiller presented in [45] is used as the reference chiller for calculating the chiller's power demand. The effect of wet bulb on chillers efficiency is shows on the Table 4 [46].

Table 4. effect of dry bulb temperature on water cooled chillers efficiency.

WB [°F]	60	65	70	75
Efficiency [kW/Ton]	0.502	0.518	0.574	0.592

2.2 Data Center cooling demand results

In order to calculate the number of hours that data center in each location need mechanical cooling, TMY data for seven locations in the United States that is home to Microsoft data center has been used as the input for the code. The number of hours of each cooling type that is required in each location based on both allowable and recommended envelope is shown in Figure 9. As expected, by expanding the range of temperature and humidity, the number of hours that mechanical cooling is required decreases. For data centers located in California, Seattle, and Wyoming a mechanical cooling is barely required, economizer and evaporative cooling will be sufficient throughout the year to keep the servers in acceptable range. However, Illinois, Iowa, Virginia and Texas require between 1000hr to 4500hr of mechanical cooling based on the location and ASHRAE requirements.

Figure 9. Cooling system type for 7 locations based on ASHRAE recommended (left bar) & allowable (right bar) range.

Servers load profile is highly confidential information that is rarely published. However, the profile is roughly constant and utilization changes between 60% to 80%. For these results, either NREL published server load profiles as shown in Figure 10 [41] is used by scaling it to the size of targeted data center, or it is assumed that the utilization is constant at 70% throughout the entire time.

**Figure 10. Load profile for the RSF data center over the first 11 months of operations
Illustration by Chad Lobato, NREL[41].**

The following result for each location is based on the assumption of a 50MW designed data center that follows the load demand of [41]. The designed temperature difference of air entering and leaving the servers is 15°C. The number of cooling hours and cooling device correspondent to that is based on ASHRAE recommended envelope. The mechanical cooling system in these results is assumed air cooled chiller. Figure 11 to Figure 14 show the results for California and Texas which are the two ends of the spectrum with California being the location with the lowest overall energy use and Texas the highest.

Figure 11 shows the TMY (average data from 2006 to 2016) dry bulb and wet bulb temperature for California and Texas which are the parameters that determine what type of cooling is required for the data center. California and Texas average dry bulb temperature is 14°C and 20.2°C and wet bulb temperature is 11.6°C and 15°C, respectively.

Figure 11. TMY data for California and Texas throughout the year.

Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the power demand breakdown and percentage of each category for California and Texas, respectively. As expected, for Texas half of the year mechanical cooling is required to keep the servers in the range, however for California the number of hour that mechanical cooling is 186hr. As a result, 9% of power consumed by data centers is dedicated to mechanical cooling device for this scenario in Texas, while for California the number is 1%.

Figure 12. Data Center power demand breakdown throughout a year for California and Texas.

Figure 13. Data Center power demand percentage for California and Texas.

PUE is the ratio of total energy used by facility to energy used by servers. This parameter shows how effectively data center uses energy. As the number get closer to 1 it means that the

facility is very efficient, and more energy is directly being used for servers. The following two graphs shows the PUE for the entire year. The spikes are because of energy being consumed by mechanical coolers. The average PUE for California and Texas is 1.16 and 1.32 respectively.

Figure 14. PUE for California and Texas for the entire year.

The results for the TMY data, Power usage breakdown, percentage of energy usage, and PUE for the other 5 locations are presented in the dissertation of Maryam Asghari.

Figure 15 shows energy use for each location for a 50MW designed data center following Figure 10 load demand. The air temperature difference is 15°C and ASHRAE 2016 standards is followed for temperature and humidity limits. Table 5 shows the average PUE for all the locations with California having the lowest PUE at 1.167 and Texas the highest at 1.315.

Figure 15. Data center energy usage for a 50MW data center.

Table 5. Average PUE for 7 data center target location.

Location	California	Seattle	Wyoming	Illinois	Iowa	Virginia	Texas
PUE	1.167	1.18	1.179	1.225	1.23	1.244	1.315

The type of cooling system, designed temperature difference, and changing allowable range has a significant effect on the amount of energy that data center consumes. For example, as the technology is rising IT manufacturers are pushing the boundaries on safe temperature that IT equipment’s can tolerate. Figure 16 and Table 6 show the energy used and percentage consumed by different part of data center for various combinations. Water cooled system use less energy than air cooled system. Increasing the temperature difference for the air entering and leaving the server room means less flow of air is required, which leads to less energy required for cooling the air. As the IT technology progresses, the IT equipment can tolerate higher temperature which leads to higher range of acceptable temperature and humidity. This means wider range of outside temperature is acceptable for cooling the server, leading to lower energy usage.

Figure 16. Energy consumed by different part of data center for various combinations.

Table 6. percentage of energy consumed by different part of data center for various combinations.

PUE	1.244	1.271	1.272	1.274	1.302	1.303	1.314	1.345
Energy (*e8 MWh)	4.6	4.699	4.70	4.71	4.81	4.82	4.86	4.97
Fan+Pump (%)	4	6	5	4	6	7	5	7
Mechanical Cooling (%)	5	5	6	7	7	6	9	9
Server (%)	80	79	79	78	77	77	76	74

2.3 Summary

In this chapter, a data center cooling model has been developed to calculate the amount of cooling required by data center. The model takes the weather data for each location and acceptable range of temperature and humidity for data center to calculate the load. In addition, the cooling demand for California, Seattle, Wyoming, Illinois, Iowa, Virginia, and Texas have been calculated and analyzes. Texas had the highest cooling demand with a PUE of 1.315 and California had the lowest with a PUE of 1.167. Energy usage of data center based on different types of cooling device (water cooled, air cooled) and at different designed temperature difference has been compared. Results showed that higher temperature difference and water-cooled system lead to less energy consumed by the cooling system.

3. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consists of a series of SOFC systems and an absorption chiller. In total, 12 kW of SOFC electrical capacity is required to provide sufficient power to a server rack, and to provide heat to power the absorption chiller used in these experiments. A series of fuel cells are used over an individual fuel cell due to differences in commercial SOFC capacity versus – there is no commercially available SOFC in the 10 kW class. Instead, eight 1.5 kW SOFC systems are used. The purpose of the experimental setup is to determine SOFC and AC performance characteristics and to evaluate SOFC degradation.

3.1 BlueGEN SOFC Systems

The SOFC system that was selected was the BlueGEN SOFC cogeneration system from Solid Power, which was the only manufacturer willing to deliver an SOFC system to us in the appropriate size class (at the time, 2019). Each BlueGEN system produces 1.5 kW of electricity and runs on natural gas. These systems are designed as residential appliances and are roughly 1m x 0.6m x 0.6m. The system package is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. BlueGEN System.

The BlueGEN systems operate at a nominal thermal efficiency of 62% with the potential for further utility in an optional hot water supply loop that can provide hot water to a residence.

To meet the single server rack scale selected for the laboratory setup, an array of eight BlueGEN systems was obtained to provide a total of 12 kW to offset the electrical consumption of the servers. All eight BlueGEN systems are connected to a common electrical source which then provides the power to the server rack. The system is supported by the electrical grid of the laboratory because the internal inverters in the BlueGEN systems require a valid grid connection to operate and constructing an electrical island with proper load balancing is outside of the scope of this experiment.

3.2 BlueGEN SOFC Operation

The BlueGEN SOFC systems are semi-autonomous systems operated remotely by the manufacturer, Solid Power. Each BlueGEN system has independent operational controls built in to maintain the desired fuel utilization and power output. These controls are not accessible for

adjustment within this experiment, so all testing where manipulation of these parameters is necessary require contact with the manufacturer.

The only controllable parameter for these systems is the power output level of the BlueGEN systems which is adjustable in an online portal where the power output profile is adjustable as a constant or based on a schedule. Using this interface, the BlueGEN systems were exercised through a set power profile designed to explore the full range of power outputs and indirectly the fuel utilization. The results of this exercise are discussed later in the results section.

Figure 18 shows the experimental schematic of the integrated system which consists of eight BlueGEN SOFC, the dehumidification unit, server, waste heat recovery unit and a heater. The system includes a heater for the cases that the fuel cell is not able to produce enough heat for the regeneration system and for startup of the system. The eight BlueGEN exhaust gas are combined in one duct, and then go through the heater if needed and then produces hot water in the water heat recovery loop. The hot water is then pumped to the regenerator. Preconditioned air goes through the dehumidifier to produce dehumidified air, then it goes through indirect evaporative cooler to cool the air sensibly and then it goes to server.

Figure 18. Experiment set up concept schematic.

3.3 SOFC system

The SOFC system installed at NFCRC are BlueGEN cogeneration system. BlueGEN is a commercially available CHP unit, built and sold by SOLIDpower. Figure 19 shows the eight BlueGEN units in the NFCRC laboratory. Operating on natural gas, the unit can produce power modulated from 500We (25%) to 2kWe (100%); however, it achieves its highest net electrical efficiency of 62% at a 1.5kWe output. The BlueGEN systems are operated and controlled remotely by SOLIDpower. However, through an online human machine interface, the power output profile and as a result fuel utilization are controllable by user. To be able to install the BlueGEN we need to provide six connections: fuel (natural gas), electrical, flue gas, internet, water, and drain connections.

Figure 19. BlueGEN system in NFCRC laboratory.

Natural gas connection:

BlueGEN requires an uninterrupted supply of natural gas, and it only operates on the second family of gases (methane-based gases). Gas supply pressure to the BlueGEN appliance must be 9–20mbar (0.9–2kPa) so an Elster Jeavons (J78R) gas pressure regulator is used to avoid fluctuations due to variations in the main gas supply pressure.

Electrical connection:

The BlueGEN systems require an electrical connection to successfully operate during startup and to export the electricity produced during normal operation. For electrical connection the grid availability is 208VAC 3 phase, 60 hertz. Each fuel cell needs 120VAC 1 phase, 60 hertz. 3 transformers are used where two of them provide electrical connection needed for six blueGENs and one of them runs two BlueGENs.

Water and drain connection:

The main water supply pressure must be at least 1bar (100kPa) and no more than 10bar (1000kPa). During operation, the appliance can consume up to 30litres of water per day, depending on heat and condensate recovery. The BlueGEN appliance has an internal water storage tank for the process water and this tank will fill from the main water supply intermittently. The water consumption rate may be up to 1 liter per minute when this tank is filling. Operation of water needs to be uninterrupted. Wastewater is ejected from the BlueGEN appliance under pressure (0–1bar or 0–100 kPa).

The main water supply connection, drain, and overflow rejection connection configuration can be seen in Figure 20. Water is distributed in a manifold to each fuel cell line and each fuel cell has its own valve for water shut down. For water rejection line, overflow and wastewater will be collected in a tank through a sloped pipe and then will be pumped to the drain. Figure 21 and Figure 22 show pump used for fuel cell water rejection connection, manifold, and valves for fuel cell supply water respectively.

Figure 20. Water connections schematic.

Figure 21. Pump used for fuel cell water rejection connection.

Figure 22. Manifold and valves for fuel cell supply water.

Exhaust connection:

The air pipe material can be aluminum, stainless steel, galvanized steel, or polypropylene pipes. It is not allowed to use PVC or any glue for the air pipe. The maximum exhaust temperature can go up to be 200°C. The exhaust connections are made on the top of the BlueGEN systems and are connected via double-walled 4inch ducting as shown in Figure 23. The laboratory facility runs a dedicated exhaust port available in the lab space which maintains a constant negative pressure, ensuring continuous flow. Shows the exhaust duct manifold infrastructure.

Figure 23. BlueGEN exhaust manifold.

3.4 Internet connection

BlueGEN must be connected to an appropriate uninterrupted and reliable internet connection. To facilitate this connection, a micro network was setup within the laboratory which includes all the eight BlueGEN systems as well as the servers within the server rack. The network is connected behind a Sonic Wall which provides the connectivity and the protection for the systems.

3.5 Server rack

Figure 24 shows the server rack in the NFCRC provided by Microsoft. The server rack consists of twenty-one HP 380E servers and during the full load needs up to 15kW power. Each server has 2 CPU and each of them has 6 cores. Each server has 96GB RAM and 25 hard drive with each 600k bite. A 24 port ethernet switch has been mounted on the server rack for the network connection.

Figure 24. Server rack at NFCRC laboratory

The servers are powered by a 208 VAC server configured power strip. The power strip has three banks of seven computer power ports which connect to one of the two power supplies in each computer. The power strip is plugged into a non-NEMA 50A style C outlet which is rated for the electrical input of up to 43.7 A. This disconnect allows for moving the server rack and modularity in the future. The outlet is connected to the three phase distribution panel to which the BlueGEN systems are also connected. See Figure 10 for details.

To operate the servers in a manner that simulates real world operation, it is necessary to run a benchmarking software on the servers. The benchmarking software artificially exercises the internal systems to determine their performance. For the purposes of this experiment, the exercise allows for full thermal loading of the servers simulating full load. Additionally, the software will allow for all the servers to be exercised and controlled remotely as a cluster simplifying the user operation.

To operate the servers at full load, they must receive sufficient airflow through them to maintain an acceptable temperature gradient. The maximum temperature gradient allowed across the servers is 25 °C (45 °F) with a maximum outlet temperature of 45°C (113 °F). To prevent this, an airflow rate of 3567 m³/hr. (2100 CFM) through the server rack is required. This airflow is produced within the process air stream by an in-duct fan.

To connect the server rack to the absorption chiller test stand, a custom square duct was designed in AutoCAD. The mounting points for the blower, cold air heat exchanger and server

rack were predetermined, and the ducting shape was designed to minimize pressure loss through it. The finalized design is shown Figure 37.

Figure 25. Custom Process Air Ducting.

The custom ducting does contain a hard ninety degree turn, but it is impossible to soften this turn due to the placement of the chiller within that slot. In the future, it may prove advantageous to install guiding vanes to better direct the air through this turn. The flanges on both sides facilitate the connection to the cold water heat exchanger and the server rack. The ducting was then fabricated in 24 gauge sheet steel since the internal pressures are quite low. The ducting was then installed on the test stand and can be seen in Figure 25.

Figure 26. Process Air Ducting Installed on Absorption Chiller Test Stand.

To achieve the required airflow through the server rack as mentioned above, a duct fan was selected. The duct fan was sized to be able to achieve the necessary airflow through the sized ducting considering the pressure drop across the cold water heat exchanger. The duct fan runs on a 0.55 kW (0.75 hp) electrical motor which is also controlled by an independent VFD. The duct fan is shown in the top right of Figure 25 and during its installation in Figure 26.

Figure 27. Process Air Duct Fan.

To measure flow and temperature profiles within the ducting, a hot wire anemometer thermocouple probe is utilized at specific points. The points are predetermined based on the ducting size and shape.

3.6 Absorption Chiller System

To test the integration of SOFC systems with absorption technology experimentally, it was necessary to design and construct a laboratory scale absorption chilling system. The absorption chiller test stand should allow for operation of an absorption chiller off the exhaust or simulated exhaust gasses of an SOFC. Additionally, the test stand must allow for incremental control of all operating parameters, allowing for experimental control and exploration. Lastly, the test stand should be constructed in such a way as to allow for integration with multiple fuel cell systems for future testing.

3.6.1 Absorption Chiller

The key component of the absorption chiller test stand is indeed the absorption chiller itself. A commercially produced absorption chiller was selected since the technology is already readily available and to expedite the construction of the test stand. Therefore, significant effort went into selecting an appropriate system which could deliver the necessary cooling capacity for one server rack, 15 kW, as well as run on the SOFC exhaust gasses.

Currently, there are two popular types of absorption chillers differentiated by the working fluid they employ to achieve cooling. The first is a Lithium Bromide absorption chiller which operates using aqueous LiBr and can only achieve chilling above freezing since water is the refrigeration working fluid. The second type is a water-ammonia absorption chiller where the ammonia acts as refrigerant working fluid and can therefore achieve chilling below freezing. However, water-ammonia systems require additional steps such as rectification after desorbing to operate and pose the risk of toxic exposure in the event of a leak. Due to these challenges along with the fact that sub-freezing chilling is not necessary for server cooling, a LiBr absorption chiller was selected for this experiment.

The absorption chiller selected for this experiment is a Yazaki WFC-SC5 LiBr chiller. The WFC-SC5 is a 5 refrigeration-ton chiller (~18 kW) and is the smallest commercially available LiBr absorption chiller on the market. The WFC indication refers to the “water fired chiller” meaning that the heat input is in the form of hot water delivered to the chiller. This allows for the design and customization of the exhaust heat exchanger, which will be discussed later. Additionally, the implementation of water loops to carry the thermal inputs and outputs of the test stand are relatively simple and inexpensive to construct. The chiller is shown in Figure 27 Note the ports for water loop inputs, but no connections at the time of the photo.

Figure 28. Yazaki WFC-SC5 LiBr Absorption Chiller.

3.6.2 Hot Water Loop

The hot water loop is the first of three water loops that facilitate the thermal inputs and outputs of the absorption chiller. The hot water loop captures heat from the exhaust gasses and delivers it to the desorber of the absorption chiller. The specified flow and temperature rating for the absorption chiller are 72 L/min (19 GPM) and 70-95 °C (158-203 °F). The loop is constructed from 1" copper pipe for a maximum flow velocity of 2.36 m/s (7.74 ft/s) to minimize pressure loss. The piping is joined using silver solder and all components are connected using unions to facilitate maintenance, changes or moving of the test stand. The piping is also wrapped in one-inch foam insulation to minimize heat loss to ambient. The hot water loop is pictured in Figure 28 along with the exhaust heat exchanger and heater to which it is connected.

Figure 29. Hot Water Loop with Exhaust Heat Exchanger.

The principal component of the hot water loop is the exhaust heat exchanger which enables waste heat recovery from the SOFC exhaust or the simulated exhaust. To select the exhaust heat exchanger, it was necessary to ensure that the selected component would provide ample heat transfer to the water while minimizing the pressure losses within the exhaust. To meet the second criteria and due to the large commercial availability, a shell and tube heat exchanger with no baffles in the exhaust pathway was selected.

The primary supplier of exhaust heat exchangers that meet both the heat transfer and size criteria for this experiment is EJ Bowman who offer a variety of products that match our description. To fully specify the exhaust heat exchanger before ordering, a mechanistic thermodynamic model was constructed to size the heat exchanger.

Using this methodology, the different options for heat exchanger from the manufacturer were evaluated. The final selection was the model 6-32-3741-5 which produced 24.49 kW of heat transfer from the exhaust to the water stream at maximum thermal input.

The hot water pump provides the flow for the hot water loop, pushing water through the exhaust heat exchanger and then through the absorption chiller's desorber to power the chiller. The pump was selected using two criteria: ability to meet the flowrate required and the ability to operate with water at temperatures up to 100 °C (212 °F). To estimate the flow capacity of the pump, it was necessary to estimate the pressure drop within the hot water loop. Based on the technical specifications provided by EJ Bowman based on the selected 3741-5 heat exchanger, the pressure

drop across the shell side is 0.4 kPa (0.058 psi). Additionally, the WFC-SC5 chiller lists the pressure drop in the desorber as 69 kPa (10.01 psi).

To meet the pressure drop requirement and temperature requirements stated, a stainless steel pump for chemicals was specified and is shown in Figure 29.

Figure 30. Hot Water Loop Pump.

The hot water pump also needed to be compatible with a variable frequency drive (VFD) to remotely control the speed. The VFD selected was an Automation Direct GS2-22P0, capable of running up to a 2 HP three-phase motor. The VFD allows for remote enabling and speed control for fine tuning of the system from the test stand monitor. The VFDs and their controls will be discussed in detail later.

To ensure proper and safe operation of the hot water loop, several other components were installed in the hot water loop. The first is an air-pressure-balanced expansion tank which allows for thermal expansion of the working fluid and can be adjusted to meet the internal pressures experienced by the hot water loop. The second is a pressure relief valve which protects the loop and the desorber internal structure from excessive pressure by venting the water should an over pressure occur. These two systems help protect the operation of the system and are specified by the plumbing diagrams included in the absorption chiller manual.

Additionally, a software “boil protection” safety loop was designed to monitor the thermocouples installed in the hot loop and shuts down the supplemental heater if the loop comes too close to boiling.

3.6.3 Cold Water Loop

The cold-water loop is the second thermal input to the absorption chiller. Similar to the hot water loop, it captures heat from the process air and then delivers that heat to the evaporator in the absorption chiller. The specified flow and temperature outlet for the cold water loop are: 45.8 L/min (12.1 GPM) and 7 °C (44.6 °F). The loop is constructed from 1” copper pipe for a maximum

flow velocity of 1.5 m/s (4.9 ft/s) to minimize pressure loss. The piping is joined using silver solder and all components are connected using unions to facilitate maintenance, changes or moving of the test stand. The piping is also wrapped in one-inch foam insulation to minimize heat loss to ambient. The cold water loop is pictured in Figure 30 along with the exhaust heat exchanger and heater to which it is connected.

Figure 31. Cold Water Loop and Duct Heat Exchanger.

The principal component of the cold water loop is the process air heat exchanger which captures heat from air within the process air duct and transfers it to the evaporator within the absorption chiller. The process air heat exchanger was selected in the tube and fin design due to its effectiveness in water to air heat transfer and its availability. The ducting sizing was determined based on the process airflow requirements and is discussed later. For the purposes of sizing the process air heat exchanger, the duct was assumed to be a square duct with dimensions of 0.6 x 0.6 m (2 x 2 ft) with an airflow rate of 3565 m³/hr. (2100 CFM). Additionally, the cold water flow from the absorption chiller was assumed based on the technical specifications of the chiller at 45.8 L/min (12.1 GPM) and 7 °C (44.6 °F). The final process air heat exchanger is shown in Figure 31 with five banks of tubes resulting in a width of 10 inches.

Figure 32. Process Air Heat Exchanger.

The process air heat exchanger was then installed within the process air ducting on top of the absorption chiller test stand. The layout of this setup will be discussed later in the server rack ducting section of this chapter.

Similar to the hot water loop pump, the cold water pump was specified to meet the requirements of achieving the necessary flow rate through the process air heat exchanger, chiller evaporator, and the plumbing. The temperature requirement for the cold water pump also corresponded to the lower temperature range with temperatures as low as 7 °C (44.6 °F).

The pressure drop through the cold water loop was calculated similarly to the hot water loop accounting for the measured pressure drop through the process air heat exchanger of 5.95 kPa (0.86 psi) and the measured pressure drop through the chiller evaporator of 52.6 kPa (7.6 psi).

The total pressure drop across the cold water loop was calculated to be ~125 kPa (18.12 psi), so a $\frac{3}{4}$ horsepower water circulation pump that could achieve the necessary 45.8 L/min (12.1 GPM) at the estimated pressure drop was selected. The cold water pump is shown in Figure 32.

Figure 33. Cold Water Pump.

The cold water pump also needed to be compatible with a VFD to remotely control the speed. The VFD selected was an Automation Direct GS2-21P0, capable of running up to a 1 HP three-phase motor. The VFD allows for remote enabling and speed control for fine tuning of the system from the test stand monitor. The VFDs and their controls will be discussed in detail later.

To ensure proper and safe operation of the cold water loop, several other components were installed in the cold water loop. The first is an air-pressure-balanced expansion tank which allows for thermal contraction of the working fluid and can be adjusted to meet the internal pressures experienced by the cold water loop. The second is a pressure relief valve which protects the loop and the desorber internal structure from excessive pressure by venting the water should an over pressure occur. These two systems help protect the operation of the system and are specified by the plumbing diagrams included in the absorption chiller manual.

Additionally, a software “freeze protection” safety loop was designed to monitor the thermocouples installed in the cold loop and shuts down the supplemental chiller if the loop comes too close to freezing.

3.6.4 Cooling Water Loop

The final thermal connection to the absorption chiller is the cooling water loop which absorbs heat from the absorption chiller’s absorber and condenser and then rejects it to the ambient. The cooling loop is the largest of the three water loops since it must carry the summation of both the cold water and hot water thermal inputs out to the ambient.

The specified flow and temperatures for the cooling water loop are: 156 L/min (44.2 GPM), 31 °C (87.8 °F) at the inlet and 35 °C (95 °F) at the outlet of the chiller. The loop is constructed from 2” PVC pipe for a maximum flow velocity of 1.37 m/s (4.49 ft/s) to minimize pressure loss. The piping is joined using PVC cement and all components are connected using unions to facilitate maintenance, changes or moving of the test stand. The cooling water loop passes through two walls to reach the exterior of the laboratory facility. No insulation is installed on the cooling water loop because any heat loss to ambient will benefit the cooling capacity of the cooling tower and temperature measurements are made close enough to the chiller to minimize error. Part of the cooling water loop is pictured in Figure 33 along with the cooling tower and pump while the PVC connections to the absorption chiller are shown previously in Figure 30.

Figure 34: Exterior Cooling Water Loop with Cooling Tower.

To facilitate the heat rejection to ambient, an evaporative cooling water tower was selected as the most conventional and cost effective method. Additionally, the chiller was specified to match a standard size of evaporative cooling tower which simplifies the design.

The cooling tower rejects heat to the ambient air using evaporation of the water within the cooling water loop. The internal structure of the cooling tower is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 35: Cooling Tower Internal Structure Schematic.

The outlet of the cooling tower is indicated by number 22 and is in the middle of the bottom reservoir to minimize debris entrance to the cooling tower loop. An additional filter is placed over the outlet to further protect the components from debris. The inlet of the cooling tower is located next to the outlet, but the water is pumped up central shaft, number 8, to the rotors, number 9, where the water is sprayed over the cooling matrix, number 13, which allows the water to fall slowly in opposite flow to the air which is being pulled up the tower by the fan, number 1. The dry air enters through a grating, number 17, and absorbs evaporating water as it falls down the matrix facilitating the cooling of the water.

Using the methodology stated above, the cooling tower is able to achieve a maximum heat rejection of 65.9 kW (225,000 Btu/hr.) at the specified flow rate and inlet temperature of 156 L/min (44.2 GPM), 31 °C (87.8 °F).

The cooling tower pump was selected to achieve the required flow rate for the cooling water loop. The first cooling tower pump specified was selected in conjunction with the cooling tower and rated for the continuous flow rate required by the system and is shown in Figure 35 next to the cooling tower.

Figure 36: First Cooling Tower Pump.

The cooling water pump was based on a 1.5 horsepower motor configured for 1 phase connections to 120 VAC or 230 VAC. During the initial operation of the test stand this pump was connected to a standard 120 VAC outlet which was protected by a 20 A circuit breaker. However, during multi-hour tests, the pump would trip the circuit breaker, causing a fault to the chiller system. To remedy the issue, the pump was then configured to a 208 VAC disconnect. When running the pump on 208 VAC the pump was expected to pull 6.7 A maximum and was therefore fused at 10 A using two time delay fuses. This setup allowed the pump to operate for only two minutes before the fuses were blown. Upon further inspection, it was determined that the motor windings had been either delivered damaged or damaged during testing since the internal resistance of two of the windings were significantly lower than the third indicating a motor short.

A replacement cooling water pump was specified to replace the faulty pump. During the prior testing, it was possible to measure the pressure drop within the cooling water loop using the pressure gauge placed at the outlet of the cooling water pump, shown in Figure 35. This allowed the new pump to be specified to meet the necessary flowrate of 156 L/min (44.2 GPM) at a pressure drop of 172 kPa (25 psi). The selected cooling water pump was a three-phase pump to operate off the 208 VAC three phase available while minimizing the current draw. Additionally, the new pump's electrical configuration allowed for a VFD to be installed to control the flowrate of the cooling water loop. The new pump and VFD are shown in Figure 36 next to the cooling tower.

Figure 37: New Cooling Water Pump with VFD.

Note that a secondary port was placed downstream of the pump to allow priming of the system to minimize the chance of damage to the water pump.

The VFD selected for the cooling water pump was an Automation Direct GS2-22P0, capable of running up to a 2 HP three-phase motor. While the VFD does allow for remote control, this VFD was configured to be manually operated due to its location outside the laboratory facility.

Since the cooling water loop is technically an open loop system, no expansion tanks or pressure relief valves are necessary to safely operate the cooling tower. However, as the cooling tower operates, the water evaporated into the air will reduce the amount of water within the reservoir over time. To counter this effect, a make-up water line is connected to the cooling tower and is controlled by a level float switch. Additionally, a water over-flow valve is installed to protect the cooling tower from overflow.

The cooling tower fan is powered by a connection to a 120VAC outlet nearby the cooling tower and facilitates a soft startup using a capacitor in the power lines.

3.7 Simulated Exhaust System

To completely explore the operation of the absorption chiller, a simulated exhaust system was designed to provide exhaust gasses at alternative temperatures and flow rates. The addition of this system allows the absorption chiller test stand to simulate the exhaust heat of fuel cell systems other than the attached BlueGEN system array.

The simulated exhaust system consists of two primary components, a centrifugal blower which provides controllable flow of air, and an electrical heater which allows for temperature control over the simulated exhaust stream.

3.7.1 Electrical Air Heater

The principal requirement for the electrical heater was the ability to produce hot air at temperatures which simulate the exhaust of a fuel cell system. The temperature and flowrate of the simulated exhaust gasses were calculated for the BlueGEN system bank as well as the minimum input to fully operate the absorption heater. Based on the heat transfer characteristics of the exhaust heat exchanger mentioned above, a simulated exhaust stream would need a maximum capacity of 300 °C (572 °F) at 849 m³/hr. (500 CFM). To create a simulated exhaust stream at this temperature and flowrate from the ambient air, a 75 kW electrical heater is required considering a 1.2 capacity factor.

The electrical heater selected is a Tutco-Farnam Flow Torch 800 and is shown in Figure 37.

Figure 38: Electrical Heater: Flow Torch 800.

The Flow Torch operates as a resistive heater, inducing electrical current in a spiral-wound dual element heater and operates at 480 VAC in a three phase configuration. The Flow Torch heater was configured with two reducing fittings to match the diameters of the blower and the exhaust heat exchanger. Custom flanges were then water jetted to match the bolt hole patterns of each flange and the inner diameter of the heater. Note it was necessary to use custom flanges since the exhaust heat exchanger is configured in metric units while the blower is configured to ANSI specifications. The heater with its modified flanges is shown in Figure 38 with the markings for flange phasing showing prior to welding.

Figure 39: Electric Heater with Custom Flanges.

To seal the flanged faces, a standard Buna-N gasket was used upstream of the heater and a high temperature fiberglass gasket was used downstream where temperatures would be higher.

To operate the Flow Torch 800, a heater controller was also ordered from Tutco-Farnam which was rated for the specified 75 kW heater. The heater controller would allow for steady-state setpoint operation of the heater using downstream thermocouples while also introducing levels of safety. The heater controller is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 40: Heater Controller.

The heater controller has a front facing user interface that allows the operator to set various values including set point, high temperature, and different alarm values. The controller also introduces safety features such as a flow switch shutoff, redundant thermocouple sensor, and a thermal snap switch. These safety features are connected to the rest of the test stand using the data

acquisition and control system. The wiring block diagram for the heater and heater controller are shown in Figure 40.

Figure 41: Electric Heater Block Diagram.

Notice the sensors and safety relay switches mentioned before in the bottom left of the block diagram. Additionally, notice that the heater and controller operate on two separate three phase 480 VAC inputs. The solid state relays (SSR) are shown at the top of the wiring diagram and the heat sinks that dissipate the heat produced are shown in black on the sides of the controller in Figure 40.

To power the heater, two 480 VAC three phase connections with a capacity of 45 amps are necessary. To further protect the system, a set of quick action fuses are required upstream of the heater controller. The wiring diagram designed for the electrical connection is shown in Figure 41.

Figure 42. Heater Grid Connection Wiring Diagram.

The laboratory has a 480 VAC disconnect with 100 A fuses installed and it is from this point of connection that the rest of the wiring was configured. The 100 A lines from the disconnect are broken into two 50 A lines using a distribution block. This facilitates the two connections required by the heater controller and heater. The two three phase lines are then run through a block of 50 A quick-blow fuses. The distribution block and fuses are all located within an electrical enclosure and are shown in Figure 42.

Figure 43. 480 V Disconnect, Distribution Block, and Fuse Blocks.

The distributed and fused wiring is then routed into 1" EMT conduit to protect the wiring as it is connected across the laboratory space. The conduit was sized to maintain a packing factor of no more than 0.5.

Following the completion of the test stand, the experiment was operated for eight consecutive hours, providing steady state data at 27 operating points. However, during this testing the electrical infrastructure for the heater suffered severe damage due to overheating inside the electrical enclosure that houses the distribution block and fuses. No damage to the facility or harm to the operator was sustained outside the enclosure. The enclosure is shown with the sustained damage in Figure 43.

Figure 44. Electrical Failure in Heater Fuse Enclosure.

The failure stems from thermal overloading of the conductors as they were connected to the fuse blocks. It is presumed that the lugs connecting the conductors to the studs were improperly crimped and therefore produced substantial heat. This problem was compounded by the connection to the fuse block which was affixed using the structural integrity of the plastic block base. The initial heat of the crimp connection softened the fuse block base material which allowed the lug to slightly disconnect from the stud creating a smaller contact patch for the electricity to flow through. This reduced contact patch between the lug and the stud created even more heat which ultimately damaged the insulation of the conductor and caused shorting between the lines.

This electrical fault occurred within the time of the authoring of this material so the solution to this issue is currently lacking. However, moving forward all design decisions and construction will be verified and inspected to ensure that this fault does not occur again.

3.7.2 Blower

The second component of the simulated exhaust system is the blower which provides the airflow through the heater at a rate which simulates the exhaust flow of the SOFC systems. Based on the initial BlueGEN model, the minimum exhaust flow rate is required to be ~84.9 m³/hr. (50 CFM). Additionally, the blower must be able to provide up to 849 m³/hr. (500 CFM) as specified by the exhaust heat exchanger model to achieve full chilling capacity within the absorption chiller.

Knowing the pressure drops through the exhaust heat exchanger and the electric heater provided the total pressure drop through the simulated exhaust system since they are directly connected in series. The pressure drop of each is listed in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Simulated Exhaust Pressure Drops.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value(s)</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Simulated Exhaust Max Flow</i>	849 (500)	m ³ /hr. (CFM)
<i>Entry Region Pressure Drop</i>	2.09 (8.426)	kPa (in.wc.)
<i>Electric Heater Pressure Drop</i>	0.57 (2.3)	kPa (in.wc.)
<i>Exhaust Heat Exchanger Pressure Drop</i>	0.7 (2.81)	kPa (in.wc.)
<i>Connections Pressure Drop</i>	1.02 (4.129)	kPa (in.wc.)

Given the pressure drops of each component, it is possible to estimate the overall pressure drop through the simulated exhaust system. Using the values from Table 7 the overall pressure drop is 1.39 kPa (17.6 in.wc.). Based on this information and the required flowrate, a custom blower company, Twin City Blowers, was contacted to consult on the design of an appropriately sized blower. The fan curve provided by them to match the characteristics of our flow requirements is shown in Figure 44 with both static pressure and power draw.

Figure 45. Blower Fan Curve.

The blower was specified for 849 m³/hr. (500 CFM) at 1.39 kPa (17.6 in.wc.) static pressure and the resulting motor power draw is 2.3 kW (3 hp). The blower itself is shown in Figure 45.

Figure 46. Simulated Exhaust Blower.

The blower is a centrifugal blower that can produce 500 CFM of flow across the simulated exhaust system. Note the flanged connection between the blower and the heater which houses the pitot tube used for measuring the flowrate of the simulated exhaust. Discussion of the pitot tube sensor will be done later.

Additionally, the motor driving the blower is connected to a VFD to control the speed, so an AEGIS ring was installed which grounds the blower impeller from the motor and protects the blower from shorts to the casing or other components on the test stand.

3.8 Data Acquisition System and Virtual Interface

The interface selected for monitoring, collecting, and analyzing data is National Instruments LabVIEW. Within LabVIEW a virtual interface (VI) is constructed to operate and monitor the data coming from the sensor array while logging the data for further analysis. The VI designed contains a user interface that mirrors the test stand setup for clarity and is shown in Figure 46.

Figure 47. LabVIEW Virtual Interface for the Absorption Chiller Test Stand.

The VI allows for a live display of temperatures and flowrates collected by the data acquisition system; a National Instruments Compact DAQ with an 8 slot chassis. The DAQ operates using independent sensor cards which define select channels for thermocouple, voltage, current inputs and SSR and voltage outputs. Using these dedicated channels, the VI is able to monitor, log and control the different components of the test stand.

The DAQ system operates several different levels of control for various components on the test stand including the VFDs, the chiller relays, and the heater relays. The DAQ system is able to remotely enable each VFD independently using a SSR and control the frequency output of the VFD by analog voltage 0-10 VDC. Similarly, the DAQ system operates as the safety system for both the chiller and heater by closing their safety relays remotely via user input. Additionally, the VI is programmed to enact autonomous safety shutdowns if certain conditions are met. The safety fault conditions are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: VI Safety Shutdown Conditions

<i>Condition Name</i>	<i>Argument</i>	<i>Action</i>
<i>Freeze Protection</i>	$T_c < 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Deactivate Chiller
<i>Boiling Protection</i>	$T_h > 95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Deactivate Heater

<i>Simulated Exhaust Flow Fault</i>	$V_{\text{exh}} < 25 \text{ CFM}$	Deactivate Heater
<i>Simulated Exhaust Overtemp</i>	$T_{\text{exh}} > 350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Deactivate Heater
<i>Emergency Stop</i>	User Initiated	Shut Down All VFDs, Chiller, Heater

The control wiring for the DAQ is contained within a small electrical enclosure with terminal connections for faster diagnosis and repair. The electrical enclosure is shown in Figure 47.

Figure 48. Low Voltage Control Box with DAQ.

An additional 24 VDC power supply is built into the control box to power the various sensors. The complete wiring diagram for the control box is shown in Figure 48. Notice the three banks of inputs and outputs at the bottom being the DAQ system, the two banks of inputs at the top being the absorption chiller and the VFDS indicated on the left. The R1 and R1C connections on the VFD are normally open relays that activate upon enabling of the drive. The right blocks show the inputs and outputs of all the analog sensors placed on the test stand.

Figure 49. Low Voltage Control Wiring Diagram.

3.9 Sensor Array

To accurately monitor the test stand, several types of sensors were designed into the systems. The first and most common are thermocouple sensors which measure temperature using an electrical potential difference across two different metals that scales with temperature. The test stand employs two types of thermocouples: Type T and Type K. Type T thermocouples are installed in the hot, cold and cooling water loops since they provide more accurate readings within the narrower temperature window of liquid water. Type K thermocouples are installed are installed within the simulated exhaust system to measure the higher temperatures experienced.

The second type of sensors are vortex-shedding flow meters for measuring the volumetric flow rate of the water loops on the chiller test stand. Vortex-shedding flow meters operate off the principle that vortices produced by flowing liquid increase their frequency at higher flow rates. By introducing an obstruction to the flow, the vortices are produced at a precise location and measured using a piezoelectric sensor as shown in Figure 49. Vortex shedding flow meters are advantageous due to their robustness, simplicity, and low cost.

Figure 50. Vortex Shedding Flow Schematic.

The flow meters selected for the test stand were specified for their specific flows, temperatures, and line sizes. Three flow meters were selected, one for each water loop with the flow capacities of up to 132 L/min (35 GPM), 190 L/min (50 GPM), and 454 L/min (120 GPM). The hot and cold water flow meters are made using a brass body with a visual indicator on the front as shown in Figure 44. These sensors operate on 24 VDC and output an analog current of 4-20 mA. The cooling water flow meter is made of PVC and outputs 4-20 mA to the DAQ system.

Figure 51. Hot Water Flow Meter.

It should be noted that these flow meters are highly sensitive to having air within the water lines, often trapping air bubbles within their measuring mechanism. If the operator notices severe oscillation of flow measurements, it is recommended to check the charge of the system.

The third type of sensor on the chiller test stand is a differential pressure transducer which measures the pressure differential across the pitot tube installed in the simulated exhaust system. The difference between the static and stagnation pressures indicate the velocity of the flow using Bernoulli's equation shown in Equation (1).

$$v^2 = \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P}{\rho_{air}}} \quad (1)$$

The pitot tube installed in the flow is an averaging pitot tube with two openings for both static and stagnant pressure. Thus, we are able to calculate the flowrate through the exhaust simulation system assuming a uniform flow distribution, which is likely based on the Reynolds number. The differential pressure transducer operates on 24 VDC and outputs a voltage between 0.2 and 5.2 V. The pressure transducer is shown with its connections to the pitot tube as installed in Figure 51. It is assumed that the pressure drop within the pitot tube and connecting lines is negligible.

Figure 52. Differential Pressure Transducer with Pitot Tube.

3.10 Data Analysis

The data collected by the DAQ system is logged once every 3 seconds and is saved to an Excel file with indicated time stamps for reference. Following any experiment, the data is then saved to the cloud to ensure its safety. To analyze the data, post processing is performed to calculate heat transfer rates, energy balances and overall performance. The data is categorized as “critical” and “non-critical” depending on what type of situation is being investigated. For example, when investigating steady state performance, the user is able to visually ascertain steady state and indicate that to the DAQ via a switch in the VI. Within the post processing, the critical data is then evaluated to see if steady state was indeed achieved and then the state point is considered as a test condition. The same process could be used for investigation of transient operation.

The data recorded by the DAQ system and saved to an Excel file is then broken down for post-processing to analyze the operation of the test stand. The data consists of the streams listed in Table 9.

Table 9. Data Acquisition Channels and Units

<i>Channel</i>	<i>Number of Streams</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Time</i>	1	Timestamp
<i>Type T Thermocouples</i>	8	°C (°F)
<i>Type K Thermocouples</i>	2	°C (°F)
<i>VFD Frequency Outputs</i>	4	Hz
<i>Flow Meter Voltage Outputs</i>	4	V
<i>Binary Control Outputs</i>	8	-
<i>Flow Meter Flow Rate Outputs</i>	4	L/min (GPM)
<i>Critical Data Binary</i>	1	-

Using the data available, it is possible to calculate the coefficient of performance (COP) of the chiller and the chilling capacity using the following steps. First, the volumetric flow rates are converted to mass flow rates by determining the density of each stream. The density of the water streams is determined based on their average temperature and a polyfit function which outputs the density in kg/m³ as shown in Equation (2)

$$\rho_w = 1000.5 - 0.0661 \bar{T} - 0.0036 \bar{T}^2 \quad (2)$$

The mass flow rate of each of the water streams is then calculated using Equation (3).

$$\dot{m}_w = \dot{V}_w \rho_w \quad (3)$$

Then the heat transfer across each of the processes is calculated using the temperature of the water streams and an assumed water pressure to determine enthalpy from a lookup table. The enthalpy state points combined with the mass flow rates give the heat transfer rate as shown in Equation (4).

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m}_w (h_{w,in} - h_{w,out}) \quad (4)$$

The heat transfer rates are calculated for the hot water loop, the cold water loop, and the two components of the cooling water loop that go through the absorber and condenser, respectively. A net system energy balance is performed to determine the accuracy of the heat transfer calculations along with any heat losses sustained within the system.

To calculate the coefficient of performance (COP) for the chiller, the heat transfer rates from the hot water loop and the cold water loop are considered as shown in Equation (5).

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cold}}{\dot{Q}_{hot}} \quad (5)$$

These equations are the fundamentals of the data reduction performed on the first set of experimental results, but in the future, more in depth analysis of each component is possible by delving into the data further.

4. Experimental Results

4.1 SOFC Dynamic Experimental Results

Following several months of steady states tests, several dynamic tests were run to characterize performance of SOFC system over dynamic operation. One of the BlueGEN systems ran over the dynamic power profile shown in Figure 52 for 10 days.

Figure 53. BlueGEN dynamic operation data.

Looking at SOFC dynamic data in Figure 52, it is observed that BlueGEN electrical efficiency is the highest, roughly 64%, at full load. BlueGEN efficiency is the lowest at 30% at 300W. BlueGEN system is recommended to go run between 1500W and 500W. At the lowest recommended power, the efficiency is roughly 43%. As expected, at load lower than nominal power current density drops, and because of lower polarization, voltage increases. Experimental results show that BlueGEN control system is designed to keep air flow constant and change the fuel utilization and fuel flow proportional to the output power. BlueGEN stack temperature difference is designed to stay at 50°C at full load. The experimental results show that by reducing the load, the temperature difference decreases. The exit temperature drops below the inlet temperature at 700W. at low current density the endothermicity of reformation reaction is higher than exothermicity of electrochemical reaction which causes temperature drop along the cell.

In another dynamic test, BlueGEN system was tested through the following profile in Figure 43 in 24h for 42 days. During this cycle, the power decreases between 1500W to 500W with 100W resolution. In each power step the system is given 1 hour to reach to steady state and then it has 15 min to ramp down (or up) to the next power level shown in Figure 53.

Figure 54. BlueGEN stack power cycle- 24h

Figure 54 shows the current density and voltage change during the introduced power cycle on 24 h. As expected, the current density changes proportional to power profile. Looking at voltage profile in each power step, voltage does not reach to steady states and is constantly changing. Stack temperature data in Figure 55 shows that one hour is not enough for the system to reach to steady state temperature due to high thermal inertia of the system which results in voltage changes.

Figure 55. BlueGEN current density and voltage on a 24h cycle

Figure 56. BlueGEN stack temperature on a 24h cycle

Figure 56 shows BlueGEN performance parameters, temperatures, and flows during ramp up from 500W to 1500W in solid lines and ramp down in dashed line. The hysteresis effect was observed because the system did not reach to steady state during this power cycle in each step.

Figure 57. BlueGEN performance

Another set of experiment was conducted to test how long it would take for BlueGEN to reach steady states. In the new test as it is shown in Figure 57, BlueGEN runs the same cycle as before,

however, in each power step it has 8 hours to reach to steady states. It takes a week for BlueGEN to go through the new cycle.

Figure 58. BlueGEN stack power cycle- one week

Figures 58 and 59 show the voltage and the stack temperature, respectively over a week. Each color is representative of one day data. Looking closer at each power step data shows that voltage and temperature changes during the first couple of hours sharply and the BlueGEN system reaches to steady states after 5 to 6 hours.

Figure 59. BlueGEN voltage on a one week cycle

Figure 60. BlueGEN stack temperature on a one week cycle

4.2 SOFC Degradation Results

BlueGEN system was tested on power cycle presented on Figure 57 for 42 days. Figure 60 shows the VJ curve for the system on the first day and last day of test. As expected, the hysteresis effect is observed due to not reaching to steady state at each power step. Results shows that the BlueGEN system degrades 0.058% for 42 days of operation (1000h) on a very highly dynamic load. This degradation is equivalent to 4.7 mV/cell.

Figure 61. BlueGEN V-J characteristics curve for a 24h power cycle for 42 days

BlueGEN system has been running for 6000h from the installation in National Fuel Cell Research Center. Figure 55 shows the power profile of BlueGEN system over 6000h operation. After 4000 hour of steady state operation the system runs the first dynamic load (Figure 61), then

after a couple of days of steady operation it goes through 24h dynamic load cycles for 1000 h and then the one-week dynamic cycle starts. Figure 62 shows the voltage change over the 6000h operation. The system operation is divided to three region and Table 10 shows the degradation results for each region. The BlueGEN degradation rate is 0.25% per 1000h for steady states operation. During the first 1000h of operation as the system is new the degradation rate is twice than the regular steady state operation. Also, the system degrades twice faster that steady state operation while operating at a highly dynamic condition. As the system degrades, the fuel consumption increases and as a result the efficiency drops.

Figure 62. BlueGEN power profile over 6000h operation.

Figure 63. BlueGEN stack voltage (V) during 6000h operation

Table 10. BlueGEN degradation analysis

Parameter	A, initial operation	B, steady state	C, dynamic
	1000h	3000h	1000h
Degradation per 1000h	0.58%	0.025%	0.59%
Degradation per cell	4.8mV	2mV	4.7mV
Efficiency decrease	0.59	0.3%	0.58%
Fuel consumption increase	0.6%	0.3%	0.5%

4.3 Absorption Chiller Primary Experimental Results

Following the completion of the experimental test stand, several tests were run to ensure the successful operation of each component individually. Following these tests, it was possible to exercise the test stand to obtain some preliminary data. The first data point was constructed somewhat arbitrarily with flow rates at roughly 60% of maximum to ensure flow but not overload the system. With a successful operation of the full system, an operational sweep was determined to exercise the system and explore the performance of the chiller across a range of operating points.

The first sweep was built around the chillers response to varying exhaust temperature inputs to the system. The sweep parameters are listed in Table 11.

Table 11. Initial Sweep Parameters

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value(s)</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Chiller Setpoint</i>	7 (44.6)	°C (°F)
<i>Cooling Water Loop Flowrate</i>	168.5 (44.5)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Cold Water Loop Flowrate</i>	45.8 (12.1)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Hot Water Loop Flowrate</i>	34.0 (9.0)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Simulated Exhaust Flow Rate</i>	229.4 (135)	m ³ /hr. (CFM)
<i>Exhaust Temperature Range</i>	150-300 (302-572)	°C (°F)
<i>Exhaust Temperature Step</i>	25 (45)	°C (°F)

The test stand was brought to steady state operation at the first state point, 150 °C (302 °F), and the data was recorded over a three minute window where steady state was achieved. The exhaust temperature was then stepped up by manipulating the electrical heater setpoint. The heat controller then brought up the exhaust temperature to the next set point. The thermal step is shown in Figures 63-66 below for the hot, cold, cooling and exhaust streams.

Figure 64. Exhaust Temperature Transient Step.

Figure 65. Hot Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.

Figure 66. Cooling Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.

Figure 67. Cold Water Loop Temperature Transient Response.

Looking at Figure 63, the controller brings the exhaust stream to temperature relatively quickly with some overshoot but is otherwise very stable as it reaches steady state. Figure 64 shows that the hot water loop follows the step increase with an expected thermal lag but eventually reaches steady state. Similarly, Figure 66 shows that the chiller is able to lower the cold water supply temperature due to the higher thermal input from the hot water loop. Notice that the chiller is operating at part capacity and is not able to reach its desired cold water setpoint due to the lack of hot water thermal input. Lastly, the cooling water temperature increases with accordance to the exhaust temperature but never truly reaches steady state, this can be attributed to the continuous warming of the ambient outside air during the day. Still, the change in temperature is relatively small so a quasi-steady state is assumed.

Using this exercise method, the system is worked through the full range of exhaust temperatures while the coefficient of performance (COP) and chilling capacity are being recorded. The results from this first sweep are shown in Figure 67.

Figure 68. Preliminary Sweep Chiller Performance Results.

Analyzing Figure 67, the chilling capacity increases with the increasing exhaust temperature. This is to be expected since the thermal energy available for capture from a hotter exhaust of the same flow capacity is larger. However, the COP reaches a maximum of 0.74, high for this system, at an exhaust temperature of 200°C (392°F). This behavior is less expected, since the higher thermal efficiency and chilling capacity should result in a better COP. However, when appreciating the fact that throughout this test the cold water temperature was decreasing, the decrease in efficiency at higher temperatures can be attributed to the larger temperature delta over which the chiller is operating.

To further explore the performance of the chiller, the sweep previously discussed was run again with varying exhaust flow rates. The parameters of the sweep are listed in Table 12 below.

Table 12. Exhaust Temperature and Flow Sweep Parameters.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value(s)</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Chiller Setpoint</i>	7 (44.6)	°C (°F)
<i>Cooling Water Loop Flowrate</i>	168.5 (44.5)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Cold Water Loop Flowrate</i>	45.8 (12.1)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Hot Water Loop Flowrate</i>	34.0 (9.0)	L/min (GPM)
<i>Simulated Exhaust Flow Rate Range</i>	158-271.8 (93-160)	m ³ /hr. (CFM)
<i>Exhaust Flow Rate Step</i>	37.4 (22)	m ³ /hr. (CFM)
<i>Exhaust Temperature Range</i>	150-300 (302-572)	°C (°F)
<i>Exhaust Temperature Step</i>	25 (45)	°C (°F)

Using the same exercise technique detailed before, the system was exercised through the state points listed in Table 12. The results were then plotted together with the results from the previous sweep and can be found in Figures 68 and 69.

Figure 69. Multi-Parameter Sweep COP Results.

Figure 70. Multi-Parameter Sweep Capacity Results.

Looking at Figure 68, an interesting trend appears with the peaks of each COP curve. For lower exhaust flow, the COP maximum occurs at higher exhaust temperature compared to the higher flow where the maximum occurs at lower temperatures. This is an interesting phenomenon which will require further exploration and analysis to better understand if this performance characteristic is derived from a thermodynamic phenomenon or a control strategy employed by the chiller.

Figure 69 follows a more expected trend with higher flow and higher temperature leading to a larger chilling capacity. Note that the state point on the 160 CFM trend at the maximum temperature may be erroneous since the system may have triggered a freeze protection during operation. Nevertheless, there is still some chilling capacity trends at the higher exhaust temperatures that indicate the chiller is not allowing full thermal input or output. This also warrants further investigation in the future.

4.4 Summary

Experimental results show that the SOFC system can dynamically respond to different power settings, potentially providing some load following capabilities for a data center. Integration with an absorption chiller shows that the chilling capacity of the chiller can be optimized by modulating both exhaust gas flow rate and temperature. Both parameters could be modified by either manipulating flow in the fuel cell, or by introducing ambient air into the exhaust gas stream.

These results also show accelerated SOFC degradation when the system is used dynamically. Although some dynamic operation is inevitable, these results indicate that there is a need to evaluate if the degradation rate is acceptable for use in either in-rack, at the server row level, or at the data center facility scale level. Subsequent analysis results will indicate that server row level SOFCs are preferred over in-rack. One potential benefit of in-rack SOFC design is that rack replacement occurs frequently enough that degraded performance may be acceptable. Shifting to row- or facility-level systems do not have the same benefit. If SOFC systems are used at the row-

or facility level, other on- and off-site energy resources should be considered to ensure that data center dynamics are powered using an optimal mix of generation, storage, and utility sources.

5. Model Development

This section addresses all models developed for use in this work, spanning steady state and dynamic SOFC models and both the AC and LDD systems. First, an integrated SOFC and AC system are developed to explore the techno-economic performance of this configuration. Then, a dynamic SOFC and LDD system are developed to explore the potential of this system to meet data center energy requirements.

5.1 Integrated Absorption Chiller Modeling – Row Level

To evaluate the effectiveness of a thermally integrated AC with an SOFC for the application of distributed power and cooling in a data center, a mathematical model was developed in Engineering Equation Solver (EES) and MATLAB. The integrated system consists of three models: a thermodynamic model of an SOFC, a floating state point model of a Lithium Bromide (LiBr) AC, and an economic model for the installation and operation of the system.

5.1.1 Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Model

To better understand the thermodynamic heat source and the different operational strategies and their impact on exhaust temperature, flow, and heat capacity, a comprehensive SOFC system model is developed. 200 kW (AC) SOFC systems meet the row-level configuration requirements and have been previously installed at data centers to supply steady state base loads [4]. The specified SOFC runs on natural gas and the layout of the balance of plant is detailed in Figure 70.

Figure 71. SOFC Balance of Plant Schematic.

The SOFC system model is coded in MATLAB and utilizes an iterative averaging solution to converge the twenty-one state points shown above in Figure 70. Each state point contains a temperature, pressure, concentration, mass flow rate, and heat capacity. Component models determine their outlet states mechanistically based upon the inlet states and given physical, chemical and electrochemical phenomena involved in their operation. The solution of each outlet state is placed in the state point array of the next iteration. The power output was set at 210 kW_e and the steam-to-carbon ratio was set at 2.5. The following component models are utilized within the balance of plant. The full set of modeling assumptions is presented in Table 13.

The output state of a mixing chamber is calculated by using a mass balance and an energy balance assuming adiabatic mixing. In this way, the outlet state's temperature, concentration, mass flow, and heat capacity can be calculated.

$$\sum_{in} \dot{m}_i = \sum_{out} \dot{m}_i \quad [1]$$

$$\sum_{in} \dot{m}_i h_i = \sum_{out} \dot{m}_i h_i \quad [2]$$

The recirculation valve is a given input that determines the percentage of mass flow that is recirculated into State 3. The two outlets of the recirculation valve are calculated using a mass balance.

The four basic heat exchangers utilized in the system are modeled mechanistically using a constant heat exchanger effectiveness, provided as an input to the model. The heat exchange capacity is determined in Equation 3. Pressure and thermal losses are assumed for each component and can be found in Table 13.

$$\dot{Q}_{HX} = \epsilon \min(\dot{m}_c(h_c|_{T_h} - h_c), \dot{m}_h(h_h - h_h|_{T_c})) \quad [3]$$

Each heat exchanger is then discretized to produce the temperature profiles of the hot and cold streams. The heat exchanger pinch point and average effective convective heat transfer coefficient can then be determined. It should be noted that all the heat exchangers were modeled in a counter flow configuration to maximize performance.

$$\dot{Q}_{HX} = UA_{HX} \left(\frac{\Delta T_h - \Delta T_c}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_h}{\Delta T_c}\right)} \right) \quad [4]$$

The post-anode combustor is treated as an ideal reacting combustor in which all the combustible fuels are reacted completely. The exothermic heat transfer is calculated from the lower heating values (LHV) of the fuels. Note that incomplete combustion can be modelled in case of a shortage of oxidizer.

$$\sum_{in} \dot{m}_i h_i + Q_{comb} = \sum_{out} \dot{m}_i h_i \quad [5]$$

The external steam reformer is modeled assuming a partially complete reaction to an equilibrium set by the outlet temperature of the reformer. The external reformer also functions as a heat exchanger with some of the heat transfer is utilized in the endothermic reactions of the steam-methane reformation and water gas shift.

A bulk fuel cell stack model was created to predict the cell voltage within the fuel cell stack. The model was based on the SOFC stack model provided in O'Hayre et al. [10]. Overpotentials from fuel and oxidizer concentrations, ohmic losses within the electrolyte, cathodic losses due to mass transport are considered. The ability to simulate losses due to stack temperature adjustments within the cells will become important because that is one of the two primary variables adjusted for the operation of the SOFC. Complete internal reforming of any methane is also assumed. The cell model combined with the endothermic internal reforming and the exothermic oxidation of hydrogen allows the model to calculate the species concentrations and enthalpy at the outlets of both the anode and the cathode.

Table 13. SOFC Model Assumptions and Inputs.

Component	Assumption	Value
Mixing Chambers	Adiabatic Mixing	-
Anode Recirc Valve	Fixed Percentage Recirc	0.4
Anode Recoup HX	Constant Effectiveness	0.75
Anode Cooler HX	Constant Effectiveness	0.8
Cathode Recoup HX	Constant Effectiveness	0.85
Anode Condenser HX	Constant Effectiveness	0.45
External Reformer HX	Constant Effectiveness	0.85
External Reforming	Fraction of Equilibrium Concentration	0.7
Heat Exchanger Pressure Loss	Constant Pressure Drop	0.75 kPa
Heat Exchanger Thermal Loss	Proportional Transfer Loss	10%

The outputs of the SOFC model are focused on the thermodynamic characterization of the exhaust, but also include overall efficiency and carbon emissions. To calculate the heat capacity of the exhaust, Equation 6 below is used.

$$\dot{Q}_{exh} = \dot{m}_{exh} C_p (T_{exh} - T_{des}) \quad [6]$$

The thermal efficiency of the SOFC system is calculated using the LHV of the fuel input as shown in Equation 7.

$$\eta_{SOFC,therm} = \frac{\dot{E}_{FC}}{\dot{m}_{fuel} LHV_{NG}} \quad [7]$$

Adjustments to input variables such as anode recirculation, heat exchanger effectiveness, and combustion efficiency were made to ensure that solutions match acceptable operating values.

5.1.2 Absorption Chiller Model

A triple effect absorption chiller was selected for its higher coefficient of performance (COP) and temperature compatibility to capture heat from the exhaust of the SOFC. A floating point model using saturation data for aqueous Lithium Bromide was utilized. The interface heat exchangers: desorbers, absorbers and condensers were all modeled using a log-mean-temperature approach while internal heat exchangers were modeled using a constant effectiveness approach. Full details of the matching 200 kW triple-effect AC model are also detailed by Lavernia et al [9]. The parallel effect triple effect absorption chiller system is shown schematically in figure 71 where heat capture from the exhaust of the SOFC occurs in the third desorber between state points 23, 24, and 27. Chilling is produced in the evaporator between states 9 and 10. External heat rejection occurs from the third condenser between state points 19, 7, and 8.

Figure 72. Triple Effect Absorption Chiller System Schematic.

The absorption model predicts the cycle's performance for various desorber temperatures and evaporator temperatures. The objective is to find an optimal temperature at which to capture heat from the SOFC exhaust. The output from the AC model is shown in Figure 72.

Figure 73. Absorption Chiller Coefficient of Performance at varying temperature constraints. [9]

To maximize the chilling performance, a higher desorber temperature should be used. The output also investigates the possibility of shifting from an air based cooling medium to a liquid based cooling medium for the servers. The area within the dashed blue line is the region in which air cooling would be feasible. The area within the red highlight is where liquid cooling could occur. For both scenarios, COPs of 1.8 are possible with high enough desorber temperatures. Note that when integrating with SOFC exhaust, the higher the desorber temperature, the less waste heat that can be recovered. This integration is explored later.

5.1.3 Economic Model

The final model within the integrated model is an economic model which predicts the economic feasibility of such an integrated system. To do so, the economic model first calculates the capital investment to install each subsystem. The three subsystems considered are the SOFC plant, the absorption chiller, and the cooling tower required to reject heat from the absorption chiller. For the purposes of this analysis, a dry cooling tower is considered to minimize the impact of operation in a hot and humid region. Additionally, dry towers are generally more expensive to install and will therefore provide a more conservative estimate of the economic costs.

The economics of the SOFC plant are broken down into three categories: capital investment, operation/maintenance, and cost of fuel. The capital investment of installation is shown below in Table 14. This cost estimate is relatively optimistic but is still reasonable considering that utilization of such technology at data center scales should reduce the unit cost. The operation and maintenance costs are similarly sourced based on existing installations. Lastly, the fuel costs are based on bulk wholesale natural gas prices in southern California.

The economics of the absorption chiller and the cooling tower are each broken down into two categories: capital investment and operation/maintenance. The capital investment for the absorption chiller is determined for a triple effect large-scale per kW cooling power. The operation and maintenance cost is also taken from an existing plant. Finally, the AC plant is oversized by a factor of 1.5 since most plants perform optimally at 70% of their full capacity. The cooling tower

is similarly oversized by a factor of 1.25 to ensure its ability to meet the heat rejection needs of the AC plant. The values for all these costs are shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Economic Model Inputs. [5],[16]

Parameter	Value	Unit
SOFC: Capital Investment	499	\$/kW
SOFC: Operation & Maintenance	6	\$/MWh
SOFC: Fuel Cost	0.45	\$/therm
AC: Capital Investment	4200	\$/kW
AC: Operation \$ Maintenance	14	\$/MWh
CT (Dry): Capital Investment	224	\$/kW
CT (Dry): Operation and Maintenance	7.2	\$/MWh
Operational Lifetime	20	years

Using these inputs, the economic model can calculate the levelized cost of electricity and chilling over an assumed lifetime of 20 years. It should be noted that this economic analysis does not account for the required restacking of the SOFC within the lifetime. The economic model's results are calculated following the thermodynamic model of both the SOFC and the absorption chiller and are discussed in the following section.

To explore the optimization of the integrated system, two operational parameters were identified as controllable values: stack temperature and fuel utilization¹. The integrated model was then exercised across a range of stack temperatures and fuel utilizations to explore the operational space and determine the optimal operating conditions. An initial converged condition is obtained using the physical inputs into the model and then a spiral search pattern is used to explore the temperature and utilization domain. This strategy was adopted to minimize the step distance between test points and thus improve the stability and speed of the iterative model. The objective of this exercise is to determine if it is possible to operate the triple effect absorption chiller in conjunction with the SOFC to produce 200 kW of electricity and 200 kW of chilling to power and cool the servers.

5.2 Dynamic SOFC stack model

A spatially and temporally resolved fuel cell stack model has been developed based on the developed model in NCFRC using the MATLAB software [47]. The model is developed for one unit cell that describes the response of the entire stack. 51 unitary anode-supported (fuel electrode-supported) planar rectangular cells are assembled into one-unit SOFC stack. Figure 74 presents one crossflow cell geometry with its components as well as a depiction of two repeated cells in series. The planar rectangular cells are flexible, compact, easy to produce, and have

¹ Fuel utilization is the percent of fuel used by the fuel cell divided by the total fuel input. Since the fuel cell is an equipotential surface (voltage from the anode to the cathode is the same at all points of the fuel cell), cell voltage is determined by the lowest voltage point in the fuel cell. This is typically at the anode outlet where fuel concentration is smallest. If fuel concentration goes to zero, i.e., fuel utilization is 100%, there is no fuel and the fuel cell electrochemical potential drops to zero. Common fuel cell fuel utilizations range between 70% and 90%.

lower manufacturing cost compared to tubular cells. The unit cell consists of five layers i.e., cathode flow, anode flow, Positive electrode, Electrolyte, Negative electrode (PEN), fuel bipolar plate and air bipolar plate.

Figure 74. Planar fuel cell model.

The spatially and temporally resolved model uses different states to calculate parameters at different nodes of a cell. These nodal states are calculated at each time step among set of points in the time vector using the MATLAB Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) solver. These nodal states are composed of nodal temperatures of fuel and air separator plates (bipolar plates), temperature of fuel and air flows, nodal temperature of the PEN, nodal concentration of different species in both cathode and anode flow sides (methane, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and steam species for anode side as well as oxygen and nitrogen species at cathode side), nodal current and cathode/anode flow inlet pressure. The evaluated parameters based on the mentioned states are nodal Nernst voltage, nodal voltage losses, nodal operating voltage (should be obtained constant across the cell in order to satisfy the equipotential surface condition), nodal molar flow rate of ions crossing the PEN, nodal heat generation in the PEN, nodal heat and mass transfers and many other parameters. A two-dimensional multi-layer approach is accomplished for both the electrochemical modeling and heat transfer modeling resulting in a quasi-3-D representation of an electrochemical cell. As an assumption, instantaneous electrochemical reactions are assumed, due to relatively fast electrochemical reactions compared to cell and stack thermal response dynamics. Using Faraday's law, the rate of electrochemical reactions is directly proportional to the cell current. Furthermore, it is considered that electrical current flows only in one direction from one electrode to the other one along the PEN, as the electrical potential is assumed constant on the electrode surfaces. In the developed model, gases behave as ideal gas due to high operating temperature of the SOFC.

In this study a 5×5 spatial resolution (number of rows and columns) is accomplished for all 5 layers (fuel plate, fuel flow, PEN, air flow, air plate). The solid oxide fuel cell has an active

surface area of 139.24cm² (11.8cm × 11.8cm). Fuel cell module material properties are presented in Table 15 and geometry parameters are presented in Table 16. Figure 75 depicts schematically the geometric parameters of the fuel cell.

Table 15. Fuel cell material properties.

Material Properties[47]	
Anode (Fuel) Electrode Material	Ni/YSZ Cermet
Cathode (Air) Electrode Material	LSCF
Electrolyte Material	YSZ Composite
Conductivity of Electrolyte (W/m. K)	6.19
Density of Electrolyte (kg/m ³)	375
Specific Heat of Electrolyte (J/kg. K)	800
Conductivity of Bipolar Plate (W/m. K)	5
Density of Bipolar Plate (kg/m ³)	2000
Specific Heat of Bipolar Plate (J/kg. K)	600

Figure 75. Geometric parameters of a fuel cell.

Table 16. Fuel cell geometrical parameters.

Geometrical Parameters	
Anode Thickness (m)	$800e^{-6}$
Cathode Thickness (m)	$50e^{-6}$
Electrolyte Thickness (m)	$18e^{-6}$
Bipolar Plate Thickness (m)	$6e^{-3}$
Plate Thickness (m)	$3e^{-3}$
Cell Length (m)	$11.8e^{-2}$
Cell Width (m)	$11.8e^{-2}$
Channel Height (Fuel Side) (m)	$2e^{-3}$
Channel Height (Air Side) (m)	$2e^{-3}$
Channel Width (Fuel Side) (m)	$5e^{-3}$
Channel Width (Air Side) (m)	$5e^{-3}$
Channel Wall Thickness (Fuel Side) (m)	$5e^{-3}$
Channel Wall Thickness (Air Side) (m)	$5e^{-3}$

5.2.1 Governing Equations

5.2.1.1 Energy balance

The developed model takes into account the conservation of energy within each node and energy transfer between control volumes to calculate the nodal temperature changes during dynamic operating conditions for all 5 layers which are fuel plate, air plate, cathode flow, anode flow and the PEN. Nodal energy balance equation for the cathode/anode stream includes convective heat transferred to the solid walls (PEN and bipolar plate), enthalpy flux due to the electrochemical reaction, mass transfer of oxygen ions from/to the PEN, and inlet/outlet enthalpy flux of the bulk flow from/to adjacent nodes. It is assumed that temperature in each control volume decreases/increases linearly along the control volume of each node (for anode/cathode streams). A nodal energy balance for the PEN includes convective heat transferred to the PEN from streams, conductive heat transferred to the PEN from bipolar plate, conductive heat transferred to adjacent nodes in PEN and heat generation due to the electrochemical reactions and electrical resistances. Radiation heat transfer between PEN and bipolar plate is negligible. A nodal energy balance equation for the bipolar plate includes convective heat transferred to bipolar plate from streams, conductive heat transferred to bipolar plate from PEN and conductive heat transferred to adjacent nodes in bipolar plate. Adiabatic boundary condition is considered for all the nodes located at the beginning and at the end of the cell on PEN and bipolar plate, as the cell height is relatively thin compared to its length. Also, it is considered that the stack is well

insulated such that heat loss to the environment is negligible. The nodal energy balance equation for cathode and anode flows, PEN and bipolar plate are presented below. Note that all nodal specific heat capacities are calculated at the node temperature. Also, for each cathode/anode node, inlet flow enthalpy is the outlet flow enthalpy of the previous node in the flow direction as follows [47].

$$\begin{aligned} & (\rho_{B.P.} \times V_{B.P.} \times C_{B.P.})|_{Node} \times \frac{\partial T_{B.P.}}{\partial t}|_{node} \\ &= \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{B.P.,A,C}}|_{node} + \sum \dot{Q}_{cond_{B.P.,PEN}}|_{node} \\ &+ \sum \dot{Q}_{cond_{B.P.,B.P.}}|_{node} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\rho_{PEN} \times V_{PEN} \times C_{PEN})|_{Node} \times \frac{\partial T_{PEN}}{\partial t}|_{node} \\ &= \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{PEN,A,C}}|_{node} + \sum \dot{Q}_{cond_{PEN,B.P.}}|_{node} \\ &+ \sum \dot{Q}_{cond_{PEN,PEN}}|_{node} - I|_{node}V|_{node} \\ &- \frac{I|_{node}}{n_e F} \left(h_{H_2O}|_{Node} - h_{H_2}|_{Node} - \frac{1}{2}h_{O_2}|_{Node} \right) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{P_C \times V_C}{R \times T_C} \times \bar{C}_{P_C} \right)|_{Node} \times \frac{\partial T_C}{\partial t}|_{node} \\ &= \sum_{Species} \dot{H}_{In}|_{node} - \sum_{Species} \dot{H}_{Out}|_{node} + \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{C,PEN}}|_{node} \\ &+ \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{C,B.P.}}|_{node} - \frac{I|_{node}}{2n_e F} (h_{O_2}|_{Node}) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{P_C \times V_C}{R \times T_C} \times \bar{C}_{P_C} \right)|_{Node} \times \frac{\partial T_C}{\partial t}|_{node} \\ &= \sum_{Species} \dot{H}_{In}|_{node} - \sum_{Species} \dot{H}_{Out}|_{node} + \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{C,PEN}}|_{node} \\ &+ \sum \dot{Q}_{conv_{C,B.P.}}|_{node} - \frac{I|_{node}}{2n_e F} (h_{O_2}|_{Node}) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

Where $\dot{H}_{In}|_{node} \left(\frac{J}{s} \right)$ and $\dot{H}_{Out}|_{Node} \left(\frac{J}{s} \right)$ are the total enthalpy of inlet and outlet stream of each node along anode/cathode stream, $\bar{C}_{P_A}|_{Node} \left(\frac{J}{mole.K} \right)$ is an average specific heat capacity of species in each node along anode/cathode stream, $C_{PEN}|_{Node} \left(\frac{J}{kg.K} \right)$ and $C_{BP}|_{Node} \left(\frac{J}{kg.K} \right)$ are specific heat capacities of each node on the PEN and interconnect plate, $\rho_{PEN}|_{Node} \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \right)$ and $\rho_{BP}|_{Node} \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \right)$ are densities of each node on the PEN and interconnect plate, $V_{PEN}|_{Node} \left(m^3 \right)$ and $V_{BP}|_{Node} \left(m^3 \right)$ are volume of each node on the PEN and interconnect plate and $T_{PEN}|_{Node} \left(K \right)$, $T_{BP}|_{Node} \left(K \right)$ are temperature of each, node on the PEN and interconnect plate

and $\dot{Q}|_{Node} \left(\frac{J}{s} \right)$ is composed of convection and conduction heat transfer to each node on each of different layers.

In order to calculate convection heat transfer between flows and solid walls, a local convective heat transfer coefficient is required. Reynolds numbers of fuel and air flows in channels are much lower than the critical Reynolds number for turbulent flow because not only are the fuel and air channels' cross-sectional area typically small, but also mean velocities of fuel and air flow are not very high. In these conditions, a fully developed laminar flow and uniform surface temperature exist approximately within all control volumes. In laminar flow condition, with considering the aspect ratio of the interconnect channels, a constant Nusselt number of four is used to calculate local convection heat transfer coefficient as below:

$$h = \frac{Nu_D \times k}{D_h} \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

5.2.1.2 Mass balance

As flows move from inlets to the cathode and anode outlets, the composition of fuel in anode side and the composition of oxygen/nitrogen at cathode side will be changed. The developed model takes into account the conservation of mass within each node and mass transfer between control volumes to calculate the nodal species' concentration's changes (species concentration are considered as states). Mass balance in cathode/anode flow side includes inlet/outlet molar flow rates from/to adjacent nodes and variation due to the existing electrochemical reaction. The nodal dynamic mass balance equations for steam, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, oxygen and nitrogen species are presented below. Note that for each node, the inlet molar flow rate is the outlet molar flow rate of the previous node in the flow direction as follows [47].

$$\frac{dX_{O_2}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{O_2,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{O_2,Out}|_{Node} - \frac{I|_{Node}}{2 \times n_e \times F}}{\frac{P_A|_{Node} \times V_A|_{Node}}{R \times T_A|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

$$\frac{dX_{N_2}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{N_2,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{N_2,Out}|_{Node}}{\frac{P_A|_{Node} \times V_A|_{Node}}{R \times T_A|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{dX_{H_2O}|_{Node}}{dt} \\ & = \frac{\dot{n}_{H_2O,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{H_2O,Out}|_{Node} + \frac{I|_{Node}}{n_e \times F} - r_{SR}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node} - r_{WGS}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{\frac{P_C|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{R \times T_C|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{dX_{H_2}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{H_2,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{H_2,Out}|_{Node} - \frac{I|_{Node}}{n_e \times F} + 3 \times r_{SR}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node} + r_{WGS}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{\frac{P_C|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{R \times T_C|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

$$\frac{dX_{CO}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{CO,Out}|_{Node} + r_{SR}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node} - r_{WGS}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{\frac{P_C|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{R \times T_C|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

$$\frac{dX_{CO_2}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CO_2,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{CO_2,Out}|_{Node} + r_{WGS}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{\frac{P_C|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{R \times T_C|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 19}$$

$$\frac{dX_{CH_4}|_{Node}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{CH_4,In}|_{Node} - \dot{n}_{CH_4,Out}|_{Node} - r_{SR}|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{\frac{P_C|_{Node} \times V_C|_{Node}}{R \times T_C|_{Node}}} \quad \text{Equation 20}$$

Where \dot{n} ($\frac{\text{mole}}{s}$) is the species molar flow rate, $I|_{Node}$ (A) is current of each node, $T_A|_{Node}$ (K) is temperature of each node along the anode/cathode stream, $P_{A/C}|_{Node}$ (Pa) is pressure of each node along the anode/cathode stream, $V_{A/C}|_{Node}$ (m^3) is volume of each node along the anode/cathode stream and $r_{SR/WGS}|_{Node}$. Are the reaction rates which are calculated below.

In this model, it is considered that Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) and Water Gas Shift (WGS) reaction take place in anode, but the actual direction and magnitude of the reaction rates depends on the operating conditions.

In the literature, the Haberman and Young's model [48] is widely used for calculating the water gas shift (WGS) and steam methane reforming (SMR) reaction rates; thus it is adopted in the present study. The following general formulations can be considered based on the quasi-homogeneous expression of the reaction kinetics.

$$r_{WGS}|_{Node} = K_{WGS}|_{Node} \left[P_{CO}|_{Node} P_{H_2O}|_{Node} - \frac{P_{CO_2}|_{Node} P_{H_2}|_{Node}}{K_{eq,WGS}|_{Node}} \right], \quad K_{eq,WGS}|_{Node} = \frac{K_{WGS}|_{Node}}{K_{RWGS}|_{Node}} \quad \text{Equation 23}$$

$$r_{SR}|_{Node} = K_{SR}|_{Node} \left[P_{CH_4}|_{Node} P_{H_2O}|_{Node} - \frac{P_{CO}|_{Node} P_{H_2}^3|_{Node}}{K_{eq,SR}|_{Node}} \right], \quad K_{eq,SR}|_{Node} = \frac{K_{SR}|_{Node}}{K_{Methanation}|_{Node}} \quad \text{Equation 24}$$

Where K_{WGS} and K_{SR} show the rate of water gas shift reaction and steam reformation reaction. K_{eq} is also equilibrium constant of each reaction. Ordinarily, based upon the first order kinetic expression (Arrhenius form), the rates of forward steam reformation and water gas shift reactions are as below:

$$K_{WGS}|_{Node} = 0.0171 \exp\left(\frac{-103191}{RT_F|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 25}$$

$$K_{SR}|_{Node} = 2395 \exp\left(\frac{-231266}{RT_F|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 26}$$

The SMR and WGS equilibrium constants can be calculated as below:

$$K_{eq,WGS}|_{Node} = \exp(-0.2935Z^3 + 0.6351Z^2 + 4.1788Z + 0.3169) \quad \text{Equation 27}$$

$$K_{eq,SR}|_{Node} = 1.0267 \times 10^{10} \exp(-0.2513Z^4 + 0.3665Z^3 + 0.581Z^2 - 27.134Z + 3.277) \quad \text{Equation 28}$$

$$Z = \frac{1000}{T(K)} - 1 \quad \text{Equation 29}$$

5.2.1.3 Polarization model

Nernst Voltage:

The Nernst potential is the electrical potential of each node which accounts for species concentration, operating temperature and pressure, and extent of reaction as well.

$$V_{Nernst}|_{Node} = E^0|_{Node} + \frac{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}{n_e F} \times \ln \left(\frac{X_{H_2,b}|_{Node} X_{O_2,b}|_{Node}^{0.5}}{X_{H_2O,b}|_{Node}} P_A|_{Node}^{0.5} \right) \quad \text{Equation 30}$$

Where $E^0|_{Node}$ (V) is a standard voltage of each node, R is a universal gas constant equal to $8.314 \left(\frac{J}{mole \cdot K} \right)$. $T_{PEN}|_{Node}$ (K) is temperature of each node on the PEN, n_e (mole of electron/moles of steam) is number of moles of electron transferred per unit mole of hydrogen equal to 2, $F \left(\frac{C}{mole} \right)$ is Faraday constant equal to 96485, X_i is species molar fraction and $P_A|_{Node}$ (atm) is pressure of each node along the anode stream.

The standard reversible voltage ($E^0|_{Node}$) of each node is calculated based upon the Gibbs energy change of reaction at the node temperature and standard pressure ($\Delta G|_{T_{PEN}|_{Node}, P_{Amb}}$ (J/mole)) according to Equation 31:

$$E^0|_{Node} = \frac{\Delta G \left(H_2 + \frac{1}{2} O_2 \rightarrow H_2O \right) |_{T_{PEN}|_{Node}, P_{Amb}}}{n_e F} \quad \text{Equation 31}$$

When the current is non-zero in the fuel cell, the cell operating voltage is lower than the Nernst voltage due to the voltage losses. These voltage losses can be described as follows: ohmic loss governed by ohm's law, activation loss governed by Butler-Volmer equation and concentration loss.

Activation Loss:

The Butler-Volmer equation is typically employed to characterize electrochemical activation loss associated with sluggish charge transfer reactions at the operating conditions of the cell as follows for the cathode and anode interfaces.

$$J|_{Node} = J_{0,Ca}|_{Node} \times \left\{ \exp \left(\frac{\alpha n_e F \eta_{act,Ca}|_{Node}}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}} \right) - \exp \left(- \frac{(1 - \alpha) n_e F \eta_{act,Ca}|_{Node}}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}} \right) \right\} \quad \text{Equation 32}$$

$$J|_{Node} = J_{0,An}|_{Node} \times \left\{ \exp \left(\frac{\alpha n_e F \eta_{act,An}|_{Node}}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}} \right) - \exp \left(- \frac{(1 - \alpha) n_e F \eta_{act,An}|_{Node}}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}} \right) \right\} \quad \text{Equation 33}$$

The exchange current density is a kinetic parameter measuring the local electrode current density at open circuit conditions i.e., at equilibrium conditions when no net current density is consumed or produced within the cell, and a is the symmetry factor or charge transfer

coefficient. Equation 34 and Equation 35 are employed to calculate the exchange current density as a function of temperature.

$$J_{0,Ca}|_{Node} = (1.344 \times 10^{10}) \times \exp\left(-\frac{1 \times 10^5}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 34}$$

$$J_{0,An}|_{Node} = (2.051 \times 10^9) \times \exp\left(-\frac{1.2 \times 10^5}{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 35}$$

The value of transfer coefficient is usually 0.5 for fuel cell applications [49]. With $\alpha = 0.5$, equations Equation 34 and Equation 35 can be expressed as:

$$\eta_{act,Ca}|_{Node} = \frac{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}{F} \times \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{J|_{Node}}{2 J_{0,Ca}|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 36}$$

$$\eta_{act,An}|_{Node} = \frac{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}{F} \times \sinh^{-1}\left(\frac{J|_{Node}}{2 J_{0,An}|_{Node}}\right) \quad \text{Equation 37}$$

Ohmic Loss:

Ohm's law is employed to evaluate the cell ohmic loss. Ohmic loss consists of cathode, anode and electrolyte ohmic losses as well as interconnect ohmic loss and contact ohmic loss which has the effect of ohmic resistance in the contact region between electrodes and interconnect plates. Equation 38 to Equation 43 describe the ohmic loss different components [47]:

$$\eta_{ohm,cont}|_{Node} = 0.1 \times 10^{-4} \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 38}$$

$$\eta_{ohm,Ca}|_{Node} = (1.05 \times 10^{-8}) \times T_{PEN}|_{Node} \times \exp\left(\frac{1150}{T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \times \delta_{Ca} \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 39}$$

$$\eta_{ohm,An}|_{Node} = (2.38 \times 10^{-8}) \times T_{PEN}|_{Node} \times \exp\left(\frac{1200}{T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \times \delta_{An} \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 40}$$

$$\eta_{ohm,El}|_{Node} = (2.99 \times 10^{-5}) \times \exp\left(\frac{10300}{T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \times \delta_{El} \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 41}$$

$$\eta_{ohm,IC}|_{Node} = (1.075 \times 10^{-7}) \times T_{IC}|_{Node} \times \exp\left(\frac{1100}{T_{IC}|_{Node}}\right) \times \delta_{IC} \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 42}$$

$$\eta_{ohm} = \sum \left(\frac{1}{A_{SOFC}} \right) \times T_{PEN}|_{Node} \times \exp\left(\frac{\Delta G_{act}}{T_{PEN}|_{Node}}\right) \times \delta \times (J|_{Node}) \quad \text{Equation 43}$$

Concentration Loss:

Concentration losses come from a physical limitation of gaseous diffusion from the bulk fluid flow to and from the reaction sites. As the cell produces current it must be continually supplied with reactants at the TPB, however, at some rate the supply of reacting species cannot diffuse through the electrode quick enough which is called the limiting current density and will reduce the operating voltage all the way to zero. Concentration losses can be expressed with the following equation:

$$\eta_{conc}|_{Node} = \frac{R T_{PEN}|_{Node}}{nF} \ln \frac{j_L}{j_L - j} \quad \text{Equation 44}$$

where j_L ($\frac{amp}{cm^2}$) is the limiting current, R is a universal gas constant equal to 8.314 ($\frac{J}{mole.K}$), $T_{PEN}|_{Node}$ (K) is temperature of each node on the PEN, n_e (mole of electron/moles of steam) is number of moles of electron transferred per unit mole of hydrogen equal to 2 and F ($\frac{C}{mole}$) is Faraday constant.

5.3 Dynamic SOFC system design & control

The SOFC system model contains a fuel cell stack, an anode off-gas oxidizer, air preheating heat exchangers, recirculate valve, mixer, blower, and reformer. A system diagram is provided in Figure 76. The oxidizer outlet preheats air and fuel first, and then, the leftover heat from the SOFC exhaust is recovered for regenerating desiccant liquid in the LDD system.

Figure 76. SOFC system configuration.

5.3.1 Balance of plant model:

5.3.1.1 Blower

A variable-speed blower model, enabling simulation of the rotating moment of inertia of the blower, is implemented in this study. The blower supplies sufficient pressure head and air flow rate for controlling the cell temperature gradient, The implemented dynamic model for blower is shown in Equation 45 [50].

$$J \cdot \omega \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dt} = P_B - P_{Imp} \quad \text{Equation 45}$$

Where ω is rotational speed, J is the moment inertia, P_B is the electric power supplied to the blower and P_{Imp} is the impeller loss evaluated according to Equation 46.

$$P_{Imp} = \frac{\dot{V}_{Air} \cdot \Delta P_{ca}}{\eta_B} \quad \text{Equation 46}$$

where \dot{V}_{Air} is the air volumetric flow rate, ΔP_{ca} is the pressure drop at cathode side and η is the blower mechanical efficiency.

5.3.1.2 Heat exchanger

Heat exchangers are modeled as one-dimensional counter flow plate heat exchangers comprised of three layers e.g., hot stream, metal separator plate and cold stream in order to

capture the thermal inertia of the heat exchangers. The developed dynamic model for a heat exchanger is spatially discretized into nodes and control volumes. In each node, material and energy balances are implemented using Equation 47 and Equation 48.

$$\rho^{c,h} \cdot V^{c,h} \cdot c_p^{c,h} \cdot \frac{dT^{c,h}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{conv} + \dot{H}_{In}^{c,h} - \dot{H}_{Out}^{c,h} \quad \text{Equation 47}$$

$$\rho_{Plate} \cdot c_{Plate} \cdot V_{Plate} \cdot \frac{dT_{Plate}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{conv} + \dot{Q}_{cond} \quad \text{Equation 48}$$

Where $\rho^{c,h} \cdot V^{c,h} \cdot c_p^{c,h} \cdot \frac{dT^{c,h}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{conv} + \dot{H}_{In}^{c,h} - \dot{H}_{Out}^{c,h}$ is convective heat transfer between solid and gaseous nodes, ρ is the density, V is volume and c_p , c are the specific heat capacity of gaseous and solid nodes.

5.3.1.3 Mixer

The following expressions can be used to find the composition of the mixed stream.

$$\dot{n}_{mix} = \sum_i (\dot{n}_1 \cdot x_{1,i} + \dot{n}_2 \cdot x_{2,i}) \quad \text{Equation 49}$$

$$x_{mix,i} = \frac{\dot{n}_1 \cdot x_{1,i} + \dot{n}_{mix} \cdot x_{1,i}}{\dot{n}_{mix}} \quad \text{Equation 50}$$

$$\dot{n}_{mix} C_p \cdot \frac{dT_{mix}}{dt} = \dot{n}_1 \cdot h_1 + \dot{n}_2 \cdot h_2 + \dot{n}_{mix} \cdot h_{mix} \quad \text{Equation 51}$$

5.3.1.4 Reformer

In this study both internal reforming and external reforming is considered. For external reforming, like internal reforming, SMR and WGS take place. The mass balance equation is the same as the one as explained in section 5.2.1.2 for fuel cell without electrochemical term ($I = 0$) and the energy balance is the same as heat exchanger which is explained in section 5.3.1.2.

5.3.1.5 Oxidizer

The combustion model accounts only for the same seven species as the remainder of the model. The following three reactions are considered in this combustor model.

Proper accounting of all the reacting species is necessary to find the resulting flow rate and composition post combustion. The energy conservation equation is as follows:

$$n_{com}C_p \cdot \frac{dT_{comb}}{dt} = \dot{n}_1 \cdot h_1 + \dot{n}_2 \cdot h_2 + \dot{n}_{out} \cdot h_{out} \quad \text{Equation 55}$$

5.3.2 Control strategy

5.3.2.1 Temperature control

Cell temperature control is one of the key issues involved in the dynamic operation of high temperature SOFC systems. In this study, the stack is thermally managed by manipulating one actuator, which controls the blower power. A variable speed blower enables control of blower dynamics that consider the inertia of the blower as described above. Increasing the blower power ultimately increases the blower speed, which in-turn increases the air flow rate introduced to the stack. The air flow rate has two functions in the proposed system, i.e., providing the oxygen for the electrochemical reactions and providing cooling or heating to the stack. The temperature control strategy consists of two parts. Stack temperature gradient is controlled with blower power. If the temperature gradient goes higher than the set point, the blower power increases which increases the air flow rate which cools the stack. To control stack average temperature, the valve position changes to increase or decrease the air flow to oxidizer which affects the cell inlet air flow temperature. To decrease the cell average temperature, the valve opens more, to decrease the hot flow temperature in the air heat exchanger. In this study, the controller set-point temperature difference constraint is 50K. Also, the inlet temperature of both anode and cathode temperature are controlled to the set point of 1023K.

5.3.2.2 Stack power management

During dynamic operating condition, the stack power is controlled by manipulating the current in feed-forward controller. At each time among set of points in time vector, the current is calculated based upon the operating voltage and the stack power as below:

$$I|_{cell} = \frac{P_{Stack}}{\bar{V}_{Op} \times N_{Cell}} \quad \text{Equation 56}$$

5.3.2.3 Fuel utilization

In controller model, fuel flow rate is controlled by manipulating cell current and system fuel utilization in feed-forward controller as below:

$$\dot{n}_{CH_4}|_{System} = \frac{I|_{Cell}}{4 \times F \times FU|_{System}} \times N_{Cell} \quad \text{Equation 57}$$

where FU is SOFC system fuel utilization defined as the ratio between stoichiometric fuel flow required for the electrochemical reactions at a given current and the actual inlet fuel flow introduced to the system. It should be noticed that the controller keeps the fuel utilization constant at a nominal value for a wide range of operating conditions except for very low powers control of very low flow rates could lead to the possibility of concentration loss increases.

5.3.2.4 Steam-to-carbon ratio

To prevent carbon deposition in the stack the molar ratio of steam-to-carbon is set to 2.02 in this study. The anode recirculation valve is manipulated to control the amount of recirculated flow to keep the steam-to-carbon ratio at this set point.

5.4 Liquid Desiccant Dehumidifier Modeling

5.4.1 Liquid desiccant technology and system

Liquid desiccants have been used to produce dry air first in 1930s by Frigidaire Division of General Motors. The interest in liquid desiccants was increased after energy crisis and gas bubble in 1970s and 1980s. most on the interest was limited to Research & Development (R&D) activities until 1997, when Drykor started selling several thousands of LDAC until 2004 [51]. Interest in liquid desiccant dehumidification and cooling has increased due to liquid desiccant multiple benefits such as [52], [53]:

- LDACs do not run based on climate polluting or toxic refrigerants.
- LDACs can be powered by low grade waste heat (45°C upwards).
- LDACs can dehumidify the air at a temperature above its dew point, therefore they do not need a reheat process such as that required by conventional AC technologies.
- LDACs run mostly on heat; their electric demand is typically one-fourth that of a vapor-compression air conditioner.
- LDAC decouples latent and sensible heat removal.
- LDACs are exceptionally good at dehumidifying air; almost all the cooling they provide can be latent cooling.

These benefits allow LDACs to overcome problems with the conventional air conditioning. The most commonly used air conditioning is Vapor Compression Systems (VCS) due to stability in performance, lower cost, long life and resendable COP of between 2-4 [52]. However, VCS use harmful refrigerants such as R-22, R-41-A, and R- 134A which have high global warming potential and consume significant amount of electrical energy to drive the compressor [53]. Conventional cooling system such as chilled water or VCS cannot meet the latent cooling load

on humid days. The other popular air conditioning systems are absorption chillers, which replace the electric driven compressor with a heat driven absorber and generator. The COP of these systems is in the range of 0.5 in single effect cycles and up to 1.2 in double effect cycles [54]. All conventional chillers and air conditioners cool the air sensibly and, dehumidify the air by lowering the air temperature below its dewpoint so that moisture condenses and can be removed. The air that leaves this cooling coil in these traditional cooling systems is thus close to saturated conditions [55].

For supplying air at 18°C and 50% relative humidity, a conventional cooling system cools the air to 8°C and then reheats the air to 18°C as it is shown with blue lines in Figure 77. In this case the air conditioner is overcoming roughly 30% more than is required to meet the load, and then also using even more power to reheat the air to desired supply temperature. A LDAC uses liquid desiccant to dehumidify the air the supply air to 25% relative humidity and a temperature that is 10C above the desired temperature. It performs almost 100% latent cooling (in case of internal cooling), then relies on a separate cooling for remaining sensible cooling and eliminate the overcooling/heating process [55], [56]. Table 17 shows the comparison of liquid desiccant dehumidifier and VCS [57].

Figure 77. Liquid desiccant comparison to conventional air conditioning system.

Table 17. Comparison between liquid desiccant and vapor compression cooling [57].

Parameter	Vapor Compression	Liquid Desiccant
Initial Investment	Similar	Similar
Operation cost	High	Up to 40% saving
Driving Energy Source	Electricity, natural gas	Low-grade heat
Humidity Control	Average	Accurate
Temperature Control	Accurate	Average
Indoor Air Quality	Average	Good
Location Specific	Slightly	Yes
System Instalment	Average	Complicated
System Storage Capacity	Bad	Good

Figure 78 shows a typical industrial liquid desiccant system. In the absorber (also called conditioner) liquid desiccant absorbs the water from the air and dehumidifies the air. In this case, the regenerator is a bed of structured contact media similar to cooling tower. Liquid desiccant is first cooled to increase the ability of it to absorb water, and then sprayed onto the contact media. In this system, high flow rate of desiccant limits the desiccant temperature rises during absorption process. The air comes in direct contact with the liquid desiccant and gets dried and cooled. Typically, a ratio of the desiccant-to-air mass flow ratio that is on the order of one will limit the temperature rise of the desiccant. During the absorption process the liquid desiccant fluid becomes “weak,” that is, the desiccant concentration in water is lowered. The desiccant fluid must then be regenerated (concentration of desiccant in water raised) to remove the water that was absorbed in the absorber. The regeneration process is the reverse of absorption. The desiccant is heated to a temperature at which the water equilibrium pressure is higher than the ambient air water vapor pressure. Hot desiccant, typically between 70°C to 90°C, is sprayed over a bed of porous structure. The water is desorbed from the hot desiccant to flowing air through the bed. This air is typically exhausted to ambient. To reduce the energy use in the heater and cooler, usually an interchange heat exchanger is used to preheat the weak desiccant and leaving the conditioner with hot strong desiccant leaving the regenerator [51], [58]

Figure 78. Conceptual layout of industrial liquid-desiccant system [51].

Liquid desiccants have lower regeneration temperatures, higher dehumidification capacity and lower air side pressure drop which reduces the fan power. Liquid desiccant makes energy storage possible and has higher capacities to hold moisture than solid desiccants. With liquid desiccant simultaneous cooling and dehumidification is achievable. Solid desiccants are compact, simple, less subject to carryover and corrosion which the carry over problem of LDAC has been solved with new generation of liquid desiccant. Also, the cost of manufacturing a liquid desiccant system is lower than that of a solid desiccant wheel [52], [59].

5.4.1.1 Liquid desiccant solution

Liquid desiccants are materials that have high attraction to water. Lithium chloride (LiCl), Calcium Chloride (CaCl₂) and Lithium Bromide (LiBr) are common types of liquid desiccants. CaCl₂ is the cheapest solution [60] but has the poorest absorption ability. The strength of a desiccant is measured by its vapor pressure. When liquid desiccant is in equilibrium with the humid air, the temperature and vapor pressure of the humid air and the liquid desiccant should be the same. The equivalent humidity ratio of liquid desiccant (w_e can be found with the equilibrium state of the air as shown in Equation 58, where P is atmospheric pressure and p_s is the desiccant's vapor pressure).

$$w_e = 0.622 \frac{p_s}{P - p_s}$$

Equation 58

At any given temperature, desiccant that has a water vapor pressure in equilibrium with the humidity ratio of the air (iso-concentration line), produces a line that is closely in line with a constant relative humidity line on psychrometric chart. Lower concentrations of desiccant come into equilibrium at higher ambient air Relative Humidity (RH) levels. Liquid desiccant dehumidification is the inverse of evaporative cooling. Liquid desiccant can either absorb or desorb water from the air based on its relative humidity. If the equilibrium relative humidity of desiccant is below the relative humidity of the air, the desiccant absorbs water from the air and its temperature increases. The temperature that the air-desiccant interface approaches is called the brine-bulb temperature. This temperature is dependent upon air temperature and humidity, and liquid desiccant concentration in solution with water. The brine temperature is slightly higher than the temperature of intersection of constant enthalpy line from air state to equilibrium relative humidity of desiccant. This is due to the chemical heat of mixing between water and desiccant that is released in addition to latent heat of condensation.

During the dehumidification process, liquid desiccant absorbs the water from the air and releases heat, which decreases its water vapor pressure and ability to absorb water. Desiccant's ability to absorb water also decreases by increasing its temperature. For example, if a 43% LiCl at 26.6°C can dry the air to 23.2 grains. But, absorbing the amount of water that dilutes it from 43% to 42% would increase the desiccant temperature to 50.5°C which decreases the ability of desiccant to dry the air to 107.6 grains, whereas if we keep the desiccant temperature at 26.6°C, the 42% solution can dry air to 25.7 grains. The red arrow in Figure 79 shows the ambient air driving to equilibrium with LiCl in case of keeping the free surface of the desiccant at 26.6°C temperature. Increasing the temperature has the highest effects on desiccant losing its drying potential. Liu XH et al. [61], showed that in order to obtain better humidification performance, liquid desiccant should be heated rather than the air, and counter flow configuration is recommended.

Figure 79. Equilibrium relative humidity for lithium chloride.

Design of a liquid desiccant system depends on the choice of desiccant. Both glycols and solutions halide salts are used in LDAC. LiCl, CaCl₂ and LiBr are three of the most widely used halide salt desiccant solutions. Different Studies [62]–[64] measured thermodynamic properties of these three desiccants, and they found that LiCl solution is the most stable liquid desiccant, which offers the lowest water vapor pressure and dehydration concentration 30-40%. However, the cost of LiCl is relatively high. LiBr solution offers similar characteristics during dehumidification and regeneration process, but the cost of LiBr is about 20% higher than LiCl. Lithium based desiccants can be expensive especially when the storage of concentrated desiccant is important [51]. LiBr and LiCl are strong desiccants that can respectively dry the air to 6% relative humidity and 11% if they are saturates solution. LiBr is mainly used in closed system that doesn't have direct contact with air due to their higher oxidation potential and LiCl is mainly used in open systems. CaCl₂ solution is the cheapest and most widely available desiccant, but it can be unstable, depending on the air inlet conditions and the solution concentration rate. Halide salts are very corrosive to metals, so all the equipment is typically made of fiberglass, plastic, or other nonmetallic materials. For the cases that metal must be used, titanium is commonly specified [59]. As a less corrosive and more environmentally friendly solution, Potassium Formate (KCOOH) solution has recently been applied in desiccant cooling unit. KCOOH solution has low toxicity and viscosity, and they are neither corrosive nor volatile [65]. However, Longo and Gasperella [66] experimentally tested the performances of a liquid desiccant cooling system using LiBr, LiCl and KCOOH solutions. Results show that LiCl and LiBr solutions demonstrated better dehumidification performance compared with KCOOH solution, which performed better in regeneration process.

Glycols are mainly used in industrial equipment. Glycols such as triethylene and propylene have low toxicity and compatible with most metals, but they are volatile. A mixture of 96% triethylene glycol and 4% water the same effect as a 42% lithium chloride solution. However, at equilibrium, the molar concentration of the glycol in air will be in the order of 1% that of the water vapor. The environmental impact and economic penalty of the triethylene glycol volatility is unacceptable in LDACs [51], [59].

5.4.1.2 Liquid desiccant system classification and design

Liquid desiccant systems can be classified as direct-contact or indirect contact, as adiabatic or intercooler, and by flow pattern: parallel flow, cross flow, counter flow and counter-cross flow. Contactors (porous beds of various designs) are typically used to bring the desiccant solution and air stream into contact for both the dehumidification and regeneration processes. In direct-contact dehumidifiers/regenerators, heat and water vapor transfer take place between air and desiccant solution streams through direct contact. Desiccant solution usually flows downward due to gravity. The processed air can either flow in a parallel, counter or a cross flow (the most commonly used) manner across the contactor surface. However, counter flow systems are generally showing better dehumidification ability compared with other two flow patterns due to the fact that the outlet air stream is located at the entrance of the fresh desiccant solution's inlet [67]. This can be either in a direct or in indirect manner. In an adiabatic dehumidifier, the solution temperature increases which gradually decreases the solution dehumidification capability [68]. By introducing internal cooling, the heat can be removed from liquid desiccant, which keeps the solution vapor pressure at lower level and improving the dehumidification process. Experimental and theoretical research [68], [69] results indicate that internally cooled dehumidifier offers higher dehumidification effectiveness.

The most commonly used and studied liquid desiccant dehumidifier/regenerator systems amongst the various direct contact types incorporate packed beds [70]. In this design, solution is usually distributed from the top of the packed bed with the help of spray nozzles and flows over the packed bed where it comes in direct contact with the air stream. This design is inexpensive and widely used for commercial and residential because it allows large contacting area between air and desiccant with simple configuration. High heat and mass transfer efficiency but the air flowing through the highly flooded porous beds causes a large pressure drop on process air side and, thus, high parasitic power consumption while flowing through the packing material. It also requires a separate heat exchanger to cool the desiccant before it is delivered to the porous bed, and the air may entrain droplets of desiccant as it flows through the highly flooded porous bed. This last disadvantage is particularly important because of the corrosiveness of the desiccant. Carryover of desiccant droplets can be eliminated by droplet filters, but at the expense of additional pressure drop. In an internally cooled/heated (i.e. isothermal) packed bed, the solution is continuously cooled/heated by a third fluid (e.g. water) as it passes through the packed bed. As a result, the solution experiences no (or small) change in its temperature as it passes through the packed bed, and consequently the potential for mass transfer is improved compared to an adiabatic packed bed [70]. Bansal et al. [71] compared the experimental performances of adiabatic and internally-cooled packed-bed dehumidifiers. It was found that the effectiveness of

the internally-cooled packed bed is 28–45% higher than the effectiveness of the adiabatic packed bed, depending on the operating conditions. It was found that the counter flow configuration has the highest effectiveness under air dehumidification and hot desiccant-driven regeneration conditions, compared to parallel-flow and cross-flow configurations, while, the parallel-flow configuration resulted in the highest effectiveness under hot air-driven regeneration conditions [61], [72]. Although the packed-bed design is characterized by several advantages, the transfer of liquid droplets to the air stream (called carryover) is a drawback of the packed-bed design especially when it is operated under high flow rates. Thus, a mist eliminator is usually installed at the air exit to capture any entrained desiccant droplets, which increases the air-side pressure drop, as well as the capital and operating costs of the packed bed LDAC system [51], [55], [70].

AIL Research patented a low flow LDAC with more than an order of magnitude less flow of desiccant compared to flooded-bed systems in 1994. This design replaces the bed of porous contact media with a plastic heat exchanger that has internal cooling/heating. In high flow LDAC, depending on the whether it's a conditioner or regenerator, the liquid desiccant is either cooled or heated before it is sprayed or dripped onto the packed bed. Low flow LDAC has internal cooling or heating in which heat transfer fluid flows within the plates of the heat exchanger, desiccant flows on the outer surface of the plates, and air flows between the plates which are spaced 0.25in. This system does not rely on thermal mass of liquid desiccant to control its temperature [59]. Figure 80 shows the main three components of internal cooling systems: the conditioner, the regenerator, and the Interchange Heat Exchanger (IHX). The conditioner and regenerator both are liquid to air heat exchanger. A very thin film of desiccant flow in wicks on the outer surfaces of the plates, and air flows in the gaps between the plates. For conditioner a coolant typically water from cooling tower (55°–85°F) flows within the plates, however, for regenerator, hot water (160°–212°F) which can be supplied by boiler or solar thermal collectors, recovered heat from an engine or fuel cell, or other energy source flows within the plates. An interchange heat exchanger is used to increase the efficiency of the regenerator and decrease the cooling load on the conditioner. The warm, humid air leaving the regenerator can also be used in an air to air heat exchanger to preheat the air that enters the regenerator.

Figure 80. Major components and packaging of the AILR LDAC [59].

Three basic ways to regenerate the desiccant system is with a thermal source: solar, water heater, and a double effect. The water heater or boiler can be fueled by many sources, including natural gas, Combined Heat and Power (CHP), or even biofuels. Hot water can also be produced by recovered heat from an engine or fuel cell, or other energy source flows within the plates. Thermally driven single stage regenerators are typically supplied by hot water above 70oC, but preferably 82oC. The higher fluid temperatures increase the water removal capacity of regenerator significantly [51], [59].

5.4.1.3 Integrated liquid desiccant air conditioning

Integration of LDAC with a dewpoint indirect evaporative cooler can efficiently deliver both latent and sensible cooling with minimal electric demands. This integration has been developed and patented by NREL (Alliance for Sustainable Energy LLC 2008) and been named Desiccant enhanced Evaporative air-conditioning (DEVap) [59]. As shown in Figure 81 in DEVap concept a portion of warm indoor air is mixed with ventilation air. This mixed air goes through the heat exchanger and comes into contact with the liquid desiccant through a permeable channel. The desiccant absorbs the water vapor in the air. Then, air is cooled and supplied to the building space. A portion of supplied air which has its dew point reduced is recirculated as the secondary air stream. This secondary air comes into contact with the water layer through a permeable membrane. Water evaporates into the air through the membrane. The two air streams are separated through the plastic sheets thermal energy including the heat of absorption flows.

Figure 81. Physical DEVap Concept description[59].

The use of membrane technology prevents the desiccant carry over into the supply air stream and it provides a large contact surface area for the heat and mass transfer between the liquid and air. As a result, membrane-based contactors can effectively improve the performance of a liquid desiccant-based air conditioning processes. The introduction of a membrane provides additional resistance to heat and mass transfer, therefore much work is focused on improving this with novel supported liquid membranes [51]. The waterside membrane is not necessary and omitting it can reduce the cost. However, the semipermeable membrane is necessary for desiccant side to prevent desiccant leak to the air. The breakthrough pressure should be 20psi or lower to avoid desiccant leakage. The membrane should be 25 μm and have pore size of 0.1 μm . Its open area should exceed 70% to promote vapor transport. Polypropylene membrane from Celgard is one possible candidate for DEVap application [59]. The deep cooling of the indirect evaporative cooler section requires a dry cooling sink; thus, some dry supply air is siphoned off (5%–30% under maximum cooling load) to provide this exhaust air stream. This section is placed in a counter flow arrangement to maximize the use of this air stream. This is essential because it has been dried with desiccant, and thus has a higher embodied energy than unconditioned air. The result is that the temperature of supply air is limited by its dew point and will come out between 55°–75°F depending on how much is siphoned off. Combined with the desiccant's variable drying ability, the DEVap Air Conditioning (A/C) system controls sensible and latent cooling independently. DEVap does not require a cooling tower, which reduces its maintenance requirements. Dehumidification can be controlled by the desiccant concentration that is supplied to the device. The outlet humidity level can be controlled by controlling the supplied desiccant concentration or decreasing the flow of highly concentrated desiccant. The latter allows the highly concentrated desiccant to quickly be diluted and thus act as a weaker desiccant solution in the device. From inspection, the peak electricity draw of the DEVap A/C is

considerably less than the standard A/C. This is primarily because compressor power is eliminated and replaced with only fan power to push air through the DEVap cooling core [59].

NREL have designed a 1-ton DEVap system for a typical Gulf Coast condition with no water side membrane and LiCl as the desiccant as shown in Figure 82. Figure 83 shows the airstream process of DEVap on psychrometric chart. The design criteria were to supply cooling to the building at 7Btu/lb (380cfm/ton) and a Sensible Heat Ratio (SHR) of 0.6 while maintaining 55% indoor RH. NREL models shows that in all residential cases, the DEVap A/C provided more than necessary humidity control. Allowing indoor humidity to rise above 50% RH would have significant energy improvement. In the summertime, when sensible loads are high (high SHR), the DEVap A/C continuously maintained the space at less than 50% RH. This level of humidity control can be reduced to create higher energy savings. In general, DEVap perform better in new construction building with added ventilation and tighter envelope because sensible heat ratio decreases. Their analysis shows regional water use (site + off-site) for the DEVap system is 2.0–3.0gal/ton.hr, is similar to the regional impact that DX A/C imposes (off-site only). The DEVap A/C does increase site water use, but in general, the regional impact is small. Implementation of the DEVap A/C in commercial cases shows a higher energy savings level than the residential cases, primarily because of the higher cooling loads of commercial buildings and their increased ventilation requirements. DEVap regional water use is expected to be 2.0–3.0gal/ton.hr for commercial buildings. Similar to the residential case, the DEVap A/C has minimal impact on regional water use compared to DX A/C [59], [73].

Figure 82. DEVap air conditioner schematic. (a) four stack channel pairs (b) top view, one channel pair[59].

Figure 83. DEVap airstreams on a psychrometric chart [73].

The integration of LDACS with VCS can provide subcooling effect from the condenser outlet to the compressor inlet which leads to improved system performance. She et al. [74] proposed a new energy-efficient refrigeration system subcooled by liquid desiccant dehumidification and evaporation. In the proposed system, liquid desiccant system produces very dry air for an indirect evaporative cooler, which sub-cools the vapor compression refrigeration system to get higher COP than conventional refrigeration system. The desiccant cooling system uses the condensation heat for the desiccant regeneration. The results show great improvement of COP for the proposed system, with maximum COPs about 18.8% higher than that of conventional VCS. Khalil [75] experimentally investigate a multipurpose desiccant integrated with vapor-compression air conditioning. The system is designed to meet the cooling load of spaces with large latent heat and at the same time to extract water from atmospheric air. the integrated system total cooling capacity is up to 6.2kW. The effect of regeneration temperature, condenser and evaporator temperature on the system COP and specific moisture recovery were analyzed under different liquid desiccant flow rates. The authors concluded that the COP of the proposed system was as high as 3.8 (68% higher than that of conventional VCS), with further 53% more annual energy saving. Based on the similar testing, Bassuoni [76] has applied CaCl₂ as the desiccant for the experimental testing. The results showed that about 54% COP improvement was achieved. Many studies have proposed hybrid LDAC- VCS where the liquid desiccant has been used to dehumidify the supply air [77]–[79]. Mansuriya et al. [79] analyzed a modified liquid desiccant dehumidification incorporated vapor compression refrigeration system based on thermo-economic approach. The system is optimized based on the co-efficient of

performance and the total annual cost of the system. The results show that 51.3% of the total cooling load can be handled by the desiccant dehumidifier alone. This significant sharing of heat duty by addition of liquid desiccant dehumidification to conventional vapor compression refrigeration system justifies this hybridization for humid and hotter climates. COP of optimized system shows 68.4% improve compared to coefficient of performance of stand-alone vapor compression refrigeration system for handling the same cooling load. Dai et al. [80] studies the integration of desiccant dehumidification, evaporative cooling and vapor compression air conditioning. In this system, latent cooling of the air is carried out in the dehumidifier, and air sensible cooling via the VCS cooling coil. Experimental investigation demonstrates significant increase (56%) in cooling production and COP of the new hybrid system compared with vapor compression system alone. Capozzoli et al. [81] has economically analyzed a case based on the climatic conditions of three cities in Italy. Their results show considerable reduction of electric energy demand as well as better control of thermal-hygrometric conditions were noted. A simple payback of about 1 year has been obtained. Researchers have also studied integration of solar driven hybrid liquid desiccant and VCS. Li et al. [82] analyzed this system for Hong Kong climate condition using EnergyPlus. The results showed that an annual operation energy saving of 6760kWh compared to conventional VCS and a payback period of 7 years for a 19kW cooling capacity design system. Su et al. [83] looks at driving vapor compression chiller by generated electricity from solar for cooling the desiccant solution for a two-stage dehumidification, and the released heat from the collector is used for the desiccant regeneration. Simulation results show the proposed system has a superior power saving ability of 55.65% comparing with the conventional one, besides the equivalent power generation efficiency reaches 8.7% in the base design condition. A comparative driven force analysis showed the two-stage dehumidification has a better match of driven force compared with the single-stage liquid desiccant dehumidification, thus leading to a reduced irreversible loss of 65.43%. Sensitivity analysis indicated that the dehumidification temperature has a decisive effect on the system performance.

In heap pump driven systems, the cooling capacity from the evaporator is used to cool the liquid desiccant and exhaust heat from the condenser is used to regenerate the liquid desiccant. In this process, there are two air streams, one outdoor fresh air (a1) that will be cooled and dehumidifier, and the second one (a3), a stream air used to regenerate the liquid desiccant (a3). In this configuration there are three liquid desiccant circulation flow as shown in Figure 84: one in dehumidifier (S5-S6), one in regenerator (S7, S8), and one circulating between the heat exchanger (S1-S2, S3-S4). The flow rate in the latter one is one order of magnitude less than the other two flows [51].

Figure 84. Heat pump driven liquid desiccant air handling devices [51].

Many studies have been conducted on combined heat pump desiccant dehumidifiers for different case studies, different configurations, and different desiccant solutions. All these studies have theoretically and experimentally shown improvement in COP and energy savings [84]–[94]. Sanaye et al. [93] modeled and optimized a hybrid liquid desiccant-heat pump system containing dehumidification and cooling section. The system was analyzed in four energy, exergy, economic and environmental aspects. Then, the system was optimized for total annual cost and exergy efficiency. Results for our case study showed that the proposed optimized system decreased the electricity consumption for 33.2% in comparison with that for an electrical HP system during seven months of operation in a year (18.9% due to using desiccant dehumidifying system and 81.1% due to using a heat exchanger instead of an electrical heater). This amount of lower electricity consumption also provided 1.85e5kgCO₂/year lower CO₂ production (33.2%) in comparison with that for a conventional HP system. The COP of the system at the optimum point was also about 4.83 (in comparison with 2.74 for the conventional case in which heat pump and electrical heater were used). Jradi and Riffat [95] experimentally investigated a micro-scale tri-generation consisting of an organic Rankine-cycle, dehumidification and cooling unit. A scroll expander was used in the Rankine unit for heat and power generation. Cooling unit was a dew point evaporative cooler to provide the cooling capacity through air cooling. An experimental setup was built and the micro-scale tri-generation system was tested under different operational conditions using a wood pellet biomass boiler as a heating source. It is shown that the proposed system is capable of providing about 9.6kW heating power, 6.5kW cooling power and 500W electric power. The overall efficiency of the tri-generation system is about 85%. The dehumidification-cooling system has a thermal COP of 0.86 and electrical COP of 7.7.

Solar has been used as the heating source for solution regeneration. The solution temperature is usually below 80°C which fit well with solar provided temperature and solar radiation availability matches with cooling demand [96]. During recent years many researches have been investigating integration of LDAC with solar theoretically and experimentally. Katejanekam and Kumar [97] simulated a solar regenerated liquid desiccant ventilation pre-

conditioning system for Thailand climate. In their proposed system, the solar energy is used for regeneration process and cooling water from a cooling tower for precooling. The effects of various parameters on the moisture removal rate and evaporation rate were analyzed theoretically. The results suggest that the solar radiation, ventilation rate, and desiccant solution concentration have the most influence on the system. They also suggested that balance between the water removed at the dehumidifier and that evaporated at the regenerator needs to be considered to maintain uniform performance during continuous operation. Similarly, Mohaisen and Ma [98] developed and simulated a solar assisted liquid dehumidification air conditioning system using LiCl solution on Matlab Simulink platform. Their result has been validated with experimental results by Fumo and Goswami [99]. The simulation results based on three consecutive sunny summer days in Sydney show daily COP of 0.5-0.55 by the proposed system and 73.4% of thermal energy required for thermal regeneration was provided by the solar collectors. Croffot and Harrisson [100] experimentally evaluated the performance of a solar driven system installed in Canada. The system includes a low-flow parallel plate liquid desiccant air conditioner, and a 95 m² evacuated tube solar collector array. Results from five test days have shown an overall solar collector efficiency of 56%, solar fraction of 63% and a thermal COP of 0.47. The average total cooling was 12.3kW and average latent cooling was 13.2kW. Peng et al. [101] studied a solar air pre-treatment collector/regenerator. Their simulation results showed that the storage capacity of proposed system could be improved by 50%, when the regeneration temperature was 60°C, and the inlet air specific humidity was 2.33kg/kg. In another study, Lychnos and Davies [113] performed experimental and theoretical simulation for a solar powered liquid desiccant system using MgCl₂. The theoretical model was developed and verified with the experimental results. Compared with conventional evaporative cooler, the proposed system could further lower the average daily maximum temperature by 5.5-7.5oC. Alizadeh [102] fields tested implementing polymer plate heat exchanger into LDAC in Australia summer weather condition. Lithium chloride with 43% was used in the experiments and a scavenger air regenerator concentrates the dilute solution from the dehumidifier using hot water from flat plate solar. Alizadeh [102] experimentally analyzed the effects of various air flow rate and desiccant flow rate on the system performance. The experimentally obtained data was compared with a developed model. The comparison showed a good agreement between the experiments and model predictions. The results showed that the proposed system could provide cooling capacity up to 20kW with dehumidification efficiency up to 72%.

Qi et al. [103] simulated yearly system performance of solar assisted LDAC for commercial application in five cities (Singapore, Beijing, Huston, LA and Boulder). In this study, the effects of various solar collector areas and monthly solar radiations, ambient air conditions on the electricity consumption saving and monthly average COP were theoretically analyzed. Results shows that for buildings located in humid areas with low sensible-total heat ratio, the electricity energy reduction of the system was high and about 450MWh in Houston and Singapore and payback was approximately 7 years. For building in dry climate, although the total cooling load was low, up to 45% of electricity of AC can be saved because of significant improve in chiller COP during more than 70% of operation time and the payback was around 22 years. However, for the buildings with mild outdoor humidity, such as those in Beijing and Los

Angeles the electricity energy saved only around 100MWh and the cost payback period was more than 30 years, and the application of LDAC was not that suitable. Li and Zhang [104], [105] investigated a solar energy driven hollow fiber membrane-based desalination system. The system consists of a membrane-based humidifier, a fin-and-tube type dehumidifier and a solar heating unit, which consists of a U-tube evacuated solar collector and a heat storage tank. The hollow fiber membrane-based humidifier is similar to a shell-and-tube heat mass exchanger. Through numerical modelling and experimental tests, they found that the COP of the system can reach about 0.75 and electric COP of 36.13 is achievable, which means electrical energy consumption is much less due to solar energy reclamation. Results show that solar accounts for 92.0% of the electric energy consumption by the entire system. Sensible heat losses account for most of the energy losses from the system. Chen et al. [106] proposes solar assisted liquid desiccant dehumidifier and regenerative indirect evaporative cooling (LDD- Regenerative Indirect Evaporative Cooling (RIEC)) system for fresh air treatment. The hot and humid fresh air is firstly dehumidified by LDD and then sensibly cooled by RIEC. The thermal energy captured by solar collectors is used for desiccant solution regeneration. In this study, they have looked into the influences of solar collector area and inlet air conditions and optimizing the extraction air ratio of RIEC. The energy saving ratio is quantitatively evaluated with respect to a conventional A/C system. Results shows that the energy saving ratio ranges from 22.4% to 53.2% under various inlet air conditions.

This characteristic of liquid desiccant dehumidification system that the dilute liquid desiccant can be regenerated by low grade heat makes it attractive option for integrating with thermal sources. Many studies have been done on integration of liquid desiccant system with solar, vapor compression, heat pump, and CHPs. But only two research has been done integrating liquid desiccant with SOFCs.

5.4.1.4 Liquid desiccant integrated with SOFC system

The typical SOFC system exhaust temperature matches very well with the required temperature for liquid dehumidification [107]. Elmer [52] has looked into design, development and proof of concept combined generation of power, cooling and heating based on SOFC and Liquid desiccant air conditioning technology for building application. A 1.5kW SOFC integrated with liquid desiccant has been proposed for providing heating, cooling and electricity to low carbon buildings. Elmer et al. [108] used empirical SOFC and liquid desiccant component data for an energetic, economic and environmental analysis. They have used a simple 0D model in Engineering Equation Solver (EES) platform for regeneration, dehumidifier and fuel cell. The model is based on dimensionless vapor pressure and temperature difference ratio designed for packed bed liquid desiccant. The results show (1) the moisture removal of the supply rate is mainly controlled by desiccant temperature and cooling water temperature in constant flow rates. (2) The air inlet condition has a large effect on cooling output performance and the unit performs better in a hot and humid climate. (3) By increasing the regeneration heat source temperature more water vapor vaporizes from the weak solution. The model they used have limitation such as not including the effectiveness of heat and mass exchanger effectiveness, geometry of the

contactor, and desiccant carry over [52]. For desiccant air conditioning system Elmer [61] developed an Integrated Desiccant air Conditioning System (IDCS). This system combines regenerator, dehumidifier and evaporative inter-cooler into a single membrane-based heat and mass exchanger to reduce the size, complexity and leakage. The IDCS operates with a KCOOH desiccant working fluid. The liquid desiccant is sprays through nozzle from the top where regenerator is located and flows downward due to gravity. In this design instead of preheating desiccant before regeneration and precooling it before dehumidification, thermal energy is supplied to the regenerator through airstream and an evaporative inter-cooler is designed. This is because all desiccant flow is contained within one complete Heat and Mass Exchanger (HMX) the solution cannot be extracted for prior heating and cooling. This feature is weakness of this design as precooling and preheating of liquid desiccant increases the performance of the system [59] Their design was supposed to significantly reduces the number of heat exchangers, pipes, and ducting in liquid desiccant air conditioning systems. The main issue with this integrated system was imbalance between moisture removal rate in the dehumidifier and moisture addition rate in the regenerator. This mass imbalance is primarily due to the available surface area for heat and mass exchange in the regenerator being too small and an insufficient vapor pressure differential between the air and desiccant solution. In order to regenerate the desiccant solution back to its original condition following the dehumidification process, the regenerator needs to operate for extended time periods. Across the variables investigated there is a greater instantaneous moisture removal rate in the dehumidifier than moisture addition rate in the regenerator. Desiccant solution leakage/carry-over on the dehumidifier side of the HMX has been noticed during the experiment as well [65]. In response to the highlighted shortcomings of the novel IDCS Theo Elmer developed a Separated liquid Desiccant air Conditioning System (SDCS) for tri-generation system integration. SDCS consist of three separate cores including dehumidifier, regenerator, and an evaporative cooler. The SDCS uses a semi-permeable, microporous-membrane-based crossflow contactor, operating with KCOOH desiccant solution. The solution channel consists of polyethylene sheet, with fiber membrane attached on either side to allow diffusion of water but prevent the liquid desiccant entering the air side. In evaporative cooler, air and water come into contact in a crossflow HMX. Before liquid desiccant entering the dehumidifier, a plate heat exchanger is used to precool the desiccant to increase its potential. After dehumidifying the air, the weak solution enters the dehumidifier tank. The regenerator has a tank and pump which delivers weak desiccant to the top of regenerator. Desiccant is preheated before entering the dehumidifier. The strong desiccant flows to regenerator tank after regeneration. In this design, because the entire SDCS is placed within the environmental, the water for the evaporative cooler and desiccant for dehumidifier are at the ambient temperature which has an impact on moisture absorption capacity of the desiccant and the sensible cooling. This design causes little to no sensible cooling achievable. Also, the evaporative cooler only provides around 80–150W of cooling over their study range. As a result, the evaporative cooling provided is not enough to produce a sufficient solution temperature decrease and to provide sensible cooling to the supply air in the dehumidifier. Theo Elmer et al. experimental results on SDCS show (1) effective instantaneous balancing of the dehumidifier and regenerator across a range of environmental and operational values, (2) operation of the dehumidifier is dictated, to

some degree by the available SOFC thermal exhaust, (3) COP values in the range of 0.4–0.66 are achievable with a low-grade thermal input (45–60°C) typical of an SOFC CHP system and (4) potential for non-synchronous operation in a tri-generation system context, bringing about improvements to peak cooling output and total system efficiency [109]. Elmer et al. used empirical SOFC and liquid desiccant component data for an energetic, economic and environmental analysis. The 1.5kW BlueGen SOFC systems is electrically connected to the grid to import or export as required. The waste heat recovery circuit is connected to a home's 300L hot water cylinder which also includes an auxiliary gas boiler. Experimental results of Theo Elmer et al. show the electrical efficiency of the SOFC system increases from 14% at 200W to maximum of 60% at 150W and then decreases to 56% at 2000W capacity. Thermal output from fuel cells varies linearly from 320Wth at 200We to 540Wth at 1500W. The calculated water heat recovery temperature for 2l/min flow based varies between 47 C at 100We to 52°C at 2000We [110].

Be Power Tech, Inc. [56] developed BeCool, a natural gas-powered air-conditioning system that produced electricity as by product on the site. The innovative idea shifts some grid-powered electricity for cooling demand to natural gas which would substantially reduce peak summer power demand and help to reduce the need for costly peaking power plants. Their studies showed that their 5ton BeCool unit eliminates ~ 10kW of peak electricity demand, generates 43MWh/yr electricity and saves ~ 10MWh/yr compared to conventional air conditioning. They build a prototype and the test results showed that the electrical power efficiency was 45% to 60%. The primary potential energy saving is 4.1 Quads, and the technology has the potential to reduce 222 million metric tons of CO₂. Their analysis for California climate 7 and 14 shows 53% CO₂ reduction in a 50% electrical efficiency for fuel cell and 90% combined heat and power efficient fuel cell system is used.

BeCool uses exhaust heat from the fuel cell and heat from the burner to increase the concentration of LiCl to 42% mass fraction in the regeneration process. Be Power Tech designed and built an experimental prototype BeCool system integrating a 2.5kW SOFC system (EnGen system), a boost natural gas burner, and a custom-made liquid desiccant air conditioner designed to produce from 2.5-tons (8.8kW thermal) to 4-tons (14.0kW thermal) of cooling. The system was tested under multiple outdoor air conditions. Their study showed that, in all cases the heat supplied by the fuel cell was not sufficient to provide the heat required for the air conditioning process, since these isolated tests could not rely on storage from daily continuous regeneration. For this reason, the supplemental natural gas burner was used to supply the heat required [56].

Integrated fuel cell dehumidification systems have never previously been studied for data center application. The only two studies that have looked at integration of SOFC with dehumidification systems were focused on building applications of the technology. The models that have been used in previous studies are simple steady state models for the fuel cell and liquid desiccant systems. In this study, we investigate the integration of rack and row level fuel cell powered servers with Liquid Desiccant Dehumidifier (LDD) technology that can be dynamically dispatched to produce electricity and cooling in various amounts to meet power and air conditioning demands of data centers. In addition, the storage capacity to meet the demand of data center for the entire year is evaluated. The objectives of this phase of the study focus on

theoretically evaluating the integrated system concept and to assess the achievable air conditioning from SOFC waste heat. To explore the feasibility of thermally integrating SOFC with LDD, a spatially resolved physical model developed in MATLAB is used to simulate the operating characteristics of this SOFC system. A corresponding physical model is developed to simulate the liquid desiccant air conditioner for dehumidification. This study considers SOFC systems capable of powering single server rack (~12kW) and row of servers (~240kW) and the operation of an LDD for cooling and dehumidification of that same configuration. The small-scale LDD operation is based on distributed waste heat from each individual SOFC at the rack level. The analysis will indicate whether waste-heat based cooling and dehumidification can power the servers and maintaining server operating temperatures and humidity in the safe range for different weather conditions.

5.4.2 Liquid desiccant component modeling

The LDD system model is based upon a similar DEVap concept developed by NREL [59]. The current physical model is developed to simulate the DEVAP components including regenerator, dehumidifier and indirect evaporative cooler. LiCl solution is the working fluid used in this system. Figure 85 shows the LLD system diagram.

Figure 85. Configuration of the LLD system.

Energy balance, and mass balance equations were applied to the LDD model. For the air and water properties EES [111] has been used, whereas for LiCl properties a library has been developed based on literature experimental results. MATLAB was used to simulate the operation of the LDD system under different SOFC exhaust and weather conditions. The detailed model for each component is explained in the next section.

5.4.2.1 Dehumidifier modeling

During the dehumidification process, the liquid desiccant is in contact with air through a permeable membrane that allows water vapor interaction but prevents the flow of LiCl into the air. LiCl absorbs the water vapor in the air until it reaches water vapor pressure equilibrium with the air. This process is exothermic. The desiccant is kept cool by the evaporation of water to the exhaust heat stream. Figure 86 shows the dehumidifier unit schematic.

Figure 86. Dehumidifier unit schematic.

Equations for each stream are presented below. Mass transfer is driven by a vapor pressure differential between the air and desiccant solution as shown in Equation 60. The supply air side heat transfer for the dehumidifier is given by Equation 62. The heat transferred to the solution includes the sensible heat due to the temperature difference between the desiccant and air, and desiccant and water, plus the latent heat of absorption and enthalpy of dilution, given by Equation 66 [51], [73].

Supply air side:

$$(\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,i} = -J_{sa}dA \quad \text{Equation 59}$$

$$J_{sa} = \frac{P_a - P_{sol}}{R_w T_a \left(\frac{1}{h_{ma}} + \frac{\delta_{mem}}{D_{mem}} \right)} \quad \text{Equation 60}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{sa,i} = q_{sa} dA \quad \text{Equation 61}$$

$$q_{sa} = \frac{T_{LD} - T_{sa}}{\left(\frac{1}{h_{sa}} \right) + \left(\frac{\delta}{k} \right)_{mem} + \left(\frac{\delta}{2k} \right)_{sol}} \quad \text{Equation 62}$$

Liquid desiccant side:

$$(\dot{m})_{LD,e} - (\dot{m})_{LD,i} = J_{sa} dA \quad \text{Equation 63}$$

$$(\dot{m}C)_{LD,e} - (\dot{m}C)_{LD,i} = 0 \quad \text{Equation 64}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{LD,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{LD,i} = q_{LD} dA \quad \text{Equation 65}$$

$$q_{LD} = q_{lat_{sa}} - q_{sa} - q_{plate} \quad \text{Equation 66}$$

$$q_{lat_{sa}} = L_{sa}(h_{fg} + h_{mix}) \quad \text{Equation 67}$$

$$q_{plate} = \frac{T_{LD} - T_w}{\left(\frac{\delta}{k} \right)_w + \left(\frac{\delta}{k} \right)_p + \left(\frac{\delta}{2k} \right)_{sol}} \quad \text{Equation 68}$$

Exhaust air side:

$$(\dot{m}\omega)_{ea,e} - (\dot{m}\omega)_{ea,i} = J_{ea}dA \quad \text{Equation 69}$$

$$J_e = h_{me}(\omega_w - \omega_e) \quad \text{Equation 70}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_pT)_{ea,e} - (\dot{m}C_pT)_{ea,i} = -q_{ea}dA \quad \text{Equation 71}$$

$$q_{ea} = q_{lat} - q_{plate} \quad \text{Equation 72}$$

$$q_{lat} = J_e h_{fg} \quad \text{Equation 73}$$

$$q_{ea} = h_{ea}(T_{ea} - T_w) \quad \text{Equation 74}$$

Where P_a and P_{sol} are the inlet equivalent vapor pressure of the air and liquid desiccant solution respectively in P_a . h_{ma} ($\frac{kg}{m^2.s}$) and h_{as} ($\frac{k}{m^2.K}$) are the respective convective mass transfer and heat transfer coefficients of the air. R_w is the molar gas constant for water ($461.5 \frac{J}{kg.K}$).

5.4.3 Indirect evaporative cooling modeling

The dehumidified air goes to an indirect evaporative cooler after the dehumidifier where it is cooled indirectly by water evaporating into a separate airstream in counter flow. A portion of cold dehumidified supply air is recirculated to the counter flow direction as the second stream to cool the primary air stream. Figure 87 shows the indirect evaporative cooler schematic.

Figure 87. Indirect evaporative cooler schematic.

Supply air stream and cooling air stream energy and mass balance equations are presented in Equation 75 to Equation 84.

Supply air:

$$(\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,i} = 0 \quad \text{Equation 75}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_pT)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}C_pT)_{sa,i} = -q_{sa}dA \quad \text{Equation 76}$$

$$q_{sa} = h_{sa}(T_{sa} - T_p) \quad \text{Equation 77}$$

Exhaust air:

$$(\dot{m}\omega)_{ea,e} - (\dot{m}\omega)_{ea,i} = J_e dA \quad \text{Equation 78}$$

$$J_e = h_{me}(\omega_w - \omega_e) \quad \text{Equation 79}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{ea,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{ea,i} = -q_{ea} dA \quad \text{Equation 80}$$

$$q_{ea} = q_{lat} - q_{plate} \quad \text{Equation 81}$$

$$q_{lat} = J_e h_{fg} \quad \text{Equation 82}$$

$$q_{plate} = \frac{T_p - T_w}{\left(\frac{\delta}{k}\right)_p + \left(\frac{\delta}{k}\right)_w} \quad \text{Equation 83}$$

$$q_{ea} = h_{ea}(T_{ea} - T_w) \quad \text{Equation 84}$$

5.4.4 Regenerator modeling

Absorption process weakens the desiccant solution and reduce its ability to absorb water vapor. To desorb water vapor from LiCl, the desiccant is heated to have equilibrium water vapor pressure that is higher than that of the air. This regeneration process is the reverse of dehumidification and can use low grade heat sources. In this study, the SOFC system exhaust heat is used in this regeneration process to increase the concentration of LiCl in solution. Then, the concentrated liquid desiccant solution is stored. When moisture must be removed, the high concentration solution is used to dehumidify the outside air. Figure 88 shows the regenerator schematic.

Figure 88. Regenerator unit schematic.

Supply air:

$$(\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}\omega)_{sa,i} = -J_{sa}dA \quad \text{Equation 85}$$

$$J_{sa} = \frac{P_a - P_{sol}}{R_w T_a \left(\frac{1}{h_{ma}} + \frac{\delta_{mem}}{D_{mem}} \right)} \quad \text{Equation 86}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{sa,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{sa,i} = q_{sa}dA \quad \text{Equation 87}$$

$$q_{sa} = \frac{T_{LD} - T_{sa}}{\left(\frac{1}{h_{sa}} \right) + \left(\frac{\delta}{k} \right)_{mem} + \left(\frac{\delta}{2k} \right)_{sol}} \quad \text{Equation 88}$$

Liquid desiccant:

$$(\dot{m})_{LD,e} - (\dot{m})_{LD,i} = J_{sa} dA \quad \text{Equation 89}$$

$$(\dot{m}C)_{LD,e} - (\dot{m}C)_{LD,i} = 0 \quad \text{Equation 90}$$

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{LD,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{LD,i} = q_{LD} dA \quad \text{Equation 91}$$

$$q_{LD} = q_{lat\,sa} - q_{sa} - q_{plate} \quad \text{Equation 92}$$

$$q_{lat\,sa} = L_{sa}(h_{fg} + h_{mix}) \quad \text{Equation 93}$$

$$q_{plate} = \frac{T_{LD} - T_w}{\left(\frac{\delta}{2k}\right)_w + \left(\frac{\delta}{k}\right)_p + \left(\frac{\delta}{2k}\right)_{sol}} \quad \text{Equation 94}$$

Exhaust air:

$$(\dot{m}C_p T)_{w,e} - (\dot{m}C_p T)_{w,i} = q_w dA \quad \text{Equation 95}$$

$$q_w = q_{plate} \quad \text{Equation 96}$$

5.4.5 Control strategy for the liquid desiccant system

The dehumidifier's model inlet parameters are the weather conditions, the return air condition, desiccant temperature and concentration, and cold water temperature and flow. The

model output is supply air temperature, desiccant outlet temperature and exhaust air temperature. In order to keep the humidity of the air cooling the servers below the allowable limits, the air humidity in the dehumidifier is controlled by manipulating the percentage of return air. In this model, the desiccant outlet concentration is also controlled by the desiccant flow rate.

In the regenerator system the inputs of the model are weather condition, desiccant inlet temperature and concentration, and hot water temperature and flow. The outlets are air (exhaust air) temperature, desiccant temperature, and hot water temperature. To use the desiccant for dehumidification purposes, it is required to regenerate it to a certain concentration. In this model the manipulating parameter to control the desiccant concentration is the desiccant flow rate.

5.4.6 Liquid desiccant system model verification

The validity of the model can be assessed by comparing its predicted supply conditions to the measured supply conditions. These comparisons are done for each stage independently: the first-stage dehumidifier and the second-stage Indirect Evaporative Cooler (IEC). Experimental data [112] from DEVap prototype testing is used to verify the dehumidifier and indirect evaporative cooler in the next two section, respectively.

5.4.6.1 Dehumidifier verification

5 different cases from [112] have been used to verify the dehumidifier model. Table 18 shows the input conditions used in all the cases as well as experimental outcome and model output for supply air temperature and relative humidity. Figure 89 compares the model predictions (x-axis) and the experiments (y-axis) of the relative temperature of the first-stage supply-side air. The $\pm 10\%$ lines in Figure 89 show that the model and the experiments match within 10%.

Table 18. Dehumidifier unit verification input and output parameter.

	Input Data										Experiment Output		Model Output	
	P_{atm} (kPa)	\dot{m}_{sa} (kg/s)	\dot{m}_{ea} (kg/s)	\dot{V}_{LD} (LPM)	C_{LD}	T_{LD} (°C)	T_{sa} (°C)	T_{ea} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)	RH_{ea} (g/kg)	T_{sa} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)	T_{sa} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)
1	82.8	0.154	0.615	0.337	0.373	27.4	26.7	35	53.26	41.31	27.2	35.45	27.85	34.15
2	82.7	0.154	0.0308	0.337	0.376	28.3	26.7	35	53.30	42.31	28.2	35.07	28.61	34.3
3	81.7	0.154	0.0616	0.299	0.424	35.2	35	35	42.16	42.31	32.6	26.74	35.5	27.4
4	82.9	0.154	0.0615	0.360	0.379	28.7	26.7	26.7	52.08	67.96	26.3	34.32	28.14	34.77
5	100	0.152	0.061	0.337	0.38	32.9	26.7	28	50.1	45.02	29.1	29.1	28.4	29.58

Figure 89. Model-experiment comparison of dehumidifier. (top) Change in supply-side air, temperature (bottom) change in relative humidity.

5.4.6.2 Indirect evaporative cooler verification

For indirect evaporative cooler, 5 different cases from [112] have been used to verify the model. Table 19 shows the input conditions as well as experimental outcome and model output for supply air temperature and relative humidity. Figure 90 compares the model predictions (x-axis) and the experiments (y-axis) of the relative temperature of the supply-side air. For the Indirect evaporative cooler, the measured supply-side temperature change predicted by the model matches the experiments within 10% except for test number 3. In case 3 the temperature difference is higher and has low mass flow which shows the weakness of bulk model to predict the result and the need for a discretized model.

Table 19. Indirect evaporative cooler verification input and output parameter.

	Input Data					Experiment Output			Model Output		
	P_{atm} (kPa)	\dot{m}_{sa} (kg/s)	\dot{m}_{ea} (kg/s)	T_{sa} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)	T_{sa} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)	T_{ea} (°C)	T_{sa} (°C)	RH_{sa} (g/kg)	T_{ea} (°C)
1	81	0.154	0.031	35	21.8	18	59.4	-	19.01	58.55	24.9
2	83.2	0.150	0.014	25	44.24	21.01	56.33	-	20.11	58.96	21.84
3	81	0.062	0.018	35	21.79	14.1	76.21	-	12.61	84.03	27.37
4	81.1	0.154	0.046	35	35.78	19.3	89.97	-	22.6	74.07	24.93
5	81	0.108	0.032	35	21.56	14.2	74.99	-	14.8	74.04	24.75

Figure 90. Model-experiment comparison of indirect evaporative cooler. (top) Change in supply-side air, temperature (bottom) change in relative humidity.

5.4.7 Summary

In this chapter, a physical model has been developed to simulate the DEVap components including liquid desiccant dehumidifier, regenerator, and indirect evaporative cooler. In addition, the control strategy for each component has been explained. The developed models have been also verified and compared to the experimental data from literatures. This model is designed to be integrated with the SOFC for examining CCHP applications in data centers.

6. Modeling Results

6.1 Liquid Desiccant Dehumidification

In this section, the possibility of using a highly efficient, zero emission solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) system to produce electricity and cooling in various amounts to meet electricity and cooling demands of a data center is investigated. In this configuration each fuel cell powers one server rack and heat from each individual SOFC system is used in a small-scale Liquid Desiccant Dehumidification (LDD) to produce cooling for one server. Figure 90 shows the integrated system configuration for rack level power and cooling. we developed a spatially and temporally resolved physical SOFC system model and a corresponding physical model for liquid desiccant dehumidification in order to simulate the integrated system behavior as installed to meet server power and cooling demands in a data center setting.

For this section, each server rack power is considered nominally 12 kW. We assume that a fuel cell that is equivalent to 8 1.5 kW BlueGEN SOFC systems is used to meet the server electrical demand. The exhaust of the SOFC is used to regenerate LiCl liquid desiccant to provide 2000 cubic feet per minute (CFM) cold and dehumidified air for each server rack.

Figure 91. System configuration for server rack level power and cooling

The polarization curve data from the 1.5 kW BlueGEN SOFC system tested at the NFCRC and the developed model results are presented in Figure 91. Note that the V-j curve obtained from the test covers only the operating envelope of the SOFC system. The results show that the Matlab model simulates the BlueGEN system V-j curve accurately.

Figure 92. SOFC polarization curve for the BlueGEN data compared to the current physical SOFC system model.

Table 20. SOFC Parameters and Design Operating Conditions.

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Value</i>
<i>Fuel Utilization</i>	0.85
<i>Steam to Carbon Ratio</i>	2.02
<i>Cell Area</i>	139.24 cm ²
<i>Power Density</i>	233 mW/ cm ²
<i>Stack Temperature Change</i>	50 oC
<i>SOFC Stack Average Temperature</i>	1023 K

The steady state performance of the system was calculated under the standard operating conditions of the BlueGEN at 85% fuel utilization and cathode outlet temperature of 750°C. The SOFC system is controlled to keep the stack temperature difference at 50 °C. The SOFC parameter and standard operating conditions are presented in Table 20. The electrical efficiency of the stack is over 61% under standard operating conditions. The SOFC system designed for the current server rack application (based upon 8 BlueGEN equivalents) is capable of producing 11.76 kW that directly powers one server rack. The steady state performance parameters of the model for one 1.5 kW SOFC system and experiment values are compared in Table 21. Note that scaled experimental values well match those of the model. Note also that the exhaust gas temperature and flow rate were not measured during the experiment.

The particular SOFC system that was evaluated in this study was designed for co-generation of heat and power (CHP), and thus produces more heat than would be used for preheating the SOFC inlet air and fuel. The heat produced from the SOFC system in the current case is then used for producing hot water for LiCl regeneration purposes. This model indicates that a nominal 1.5 kW system would produce 0.0104 kg/s of exhaust gas and that the temperature of the exhaust would be 100 °C.

Table 21. SOFC Steady State Performance Parameters.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Model Value</i>	<i>Experiment Value</i>
<i>Net Power Output</i>	1.49 kW	1.5 kW
<i>Voltage</i>	42.5 V	42.5 V
<i>Current</i>	38.94 A/cm ²	38.94 A/cm ²
<i>Electrical Efficiency</i>	61.1%	61.27%
<i>Exhaust Gas Temperature</i>	373 K	-
<i>Exhaust Gas Mass Flow Rate</i>	0.0104 kg/s	-

Figure 92 shows the integrated SOFC-LDD system. The SOFC exhaust gas produces hot water that will supply the heat demand for regenerating the liquid desiccant. The regeneration process occurs within a heat and mass exchanger where the vapor desorbs from the desiccant and is carried away by an air stream due to desiccant solution that has higher water vapor pressure than the air. The high concentration LiCl is stored in a tank. When air conditioning is required, the high concentration LiCl is used to dehumidify the air. The American Society of Heating Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) recommended suitable range of temperature and humidity for all environmental classes inside the data centers is 18 °C to 28 °C dry bulb temperature -9 °C to 15 °C dew point and 60% RH [1].

Figure 93. Integrated SOFC- LDD system model schematic.

For this study, the integrated system is tested for spontaneous load for three different weather conditions to analyze whether SOFC system exhaust-heat based cooling and dehumidification is capable of maintaining server operating temperatures and humidity in the safe range for different weather conditions. Tables, 22, 23 and 24 show the inlet and outlet condition for each of the three scenarios. The weather conditions studied are warm and humid air (25 °C, 70% RH), hot and moderate humidity air (35 °C, 45% RH) and hot and dry air (40 °C, 20% RH).

Table 22. Inlet and outlet conditions of the regenerator stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	\dot{m}_{air} (kg/s)	$T_{w,in}$ (°C)	$T_{w,out}$ (°C)	\dot{m}_w (kg/s)	$T_{LiCl,out}$ (°C)	$X_{LiCl,out}$
35	40%	0.02	60	35	0.055	48.5	34.5%
35	45%	0.035	60	55	0.055	46	35%

Table 23. Inlet and outlet conditions of the dehumidifier stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	$T_{LiCl,in}$ (°C)	$X_{LiCl,in}$	$X_{LiCl,out}$	\dot{m}_{LiCl} (kg/s)	\dot{m}_{air} (kg/s)	$T_{air,out}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,out}$
25	70%	35.2	34.5%	33%	0.25	0.045	30.5	33.9%
35	45%	35.2	35%	33%	0.25	0.06	34.9	31.2%
40	20%	-	-	-	-	-	40	20%

Table 24. Inlet and outlet conditions of the IEC stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	$T_{w,in}$ (°C)	$T_{Cair,in}$ (°C)	\dot{m}_{Cair} (kg/s)	$T_{Sair,out}$ (°C)	$w_{Sair,out}$ (kg/kg)	$DP_{Sair,out}$ (°C)
30.5	33.9%	20	19.8	0.038	19.8	0.0093	12.5
34.9	31.2%	20	21	0.051	21	0.0109	15
40	20%	20	20		20	0.009	12.4

Figure 93 shows the model results of the first test on a psychrometric chart. The green line labeled 'LiCl – 35%' shows the humidity ratio of the air in equilibrium with the liquid desiccant at a mass fraction of 0.35 LiCl and at each of the temperatures considered. Line black shows the first stage dehumidification process for supply air and then the cooling air process. The dehumidification process is internally cooled by evaporation of water to exhaust air to keep the desiccant cooler and increase its dehumidification potential. Then, the supply air is cooled by indirect evaporative cooling at constant humidity ratio. Horizontal black line shows the second stage process for supply air, which goes through indirect evaporative cooling at constant humidity ratio. Under these conditions the integrated system was able to produce cold and dehumidified air that is in the safe range for server racks. In this case the return air from server is considered for first stage cooling air which has lower relative humidity and higher potential for evaporative cooling.

Figure 94. Airstream at 25 °C and 70% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

However, the system is able to provide only 97 CFM of air flow under these conditions, which is less than the maximum air flow demand (almost 7%) for each server rack. This suggests that the current integrated SOFC-LDD system cannot continuously provide all of the power and cooling required for the server rack if it is operated continuously at 12 kW. However, both the server demand dynamics and day-night weather variations, could lead to dynamic conditions that with some storage of the concentrated solution (at times when cooling and dehumidification are not needed) could be well-matched to the server demands for power and for cooling and dehumidification.

Figure 95. Airstream at 35 °C and 45% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

For the second weather condition (35 °C, 45% RH) the system is able to produce 96 CFM cold and dry air for each server rack. In this case the outside air is considered for the first stage cooling air. Please note that the SOFC system is running based upon design operating conditions for the system. Further investigation is needed to evaluate the SOFC system available heat under different operating conditions that could produce higher quality exhaust heat (e.g., operation at lower fuel utilization) likely at the expense of electrical efficiency. Figure 68 presents the results of hot and dry air (40 °C, 20% RH) conditions on a psychrometric chart. In this scenario dehumidification is not needed for the supply air entering the server rack. The incoming air only goes through the second stage and gets cooled through indirect evaporation. The mass flow rate of air in this condition is independent of SOFC heat.

Figure 96. Airstream at 40 °C and 20% RH process on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

The Initial results show that the SOFC system was capable of producing enough power for a single server rack. The SOFC system exhaust heat is predicted to leave the 12 kW SOFC system at 100 °C temperature and 0.832 kg/s flow rate. The exhaust of the SOFC system can produce hot water at 0.044 kg/s at 60 °C. The results show that the SOFC exhaust heat is not able to continuously provide all the server required supply air in the safe range of temperature and dehumidification under these conditions. To provide enough cooling and dehumidification required for server rack further modifications to the system (e.g., change fuel utilization) should be made to supply additional heat for liquid desiccant regeneration or look into yearly storage of liquid desiccant. [2]

6.2 Steady State SOFC Model Results

Before assessing the performance of the integrated system, several outputs from the SOFC model are considered to ensure that it is operating in a feasible manner. The first parameters are the inlet flows of both fuel and air into the SOFC.

Figure 97. Mass flow rate of fuel (a) and air into the SOFC system (b).

The fuel flow rates shown in Figure 96a reflect that as the fuel utilization decreases, more fuel is required to make the 200 kW of electricity. Also, while it is less impactful the lower the stack temperature the lower the cell voltage, which requires more fuel to maintain power output. Similarly, the air flow rates shown in Figure 96b reflect how the air is used to control the stack temperature. The lower the stack temperature the more air that is needed to cool it. Additionally, decreased fuel utilization requires more airflow since more fuel is introduced into the system, generating more heat in either the stack or the downstream oxidizer.

The next outputs of the integrated model considered are the cell voltage and the post-anode oxidizer temperature. These values are checked to ensure their validity within the operational domain.

Figure 98. Cell voltage within SOFC stack (a) and Post-anode oxidizer outlet temperature (b).

The cell voltages shown in Figure 97a reflect the impact of the Nernst potential change due to temperature where higher stack temperatures have higher voltages. Additionally, a small amount of ohmic losses is also shown as the fuel utilization increases. Note that the shape of the voltage curves is caused by the spiraling search strategy adopted for the iterative model. Note that no mass transfer losses are incurred since the current density of the stack never climbs above 0.5 A/cm^2 .

The oxidizer temperatures are considered to ensure that combustion can occur at the temperatures seen while not producing excessive temperatures that could damage the materials internal to the SOFC's balance of plant.

Figure 99. SOFC system efficiency over operational domain.

The SOFC system efficiency is a critical output from the integrated model because it represents the performance of the system to produce electricity. The system efficiency is explored across the

operational domain in Figure 98 and as expected the fuel utilization has the largest impact on the system efficiency. There is a slight dependence on stack temperature which can be explained by the increased cell voltage at higher temperatures resulting in better efficiencies. The range of efficiencies from 0.5 to 0.6 indicate that the system is operating as expected and can compete with much larger advanced combined natural gas plants on a much smaller scale.

One final output from the SOFC system model is the carbon emissions produced by making electricity from natural gas. The output of CO₂ from the system is shown in Figure 99 below.

Figure 100. Carbon dioxide emissions from SOFC system.

As expected, the carbon emissions are very closely tied to the fuel utilization because at lower fuel utilization more fuel is burned in the post-anode oxidizer. It should be noted that at CO₂ productions above 0.44 kg/kWh, the SOFC is producing more CO₂ than an advanced natural gas combined plant.

6.2.1 Integrated Model Results

Now that the operation of the SOFC has been explored and assured to be within feasible norms, the model can characterize the exhaust of the SOFC and its utility to an absorption chiller. The temperature and mass flow of the SOFC system's exhaust is shown below in Figure 100.

Figure 101. SOFC system exhaust temperature (a) and mass flow rate (b).

The SOFC system exhaust temperature is predominantly influenced by the stack temperature. The higher the stack temperature, the higher the temperature in the exhaust, which is caused in part because at higher stack temperatures there is less airflow through the system. Additionally, increasing the fuel utilization also increases the exhaust temperature due to a drop in fuel cell efficiency. This indicates that the heat generated within the stack is more dominant than the heat generated in the post-anode oxidizer.

In contrast, the exhaust mass flow, shown in Figure 100b, is mostly influenced by the fuel utilization since the lower the utilization results in a higher concentration of fuel in the exhaust gas stream. This fuel is oxidized, and the higher fuel concentration leads to an increase in exhaust gas temperature. Similarly, the cooler the stack temperature, the more air flow that is required, thus boosting the exhaust mass flow rate.

Combining the temperature, exhaust, composition, and specific heat of the exhaust from the SOFC system, it is possible to calculate the useful heat available in the exhaust. To do so, a reference temperature to which the exhaust rejects heat is necessary. This temperature corresponds to the desorber temperature of the triple-effect absorption chiller since this is what will be capturing heat from the exhaust. The range of desorber temperatures within the triple-effect model ranged from 150 to 170 °C. Using this method, the useful exhaust heat is calculated and shown in Figure 101 below.

Figure 102. SOFC system exhaust heat capacity.

Looking at Figure 101, it is apparent that the SOFC system's useful exhaust heat capacity is mostly correlated to the fuel utilization. Lower fuel utilizations allow for more heat in the exhaust, which makes physical sense since more fuel is flowing into the system and is ultimately converted to heat in either the stack or the oxidizer.

Utilizing the useful heat and exhaust characterization within the triple-effect absorption chiller, it is possible to calculate the available chilling from the integrated system. The results from the absorption chiller model are shown below in Figure 102.

Figure 103. Triple-effect absorption chiller chilling capacity from SOFC exhaust heat.

The chilling capacity is very closely tied to the heat capacity within the SOFC system exhaust, and with COPs ranging from 1.60 to 1.82, the maximum chilling capacity is 272 kW of chilling. Based on these results it is possible to produce the needed 200 kW of chilling to fully offset the server's thermal requirement while operating the SOFC at a fuel utilization around 0.82.

It is promising to show that an integration between an SOFC system and an absorption chiller could produce the necessary power and chilling for a row of servers within a data center. This unique synergy makes the most of the SOFC system's power and thermal generation and allows a reduction in primary energy usage. To compare the cogeneration of this integrated system with the more classical approach of grid provided electricity with industrial chilling units, we utilize the primary energy savings ratio metric (PES) which is calculated by Equation 8.

$$PES = 1 - \frac{E_f}{\frac{E_{el}}{\eta_{el,ref}} + \frac{Q_{th}}{\eta_{th,ref}}} \quad [8]$$

For this calculation, the reference electrical production efficiency was 52.5%, the reference grid efficiency was 89.2% based on transmission system losses, and the reference COP for chilling was 5 [18]. The PES was then computed within the operational domain to determine to show the effects of adjusting the fuel utilization and stack temperature on primary energy savings. The results are shown below in Figure 103.

Figure 104. Primary energy savings ratio of integrated SOFC and absorption system.

Looking at Figure 103, the ability to save between 18 and 30% of the primary energy input is a very positive result for the integrated system. It is also apparent that the operating efficiency of the SOFC system is much more important in the PES than the chilling capacity. To better actively control the integrated operation, utilizing higher fuel utilization and stack temperature would yield

the best results. However, it is prudent to consider the operational constraints placed within this domain by limits in chilling, carbon emissions, and temperature rises in the cathode and anode. These constraints can be overlaid onto the PES chart to show an operational envelope, shown below in Figure 104, in which an optimal condition can be obtained.

Figure 105. Operational envelope superimposed on primary energy savings ratio.

The overlays on Figure 104 are as follows: red represents conditions where the temperature rise across the anode is greater than 80 °C, orange represents conditions where the temperature rise across the cathode is greater than 80 °C, green represents conditions where carbon dioxide emissions are above 0.44 kg/kWh, blue represents conditions where less than 200 kW of chilling is available. Considering these constraints and maximizing primary energy savings, the best operating condition was found to have parameters of 0.819 for fuel utilization and a stack temperature of 861°C, which results in a PES of 25.8%.

When considering this maximized PES solution, it is also prudent to consider the transient nature of the servers cooling requirement. For example, should the ambient air temperature allow some induction of outside air to assist in cooling, the demand for cooling capacity can be decreased. In these instances, the imposed constraint of 200 kW of chilling can be lowered or removed. This allows for an alternative maximized PES solution which is shown as the white cross in Figure 77. In this condition, the SOFC can operate more efficiently at a fuel utilization of 0.827 and a stack temperature of 859°C while the chiller operates at partial capacity. Referencing Figure 75, we can see that even at the secondary maximized point, the chilling capacity is 184kW. Using this active control with feedback from ambient conditions, the primary energy savings can be maximized, and carbon emissions can be minimized.

6.2.2 Economic Model Results

The final investigation that the integrated model is used to understand is the effect that the adjustments to the operational parameters, fuel utilization and stack temperature, have on the economics of a theoretical installation. Using the cost inputs described in Table 12, it is possible to calculate the levelized cost of electricity and the levelized cost of chilling. Exploring these values in the same operational domain, the levelized costs of electricity and chilling are shown below in Figure 82.

Figure 106. Levelized costs of electricity (a) and chilling for the integrated system (b).

Reviewing Figure 105a, the cost of electricity is very competitive due to the optimistic capital investment costs. Ranging from 35 to 42 \$/MWh, the levelized costs track very closely with the overall efficiency of the SOFC system. In Figure 105b, however, the cost of chilling is very high ranging from 54 to 57 \$/MWh when compared to a cost of chilling from a conventional cooling system using utility electricity of < \$30/MWh. This is due to the very large capital investment for a triple-effect absorption chiller combined with the cost of the cooling tower. Additionally, the cost of chilling scales with the chilling capacity because it is assumed that the chiller will be sized to match the thermal output of the fuel cell.

When considering the combined integrated system, it is possible to assess the levelized cost of utility, where utility is the sum of the electric power and chilling power. To account for the thermodynamic value of thermal energy (chilling) compared to work (electricity) the chilling energy is valued at 20% of electricity production in this utility metric due to a standard chiller's COP of 5. The levelized cost of utility is shown below in Figure 106.

Figure 107. Levelized cost of utility (electricity & chilling) from the integrated SOFC and absorption chiller.

The overall costs of utility from 70 to 88 \$/MWh are still high compared to traditional electricity and chilling plants, which can cost less than 70 \$/MWh when data center loads are consistent. However, considering the greenhouse gas and criteria pollutant emissions benefits and the future potential of such a system to cost much less and incorporate renewable hydrogen use, an integrated SOFC system and absorption chiller could present a promising architecture for the powering and cooling of data centers in locations with high cooling demands.

6.3 SOFC stack results

Figure 108 to Figure 112 show the spatial distribution of temperature, Nernst voltage, losses, voltage, and current density in a unit SOFC. The temperature changes between 1000K-1040K. The temperature has its lowest amount at the corner close to the cathode and anode streams inlet where the air which is cooling stream has its lowest temperature (highest cooling potential) and the reformation which is endothermic is still occurring at the beginning of the cell. Temperature has the highest amount at the corner close to the cathode and anode streams outlet where air has its highest temperature (lowest cooling potential) and electrochemical reaction which is dominant at the end of cell generates heat due to its exothermicity.

Figure 108. State spatial distribution of temperature.

The Nernst voltages are among 0.9V-0.98V. The Nernst voltage is highest at the corner close to the cathode and anode inlet streams where both fuel and oxidant partial pressures are high leading to high thermodynamic potential with the lowest Nernst potentials realized at the corner close to the cathode and anode streams outlet.

Figure 109. Steady-state spatial distribution of Nernst voltage.

The lowest amount of losses is 0.065V captured where the temperature is highest. High temperature increases the thermal energy available in the system, generally resulting in the fact that all the particles in the system now move and vibrate with increased intensity. This higher level of thermal activity will possess sufficient energy to overcome activation polarization and most importantly increases electrolyte ionic conductivity, which decreases the ohmic loss.

Figure 110 shows the spatial distribution of cell operating voltage which is uniform along the cell as expected due to the equipotential surface that is established by the good electronic conductivity of the electrodes and bipolar plates. The current density along the direction of fuel flow decreases as the fuel gets consumed and has less potential to produce current.

Figure 110. Steady-state spatial distribution of losses.

Figure 111. Steady-state spatial distribution of voltage.

Figure 112. Steady-state spatial distribution of current density.

6.3.1 Steady state results

The system model is based on a commercially available SOFC systems called BlueGEN. BlueGEN CHP unit, originally manufactured by Ceramic Fuel Cells Ltd (CFCL). BlueGEN is a commercially available SOFC CHP system, now built and sold by SOLIDpower, designed for small- to medium-scale building applications. Operating on natural gas, the unit can produce power modulated from 500We (25%) to 2kWe (100%); however, it achieves its highest net electrical efficiency of 60% at a 1.5kWe output. The BlueGEN SOFC unit consists of 51 planar type Yttria Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) electrolyte-supported cell layer sets (each layer consists of 4 cells) and operates at around 750°C. Hydrogen is produced from natural gas by external and internal steam reforming.

The polarization curve data from the BlueGEN SOFC system tested at the NFCRC and the developed model results are presented in Figure 113. Note that the V-j curve obtained from the test covers only the operating envelope of the SOFC system. The results show that the MATLAB model simulates the BlueGEN system V-j curve accurately.

Figure 113. SOFC polarization curve for the BlueGEN data compared to the current physical SOFC system model.

The steady state performance of the system was calculated under the standard operating conditions of the BlueGEN at 85% fuel utilization and cathode outlet temperature of 750°C. The SOFC system is controlled to keep the stack temperature difference at 50°C. The SOFC parameter and standard operating conditions are presented in Table 25. The electrical efficiency

of the stack is over 61% under standard operating conditions. The steady state performance parameters of the model for 1.5kW SOFC model Table 26. Note that experimental values well match those of the model. Note also that the exhaust gas temperature and flow rate were not measured during the experiment.

Table 25. SOFC Parameters and Design Operating Conditions.

Parameters	Value
Fuel Utilization	0.85
Steam to Carbon Ratio	2.02
Cell Area	139.24cm ²
Power Density	233mW/cm ²
Stack Temperature Change	50°C
SOFC Stack Average Temperature	1023K

The particular SOFC system that was evaluated in this study was designed for CHP, and thus produces more heat than would be used for preheating the SOFC inlet air and fuel. The heat produced from the SOFC system in the current case is then used for producing hot water for LiCl regeneration purposes. This model indicates that a nominal 1.5kW system would produce 0.0104kg/s of exhaust gas and that the temperature of the exhaust would be 100°C.

Table 26. SOFC steady state performance parameters.

Parameters	Model Value	Experiment Value
Net Power Output	1.49kW	1.5kW
Voltage	42.5V	42.5V
Current	38.94A/cm ²	38.94A/cm ²
Electrical Efficiency	61.1%	61.27%
Exhaust Gas Temperature	373K	-
Exhaust Gas Mass Flow Rate	0.0104kg/s	-

6.3.2 SOFC system dynamic modeling results

Electricity demand for a single residential unit is used as a desired demand applied to the spatially resolved dynamic SOFC model. SOFC model results (Figure 114) that generated output power follows the desired demand quite closely except for very short periods of high ramp rate operating conditions. Figure 115 shows the electrical efficiency of the system during the dynamic operation. The average efficiency during dynamic operation is 71%. The high efficiency is due to high fuel utilization (85%) and part load operation of the system which also lead to a lower exhaust temperature.

Figure 114. SOFC model power output following the residential electricity demand

Figure 115. Variation of electrical efficiency versus time.

Temperature and mass flow rate of SOFC exhaust gas versus time are presented in Figure 116 and Figure 117, respectively. As shown in Figure 76, the oxidizer output is used for preheating fuel and air and then leaves the system as exhaust. This SOFC system exhaust is used to produce hot water for regenerating LiCl in liquid desiccant regenerator.

Figure 116. Exhaust gas temperature of the SOFC system.

Figure 117. Exhaust gas mass flow rate of the SOFC system.

Figure 118 and Figure 119 show the PEN average temperature and stack temperature difference during the dynamic operation, respectively. The set point for PEN average temperature is 1023K and for stack temperature difference is 50K, due to very high dynamic load the controller is not able to keep the cell at the desired temperature. PEN average temperature goes as high as 1078K and stack temperature difference changes up to 94K.

Figure 118. PEN average temperature.

Figure 119. Stack temperature difference.

6.3.3 Summary

This chapter has focused on developing a spatially and temporally resolved dynamic physical SOFC model. It also focused on designing the SOFC system components and balance of plant based upon the commercially used SOFC in this research experiment. Additionally, it has focused on the control strategies for the SOFC system. This chapter has included the steady state stack spatially distribution results, and verification of developed model with experimental tests. Finally, SOFC results under dynamic operation of a residential load have been presented.

Dynamic results show that the SOFC stack is capable of rapid load following. This behavior is not present in our current experimental system. Differences between the experimental and modeled stack is the balance of plant. Fuel conditioning balance of plant components typically have a thermal and mass flow delay that slows down the response of the entire SOFC system. If a consistent fuel supply is available and the appropriate stack level controls are implemented, we would expect that an experimental system could replicate these modeled results.

6.4 Integrated system design

In this section, the possibility of using a highly efficient, zero emission SOFC system to produce electricity and cooling in various amounts to meet electricity and cooling demands of a

data center is investigated. In this configuration each fuel cell powers one server rack and heat from each individual SOFC system is used in a small-scale LDD to produce cooling for one server. Figure 120 shows the integrated system configuration for rack level power and cooling.

Figure 120. System configuration for server rack level power and cooling.

Server rack average power density can start as low as 6kW and go to above 20kW per rack. For this analysis, each server rack power is considered nominally 12kW. We assume that a fuel cell equivalent to eight 1.5kW BlueGEN SOFC systems is used to meet the server electrical demand (note that some above nominal power conditions can usually be provided by SOFC systems, e.g., to periodically achieve peak demands in the 20kW range). The exhaust of the SOFC is used to regenerate LiCl liquid desiccant to provide 1400CFM cold and dehumidified air for each server rack.

6.4.1 Spontaneous integrated system performance

Figure 121 shows the integrated SOFC-LDD system. The SOFC exhaust gas produces hot water that will supply the heat demand for regenerating the liquid desiccant. The regeneration process occurs within a heat and mass exchanger where the vapor desorbs from the desiccant and is carried away by an air stream due to desiccant solution that has higher water vapor pressure than the air. The high concentration LiCl is stored in a tank. When air conditioning is required, the high concentration LiCl is used to dehumidify the air. As mentioned before the ASHRAE recommended suitable range of temperature and humidity for all environmental classes inside the data centers is 18°C to 28°C dry bulb temperature and 9°C to 15°C dew point and 60% RH [17].

Figure 121. Integrated SOFC-LDD system model schematic.

For this section, the integrated system is tested for spontaneous load for three different weather conditions to analyze whether SOFC system exhaust-heat based cooling and dehumidification can maintain server operating temperatures and humidity in the safe range for different weather conditions. Table 27,

Table 28 and Table 29 show the inlet and outlet condition for each of the three scenarios. The weather conditions studied are warm and humid air (25°C, 70% RH), hot and moderate humidity air (35°C, 45% RH) and hot and dry air (40°C, 20% RH). All three scenarios utilize the same system with the only difference being the ambient air conditions.

Table 27. Inlet and outlet conditions of the regenerator stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	\dot{m}_{air} (kg/s)	$T_{w,in}$ (°C)	$T_{w,out}$ (°C)	\dot{m}_w (kg/s)	$T_{LiCl,out}$ (°C)	$X_{LiCl,out}$
35	40%	0.02	60	35	0.055	48.5	34.5%
35	45%	0.035	60	55	0.055	46	35%

Table 28. Inlet and outlet conditions of the dehumidifier stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	$T_{LiCl,in}$ (°C)	$X_{LiCl,in}$	$X_{LiCl,out}$	\dot{m}_{LiCl} (kg/s)	\dot{m}_{air} (kg/s)	$T_{air,out}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,out}$
25	70%	35.2	34.5%	33%	0.25	0.045	30.5	33.9%
35	45%	35.2	35%	33%	0.25	0.06	34.9	31.2%
40	20%	-	-	-	-	-	40	20%

Table 29. Inlet and outlet conditions of the IEC stage.

$T_{air,in}$ (°C)	$RH_{air,in}$	$T_{w,in}$ (°C)	$T_{Cair,in}$ (°C)	\dot{m}_{Cair} (kg/s)	$T_{Sair,out}$ (°C)	$w_{Sair,out}$ (kg/kg)	$DP_{Sair,out}$ (°C)
30.5	33.9%	20	19.8	0.038	19.8	0.0093	12.5
34.9	31.2%	20	21	0.051	21	0.0109	15
40	20%	20	20		20	0.009	12.4

Figure 122 shows the model results of the first test on a psychrometric chart. The green line labeled 'LiCl – 35%' shows the humidity ratio of the air in equilibrium with the liquid desiccant at a mass fraction of 0.35 LiCl and at each of the temperatures considered. Line black shows the first stage dehumidification process for supply air and then the cooling air process. The dehumidification process is internally cooled by evaporation of water to exhaust air to keep the desiccant cooler and increase its dehumidification potential. Then, the supply air is cooled by indirect evaporative cooling at constant humidity ratio. Horizontal black line shows the second stage process for supply air, which goes through indirect evaporative cooling at constant humidity ratio. Under these conditions the integrated system was able to produce cold and dehumidified air that is in the safe range for server racks. In this case the return air from server is considered for first stage cooling air which has lower relative humidity and higher potential for evaporative cooling.

Figure 122. Airstream at 25°C and 70% RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

However, the system is able to provide only 97CFM of air flow under these conditions, which is less than the maximum air flow demand (almost 7%) for each server rack. This suggests that the current integrated SOFC-LDD system cannot continuously provide all the power and cooling required for the server rack if it is operated continuously at 12kW. However, both the server demand dynamics and day-night weather variations, could lead to dynamic conditions that with some storage of the concentrated solution (at times when cooling and dehumidification are not needed) could be well-matched to the server demands for power and for cooling and dehumidification. Next step will consider these dynamics for several real-world weather (temperature and relative humidity) and server power.

For the second weather condition with 35°C and 45%RH (Figure 123) the system can produce 96CFM cold and dry air for each server rack. In this case the outside air is considered for the first stage cooling air. Please note that the SOFC system is running based upon design operating conditions for the system. Further investigation is needed to evaluate the SOFC system available heat under different operating conditions that could produce higher quality exhaust heat (e.g., operation at lower fuel utilization) likely at the expense of electrical efficiency.

Figure 123. Airstream at 35°C and 45%RH with simulated LDD processes on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

Figure 124 presents the results of hot and dry air (40°C, 20% RH) conditions on a psychrometric chart. In this scenario dehumidification is not needed for the supply air entering the server rack. The incoming air only goes through the second stage and gets cooled through indirect evaporation. The mass flow rate of air in this condition is independent of SOFC heat.

Bottom line for these scenarios is that the LDD system can produce cooling for the different inlet air conditions. The extent to which the LDD system can provide cooling for a data center, however, is not immediately clear since CFM conditioned air is based on SOFC input. Adding LDD storage will decouple this relationship, allowing for LDD cooling operation regardless of SOFC operation.

Figure 124. Airstream at 40°C and 20% RH process on a psychrometric chart at 100kPa.

6.4.2 LiCl daily storage

Microsoft has 7 different locations in the States for data centers which is shown at Figure 125. The locations are in Washington, California, Texas, Wyoming, Iowa, Illinois, and Virginia. For this study, 24-hour weather data on July 20, 2018 is considered. Figure 126 shows the temperature variation during 24 hours on July 20th.

Figure 125. Microsoft data center location in the US.

Figure 126. Temperature of 7 different location for 24 hours on July 20, 2018.

Figure 127. Dew point temperature of 7 different locations for 24 hours on July 20, 2018.

Figure 127 shows the dew point for each hour during one day for 7 different locations. In this part, only latent load is considered. As it is shown in Figure 127, Washington, California, and Wyoming dew point are below the higher limit for data centers (15°C) during the 24 hours which means that these three locations do not have any latent heat during this day. For the other 4 locations, Virginia, Illinois, Iowa, and Texas, the dew point is almost always above the limit. Table 30 shows the average temperature, relative humidity, and Dew point for all locations. Illinois and Texas have the highest latent load for 24 hours.

Figure 128 shows the schematic of the system for the case that the dehumidification is independent from regeneration. The regenerator will produce strong desiccant spontaneously as the fuel cell is working all day 24 hours, then this strong LiCl will be stored and when the dehumidification is needed will be used.

Figure 128. SOFC-LDD schematic for considering storage capacity.

Table 30. 24-hour average weather data on July 20, 2018.

Location	Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity	Dew Point (°C)
Virginia	25.21	65.08	17.09
Illinois	22.61	89.43	20.69
Iowa	23.95	68.7	17.47
Texas	30.93	59.88	19.95
Washington	20.12	37.46	5.18
California	23.36	43.66	10.32
Wyoming	25.23	37.44	9.7

Table 31 shows the result for the four locations that need dehumidification on July 24th, the results show that fuel cell will be able to produce almost 10% of the daily storage for these cases. This is because during this day all these 4 locations need dehumidification all day long, so there won't be time during the day/night that regeneration can store extra amount of storing desiccant for later use. For storage capacity we need to look into the yearly capacity which during some months there won't be any latent load and the regenerator can produce and store LiCl for months that dehumidification is needed.

Table 31. Daily storage capacity for 7 data center locations during July 20th.

Location	Temperature (°C)	Humidity ratio (g/kg)	Relative humidity	Pressure (kPa)	Outlet Temperature (°C)	Outlet Humidity ratio	Required LiCl capacity	Fuel Cell LiCl Capacity
Virginia	25.21	12.41	79.8	100	7.84	11	2.31	0.173
Illinois	22.61	15.94	88.97	98	25.93	11	2.35	0.173
Iowa	23.95	13.12	67.07	97	28.43	11	2.3	0.202
Texas	30.93	15.06	52.04	99	30.99	11	2.31	0.194

6.4.3 LiCl yearly storage

Figure 129 shows dew point for the seven locations of the study for the entire year. As we can see Virginia, Iowa, Illinois, and Texas are the four locations that have significant number of hours with dew point higher than 15°C, which is the limit for acceptable humidity level of the servers. In this section, we investigate the amount of liquid desiccant that is required to dehumidify the air in these locations, as well as the storage capacity for each of these four locations.

Figure 129. Dew point for the seven locations of the study for the entire year.

For this section's results, the assumptions are as follow:

1. Each single server rack is 12kW.
2. The space is designed so that each row of servers contains 10 server racks. (Figure 130 shows the schematic of row level server cooling.)
3. The temperature difference of the air entering and leaving the servers is 15 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
4. The humidity ratio of the air cooling the server is kept below $11\frac{\text{g}}{\text{kg}}$ (ASHRAE recommendation);
4. Each fuel cell powering the servers is equivalent to 8 BlueGEN (12kW).

Figure 130. Schematic of row level server cooling.

The results are presented for two scenarios; in first scenario, liquid desiccant provides dehumidified air for one single server rack for the entire year, the fuel cell runs at full load, and the dehumidifier is sized based on server rack, and the regenerator is sized based on FC exhaust. In second scenario, liquid desiccant provides dehumidified air for two rows (20 server racks), Fuel cell runs at 70% load, dehumidifier is sized based on cooling required for two rows, and regenerator is sized based on equivalent of two rows fuel cell exhaust. The reason for row level fuel cells running at 70% and in rack level running at 100% is that when fuel cell provides power for only one rack, it is more likely that the single server rack runs at full load, however, when several fuel cells provide power for 20 racks, the load of serves will be balanced to the data center overall utilization (between 60 to 80%).

6.4.3.1 First scenario: Rack level regenerator and dehumidifier results

In the rack level scenario, each server rack is 12kW and the server load is at 100%, which results in the 12-kW fuel cell running at full load. The efficiency of the fuel cell is 60% at full load and the exhaust leaves the fuel cell at 100°C and $0.0832 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}}$. The dehumidifier capacity is 3 tons, sized based on worst case scenario for one single server. The regenerator is sized one ton based on the available heat from fuel cell exhaust. Figure 131 to Figure 136 shows the regenerators results for Illinois for the entire year.

Figure 131. Mixture air temperature before and after regeneration process for the entire year.

Figure 132. Mixture air humidity before and after regeneration process for the entire year.

In regenerator, as shown in Figure 88 a mixture of outside air and return air is send to the regenerator. When outside air temperature is hot and humid, more return air is mixed with outside air, and when the outside air humidity is more than $11 \frac{g}{kg}$, 100% return air is used for regeneration process. Figure 131 and Figure 132 show the mixture air temperature and humidity before and after regeneration process respectively. As expected, during the regeneration process, the air humidity increases as it absorbs the humidity of the desiccant and while the hot water facilitates the regeneration process it also causes the increase in air temperature. Figure 133 shows the return air percentages.

Figure 133. Return air percentages for regeneration process.

Figure 134. Rate of regenerated desiccant flow for the entire year.

Figure 134 shows the flow rate of desiccant that is being regenerated throughout the year. The model controller keeps the desiccant concentration in a constant range, changing from 32% to 35% as shown in Figure 135. To keep the concentration at constant it manipulates the amount of desiccant in can regenerate at a time. During the month that the air inlet humidity is high and has less capability to absorb the humidity of desiccant, less desiccant is regenerated as it is seen in Figure 134 during the summer months. The hot water produced from the exhaust of fuel cell enters the regenerator at 60°C and leaves at between 44°C to 47°C shown in Figure 136.

Figure 135. Desiccant inlet and outlet concentration in regenerator.

Figure 136. Hot water inlet and outlet from regenerator.

Figure 137 to Figure 142 show dehumidifier results for Illinois. In dehumidifier, two air streams are sent to the system, one is the supply air which is a mixture of outside air and return air and the second stream is the cooling air that is sent to the dehumidifier to keep the temperature constant by evaporative cooling. Figure 137 and Figure 138 show the supply air and cooling air inlet and outlet temperature. Figure 139 shows the amount of return air. For Illinois during May to September dehumidification is needed. Other time of the year the humidity of supply air is within the acceptable range. As the outside air humidity is higher the use of return air increases due to lower humidity. However, the return air percentages depend both on temperature and humidity of outdoor air and return air to keep the supply air humidity within the acceptable range for servers. Figure 140 shows the humidity ratio of inlet and outlet supply air.

Figure 137. Supply air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier for the entire year.

Figure 138. Cooling air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier for the entire year.

Figure 139. Return air percentages for dehumidifier process for the entire year.

Figure 140. Humidity ratio of inlet and outlet supply air for the entire year.

Figure 141 shows the desiccant flow that is needed for the entire year to dehumidify the air for the server while keeping the desiccant concentration between 35% to 32%. The desiccant concentration changes are shown at Figure 142. For Illinois the strong desiccant is used during May to September and the rest of the year is stored.

Figure 141. Desiccant flow that is needed for the entire year to dehumidify the air for the servers.

Figure 142. Desiccant inlet and outlet concentration in dehumidifier.

The dehumidifier and regenerator rack level results for Iowa, Texas, and Virginia can be found in Appendix B.1.

6.4.3.2 First scenario: Rack level storage

Figure 143 shows the net desiccant consumption and production for the entire year for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois. The positive bar (blue lines) shows the time that the strong desiccant produced is being stored, and the negative bar (orange lines) are when the consumption of strong desiccant is higher than the amount that is being produced and as a result is a desiccant deficit. The areas with higher temperature and humidity level such as Texas has more deficit periods during the year. At rack level, the stored desiccant goes as high as 58lit, and the deficit goes as high as 86lit at a time.

Figure 143. Net desiccant consumption and production for the entire year for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois.

Figure 144 shows the state of storage (charge) of strong desiccant for all four locations. Considering starting at zero state in January. During the first couple of months most of the strong desiccant get stored and fills the tank, as the usage of strong desiccants increases during spring and summer, the tank gets empty and a deficit is observed, and then again during fall the tank gets filled with strong desiccant. For Texas, there is a time period between Feb to April that the rate of production and consumption of the strong desiccants is more or less similar which keeps the tank as constant state.

Figure 144. State of storage (charge) of strong desiccant for all four locations.

Table 32 shows the row level results for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois. The net production to consumption ratio without storage shows what percentages of the demand of data center cooling in each location can be met directly using heat from the SOFC to regenerate saturated desiccant. This metric describes the fraction of data center cooling load that can be met without desiccant storage. For all four locations this ratio is below 40%. However, with storage only 60% and 44% of annual production is enough to meet the entire years demand for Illinois and Iowa respectively. For Virginia, with storage there is only 4% deficit for Virginia and for Texas the deficit decreases from 60% to 20% with storage. For row level results, the annual production and consumption of strong desiccant is shown for each location. Virginia needs the biggest tank size with 187m³, which is due to the unbalance between production season and consumption. For Virginia, the first couple of months the year the cooling system is mainly producing strong desiccant without the consumption (unlike Texas) which leads to need for a bigger size storage tank.

Table 32. Rack level storage results for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois.

	Illinois	Iowa	Texas	Virginia
Net Production to Consumption Ratio (Without storage) (%)	36.94	38.14	39.65	36.73
Annual Production (m³)	366	372	314	333
Annual Consumption (m³)	229	227	397	347
Excess production (m³)	137	145	-82.9	-13.8
Tank size (m³)	110	107	173	187
Annual Net Production to Consumption Ratio (%)	59.8	63.9	-20.9	-3.9

6.4.3.3 Second scenario: Row level regenerator and dehumidifier results

In the row level scenario, each row has 10 server racks, and two rows are cooled by one dehumidifier system. Each server rack is 12kW and the server load is at average 70%, which results in the equivalent of 240kW fuel cell running at 70% capacity. The efficiency of the fuel cell is 64% and the exhaust leaves the fuel cell at 86°C and $0.0635 \frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{s}}$. The dehumidifier capacity is 42 tons, sized based on the cooling required for worst case weather condition for 20 servers. The regenerator is sized 15 tons based on the available heat from fuel cell exhaust. Figure 145 to Figure 150 show the regenerators results for Illinois for the entire year.

Figure 145. Mixture air temperature before and after regeneration process.

Figure 146. Mixture air humidity before and after regeneration process.

Figure 147. Return air percentage for regenerator.

Figure 145 and Figure 146 show the mixture air temperature and humidity before and after regeneration process respectively. Figure 147 shows the return air percentages.

Figure 148. Regenerated desiccant flow rate throughout the year.

Figure 149. Desiccant concentration inlet and outlet in regenerator.

Figure 148 shows the flow rate of desiccant that is being regenerated throughout the year. The model controller keeps the desiccant concentration in a constant range, changing from 32% to 35% as shown in Figure 149. The hot water produced from the exhaust of fuel cell enters the regenerator at 60°C and leaves at between 40°C to 45°C shown in Figure 150.

Figure 150. Hot water inlet and outlet temperature before and after regenerator.

Figure 151 to Figure 156 show the dehumidifier row level results for Illinois. Figure 151 and Figure 152 show the supply air and cooling air inlet and outlet temperature. Figure 153 shows the amount of return air. Figure 154 show the humidity ratio of inlet and outlet supply air.

Figure 151. Supply air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier.

Figure 152. Cooling air inlet and outlet temperature in dehumidifier.

Figure 153. Return air percentage in dehumidifier.

Figure 155 shows the desiccant flow that is needed for the entire year to dehumidify the air for 20 servers while keeping the desiccant concentration between 35% to 32%. The desiccant concentration changes are shown at Figure 156.

Figure 154. cooling air inlet and outlet humidity ratio in dehumidifier.

Figure 155. Desiccant flow rate in dehumidifier for the entire rate.

Figure 156. desiccant inlet and outlet desiccant concentration.

The dehumidifier and regenerator row level results for Iowa, Texas, and Virginia can be found in Appendix B.2.

6.4.3.4 Second scenario: Row level storage

Figure 157 shows the net desiccant consumption and production for the entire year for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois in row level storage. The positive bars show excess strong desiccant produced, and the negative bar shows the desiccant deficit. At row level, the stored desiccant goes as high as 822 liters and the deficit goes a high a 1200 liters at a time.

Figure 157. Net desiccant consumption and production for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois in row level storage.

Figure 158 shows the state of storage (charge) of strong desiccant for all four locations. Considering starting at zero state in January. Table 33 shows the rack level results for the four locations. For all three locations this ratio is below 40% the same as rack level results. However, with storage 80% and 72% annual production meets the entire years demand for Illinois and Iowa respectively. For Virginia, with storage there the strong desiccant production is equivalent to demand and for Texas the deficit decreases from 20% to 16% compared to rack level. For row level results, the annual production and consumption of strong desiccant is shown for each location. Virginia needs the biggest size of tank (2600m³) due to the high humidity level and unbalanced strong desiccant production and consumption.

Figure 158. the state of storage of strong desiccant for Virginia, Texas, Iowa, and Illinois in row level storage.

Table 33. Rack level storage results for the four locations.

	Illinois	Iowa	Texas	Virginia
Net production to consumption (Without storage) (%)	37	39	40	36
Annual production (m³)	5400	5400	4600	4920
Annual Consumption (m³)	3220	3190	5500	4910
Excess production (m³)	2180	2300	-900	13
Tank size (m³)	1516	1550	2360	2600
Annual net production to consumption (%)	67.7	72.1	-16.4	0.26

6.4.3.5 Rack and Row level Comparison:

To compare the two scenarios, it is assumed that the cooling and power system is designed for a 240MW data center at Illinois. Table 34 shows a comparison of the two scenarios. Each server is 12kW and requires 1400CFM cold air entering the servers at 20°C and leaving the servers at 35°C. The humidity ratio is kept below $11 \frac{g}{kg}$. Fuel cells are used to power the servers. Each fuel cell is equivalent of 8 BlueGEN system. The hot water loop temperature change is between 45°C to 60°C and the max recirculated air in IEC is 20%. The results show that designing the server cooling is row level instead of rack level can decrease the size of storage needed for servers between 26 to 32% in different weather conditions. This design gives the opportunity to run the fuel cell at partial load with higher efficiency and decreases the infrastructure needed for server cooling.

Table 34. Rack and Row level storage comparison.

Rack					Row				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fuel cell runs full load FC efficiency 60% FC exhaust at 100°C, 0.0832kg/s Server load 100% Dehumidifier: 3ton Regenerator 1ton 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fuel cell runs 70% load FC efficiency 64.5% FC exhaust at 86.3°C, 0.0635kg/s Server load 70% Dehumidifier: 42ton Regenerator 15ton 				
	Illinois	Iowa	Texas	Virginia		Illinois	Iowa	Texas	Virginia
Tank size (10 ⁶ m ³)	2.2	2.1	3.4	3.7	Tank size (10 ⁶ m ³)	1.5	1.55	2.3	2.6

6.4.4 Summary

In this chapter, the integrated system behavior had been analyzed to meet server power and cooling demands in a data center setting for both spontaneous case and with storage. The SOFC system could produce enough power for a single server rack. The SOFC system exhaust heat had been predicted to leave the 12kW SOFC system at 100°C temperature and 0.832kg/s flow rate. The exhaust of the SOFC system can produce hot water at 0.044kg/s at 60°C. The results showed that the SOFC exhaust heat was able to continuously provide 8% of server rack required supply air in the safe range of temperature and dehumidification under these conditions. Results showed that for daily storage in a summer day, that needed dehumidification all 24 hours, the integrated system did not provide server required cooling demand. In the second section the yearly storage has been analyzed for 4 different locations in the US, Illinois Iowa, Virginia, and Texas in two scenarios 1: rack level server with 12kW demand, and 2: row level servers with 240kW demand. Yearly storage results showed that in rack level design only 60% and 44% of annual production is enough to meet the entire year demand for Illinois and Iowa respectively. In Virginia there is only 4% deficit to meet the yearly demand, while in Texas the deficit is 20%. In row level design, Virginia's annual production balances the demand, while Texas still has deficit, but decreased from 20% to 16% compared to rack level design. Comparison between row level scenario and rack level scenario shows that row level design cooling system decrease the size of storage needed for servers between 26 to 32% in different weather conditions.

7. Conclusion

This report details experimental and physical modeling efforts to analyze a SOFC based CCHP system for data center applications. We considered two cooling systems for CCHP integration – an absorption chiller and liquid desiccant dehumidification system. Experimental work was based on the BlueGEN 1.5 kW SOFC system coupled with a Yazaki absorption chiller. No desiccant system was included in the experiments.

Experimental results showed that:

- The BlueGEN systems operated with a higher efficiency at full load (> 60% fuel to electricity conversion efficiency), and efficiency dropped at lower loads. The control system of the BlueGEN was designed to maintain a constant air flow and adjust the fuel utilization and flow proportional to the output power, which results in lower efficiency at part load.
- The BlueGEN SOFC system showed an increased fuel requirements of 0.58% over 42 days of highly dynamic operation. When operated at steady state over 3,000 hours, fuel requirements increased only 0.3%.
- Yazaki chiller performance peaks when inlet SOFC exhaust temperature is between 190 and 210°C while chiller power peaks at the highest SOFC exhaust temperature that we tested.

Modeling results for the SOFC and absorption chiller indicate:

- A SOFC paired with a triple effect absorption chiller may be capable of meeting data center cooling demand. However, cooling power versus SOFC electric power peaks at a ratio of 1:1. Real cooling dynamics could differ from this where more cooling power is required. This behavior is not expected in mild and colder climates, but must be considered in any SOFC CCHP system design.
- This CCHP system is able to reduce primary energy requirements 20% to 30% when operated using conventional natural gas, representing a 20% to 30% reduction in GHG emissions in most locations across the United States. As the electric grid transitions to renewable sources of electricity, conventional natural gas would need to be replaced with renewable fuels to sustain or increase GHG reductions.
- Primary energy savings are primarily driven by a combination of higher SOFC electrical efficiency and cooling production from the absorption chiller. The increase in electrical efficiency accounts for approximately half of primary energy and GHG emission reductions. The other half is due to the proximity of the SOFC to electrical demand, which enables the use of CCHP techniques that meet cooling loads, reducing conventional cooling system operation.
- Total cost of the SOFC – absorption chiller based system is approximately \$80/MWh. This cost represents a floor since switching to a renewable fuel will increase cost of operation.

Modeling results for the SOFC and liquid desiccant dehumidification and cooling system show:

- Under certain conditions, the integrated SOFC-LDD system could not continuously provide all the power and cooling required for server racks if operated continuously at 12kW. Desiccant storage must be included where regenerated desiccant is stored and used for cooling. This storage system would decouple server electricity requirements from server cooling demand, which do not directly correspond due to ambient weather conditions.
- If desiccant storage is used, long duration storage is required. Allowing one day of desiccant storage was found to be insufficient for meeting cooling load requirements.

However, scaling storage to a year met 93% of cooling loads in Virginia, and 80% of cooling loads in Texas.

- A comparison between rack and row level scenarios indicated that designing the server cooling system at the row level could reduce the size of the storage needed for servers by 26% to 32% in different weather conditions.

For practical applications, this work suggests that the SOFC-liquid desiccant system is not suitable for data center applications since a more complicated system with long duration desiccant storage is necessary. This work does suggest that a SOFC paired with a triple effect absorption chiller could meet data center cooling loads. One challenge is acquiring a triple effect absorption chiller, which are not readily available at the row level scale. This leads to the suggestion that SOFC at the data center scale are suitable for direct integration with an absorption chiller based chiller plant. This concept was not explored in this work. However, general results from this report indicate that there is a mismatch between server electric and cooling demand, and that shifting towards CCHP systems designed to meet the energy demand of a larger number of servers leads to the best overall system results. Designing a system for the data center versus row or rack of servers could reduce the severity of electric load fluctuations, allow for more intimate and efficient connections between the SOFC and thermally driven cooling systems, could maintain primary energy savings associated with CCHP at the data center, and would allow for direct integration with backup cooling equipment.

Four immediate research needs are:

1. SOFC + Absorption Chiller dynamic performance: SOFC and absorption chiller dynamic performance were not explored in this work. Results suggest that triple effect absorption chillers may be suitable for meeting data center cooling loads. Triple effect absorption chillers typically do not have the dynamic response capabilities of a single-effect AC. Actual implementation of the SOFC+AC system would need to be dynamically modeled and explored.
2. Electrical and thermal integration: Dynamic operation results indicate that SOFC systems may not respond quickly enough to match data center dynamics. Analysis of larger scale systems need to be examined to evaluate the potential of SOFC systems to meet data center dynamic load requirements.
3. Design optimization: If SOFC systems are unable to meet dynamic load requirements, and/or if a CCHP system cannot meet cooling load energy or dynamic requirements, integration with other electrical and cooling systems is necessary. Technoeconomic design is necessary to balance the adoption of SOFC and other CCHP components.
4. Renewable fuel: Complete decarbonization of a data center with SOFC systems requires the use of renewable fuel and/or other carbon offsets (i.e., exhaust gas or direct air capture). This analysis did not consider a 100% renewable fuel. One potential candidate is pure renewable H₂. Since pure H₂ SOFC systems use different balance of plant components, system performance will change as we switch from conventional to renewable fuel.

8. References

- [1] N. Jones, “The information factories,” *Nature*, vol. 561, no. 7722, pp. 163–166, 2018.
- [2] A. S. G. Andrae and T. Edler, “On global electricity usage of communication technology: trends to 2030,” *Challenges*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 117–157, 2015.
- [3] A. Strategy, “SMARTer2030: ICT solutions for 21st century challenges,” *The Global eSustainability Initiative (GeSI), Brussels, Brussels-Capital Region, Belgium, Tech. Rep.*, vol. 3, 2015.
- [4] Í. Goiri *et al.*, “Matching renewable energy supply and demand in green datacenters,” *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 25, pp. 520–534, 2015.
- [5] E. Oró, V. Depoorter, A. Garcia, and J. Salom, “Energy efficiency and renewable energy integration in data centres. Strategies and modelling review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 42, pp. 429–445, 2015.
- [6] “Electric Power Annual 2020,” <https://www.eia.gov/electricity/annual/pdf/epa.pdf>.
- [7] L. Zhao *et al.*, “Fuel cells for data centers: Power generation inches from the server,” *Microsoft Research, Tech. Rep. MSR-TR-2014-37*, 2014.
- [8] H. Rong, H. Zhang, S. Xiao, C. Li, and C. Hu, “Optimizing energy consumption for data centers,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 58, pp. 674–691, 2016.
- [9] “Data Center Outages are Common, Costly, and Preventable,” <https://uptimeinstitute.com/data-center-outages-are-common-costly-and-preventable>.
- [10] Mike DeCamp, “Eaton’s Blackout Tracker Annual Report shows 36.7 million people affected by more than 3,500 power outages in 2017,” https://www.eaton.com/us/en-us/company/news-insights/news-releases/2018/eaton_s-blackout-tracker-annual-report-shows-36-7-million-people.html.
- [11] Tom Krazit, “Microsoft releases details on last week’s big Azure outage, during which servers were damaged but no data was lost,” <https://www.geekwire.com/2018/microsoft-releases-details-last-weeks-big-azure-outage-servers-damaged-no-data-lost/>.
- [12] “New Thinking on Data Center Power Security,” <https://www.bloomenergy.com/blog/category/data-center/>.
- [13] “What is a Data Center?,” <https://www.paloaltonetworks.com/cyberpedia/what-is-a-data-center>.
- [14] “Data Center Power Design and Features,” Data Center Power <https://www.digitalrealty.com/data-center-powerand-Features>.
- [15] R. Ascierio, “Uptime institute global data center survey,” *Seattle: Uptime Insitute*. https://uptimeinstitute.com/uptime_assets/f7bb01a900c060cc9abe42bb084609f63f02e448f5df1ca7ba7fdebb746cd1c4-2018-data-center-industry-survey.pdf, 2018.
- [16] Bob West, “Understanding the Interplay Between Data Center Power Consumption/Data Center Energy Consumption and Power Density,” <https://www.datacenters.com/news/understanding-the-interplay-between-data-center-power-consumption-data-center-en>.
- [17] A. TC, “Data center power equipment thermal guidelines and Best practices,” *ASHRAE TC 9.9, ASHRAE, USA*, 2016.
- [18] R. I. Salim, H. Noura, M. Nabag, and A. Fardoun, “Modeling and temperature analysis of the nexa 1.2 kw fuel cell system,” *J Fuel Cell Sci Technol*, vol. 12, no. 6, 2015.
- [19] Stephen J. Bigelow, “Free Cooling,” <https://www.techtarget.com/searchdatacenter/definition/free->

- cooling?_gl=1*1i5xvc9*_ga*NzE0NzE4MDM1LjE2MTEwNjk1OTk.*_ga_RRBYR9CG
B9*MTYxMjgwNTk5OC4yLjEuMTYxMjgwNjk5MC4w&_ga=2.97313119.1364078739
.1612805999-714718035.1611169599.
- [20] Adam Meyer, “Adiabatic cooling: best of both worlds,”
<https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/en/opinions/adiabatic-cooling-best-of-both-worlds/>.
- [21] Hans Vreeburg, “Indirect Adiabatic Data Center Cooling,”
https://datacenter.com/news_and_insight/indirect-adiabatic-data-center-cooling/.
- [22] M. Saito, H. Yoshida, Y. Iwamoto, and A. Ueda, “An analysis of a micro cogeneration system composed of solid oxide fuel cell, microturbine, and h₂O/LiBr absorption refrigerator,” *Journal of Thermal Science and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 168–179, 2007.
- [23] S. H. Chan, H. K. Ho, and Y. Tian, “Modelling of simple hybrid solid oxide fuel cell and gas turbine power plant,” *J Power Sources*, vol. 109, no. 1, pp. 111–120, 2002.
- [24] Y. Yi, A. D. Rao, J. Brouwer, and G. S. Samuelsen, “Analysis and optimization of a solid oxide fuel cell and intercooled gas turbine (SOFC–ICGT) hybrid cycle,” *J Power Sources*, vol. 132, no. 1–2, pp. 77–85, 2004.
- [25] X. Zhang, J. Li, G. Li, and Z. Feng, “Cycle analysis of an integrated solid oxide fuel cell and recuperative gas turbine with an air reheating system,” *J Power Sources*, vol. 164, no. 2, pp. 752–760, 2007.
- [26] M. Mehrpooya, H. Dehghani, and S. M. A. Moosavian, “Optimal design of solid oxide fuel cell, ammonia-water single effect absorption cycle and Rankine steam cycle hybrid system,” *J Power Sources*, vol. 306, pp. 107–123, 2016.
- [27] M. Rokni, “Design and analysis of a waste gasification energy system with solid oxide fuel cells and absorption chillers,” *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 11, pp. 5922–5938, 2018.
- [28] M. Tian, Z. Yu, H. Zhao, and J. Yin, “Thermodynamic analysis of an integrated solid oxide fuel cell, Organic Rankine Cycle and absorption chiller trigeneration system with CO₂ capture,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 171, pp. 350–360, 2018.
- [29] N. de Arespacochoaga, C. Valderrama, C. Mesa, L. Bouchy, and J. L. Cortina, “Biogas deep clean-up based on adsorption technologies for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell applications,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 255, pp. 593–603, 2014.
- [30] V. Palomba, M. Ferraro, A. Frazzica, S. Vasta, F. Sergi, and V. Antonucci, “Dynamic simulation of a multi-generation system, for electric and cooling energy provision, employing a SOFC cogenerator and an adsorption chiller,” *Energy Procedia*, vol. 143, pp. 416–423, 2017.
- [31] V. Palomba, M. Ferraro, A. Frazzica, S. Vasta, F. Sergi, and V. Antonucci, “Experimental and numerical analysis of a SOFC-CHP system with adsorption and hybrid chillers for telecommunication applications,” *Appl Energy*, vol. 216, pp. 620–633, 2018.
- [32] C.-C. Wu and T.-L. Chen, “Design and dynamics simulations of small scale solid oxide fuel cell tri-generation system,” *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, vol. 1, p. 100001, 2019.
- [33] “eBay plans for 6 MW of Bloom SOFCs to power new data centre,” *Fuel Cells Bulletin*, vol. 2012, no. 7, p. 5, 2012, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859\(12\)70196-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859(12)70196-7).
- [34] “Apple doubles fuel cell capacity at NC data centre with Bloom,” *Fuel Cells Bulletin*, vol. 2013, no. 1, p. 5, 2013, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859\(13\)70011-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859(13)70011-7).

- [35] “Bloom to power 12 Equinix data centres in US,” *Fuel Cells Bulletin*, vol. 2017, no. 8, p. 1, 2017, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859\(17\)30276-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859(17)30276-6).
- [36] L. Zhao, J. Brouwer, S. James, E. Peterson, D. Wang, and J. Liu, “Fuel cell powered data centers: In-rack dc generation,” *ECS Trans*, vol. 71, no. 1, p. 131, 2016.
- [37] A. A. Etemadieh, *Verification of a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell System for In-Rack Server Power Generation in Data Centers*. University of California, Irvine, 2016.
- [38] “Cummins, McKinstry, Microsoft open energy lab in Seattle to test fuel cells in data centres,” *Fuel Cells Bulletin*, vol. 2017, no. 10, p. 1, 2017, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859\(17\)30309-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1464-2859(17)30309-7).
- [39] A. J. Ritchie and J. Brouwer, “Design of fuel cell powered data centers for sufficient reliability and availability,” *J Power Sources*, vol. 384, pp. 196–206, 2018.
- [40] G. Saur *et al.*, “Radical Re-Envisioning of Data Centers with Row-Integrated Fuel Cells,” National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2020.
- [41] M. Sheppy, C. Lobato, O. van Geet, S. Pless, K. Donovan, and C. Powers, “Reducing Data Center Loads for a Large-Scale, Low-Energy Office Building: NREL’s Research Support Facility (Book),” National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2011.
- [42] I. Metzger, J. Dean, and C. Kurnik, “Psychrometric bin analysis for alternative cooling strategies in data centers,” *ASHRAE Trans*, vol. 117, p. 254, 2011.
- [43] R. Rahmani, I. Moser, and M. Seyedmahmoudian, “A complete model for modular simulation of data centre power load,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.00703*, 2018.
- [44] Cartier Corporation, “commercial HVAC chiller equipment: air cooled chiller,” 2005.
- [45] Stephen G. Kline, “Energy Water Nexus: Balancing Two Precious Resources in HVAC Systems.” 2016.
- [46] Ian Seaton, “Cooling Efficiency Algorithms: Condensers and Temperature Differentials.”
- [47] D. McLarty, J. Brouwer, and S. Samuelsen, “A spatially resolved physical model for transient system analysis of high temperature fuel cells,” *Int J Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 38, no. 19, pp. 7935–7946, 2013.
- [48] B. A. Haberman and J. B. Young, “Three-dimensional simulation of chemically reacting gas flows in the porous support structure of an integrated-planar solid oxide fuel cell,” *Int J Heat Mass Transf*, vol. 47, no. 17–18, pp. 3617–3629, 2004.
- [49] P. Kazempoor, V. Dorer, and F. Ommi, “Modelling and Performance Evaluation of Solid Oxide Fuel Cell for Building Integrated Co-and Polygeneration,” *Fuel Cells*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1074–1094, 2010.
- [50] M. S. Reineh, M. Fardadi, and F. Jabbari, “Thermal control of SOFC: An anti-windup approach for maximizing usable power,” in *2017 IEEE Conference on Control Technology and Applications (CCTA)*, IEEE, 2017, pp. 311–316.
- [51] C. E. L. Nóbrega and N. C. L. Brum, *Desiccant-assisted cooling: fundamentals and applications*. Springer, 2013.
- [52] T. Elmer, *A novel SOFC tri-generation system for building applications*. Springer, 2016.
- [53] T. Welch, H. Carwarardine, and K. Butcher, “CIBSE Knowledge Series: KS13-Refrigeration.” H. Carwarardine and K, 2008.
- [54] B. Ouazia, H. Barhoun, K. Haddad, M. Armstrong, R. G. Marchand, and F. Szadkowski, “Desiccant-evaporative cooling system for residential buildings,” in *12th Canadian Conference on Building Science and Technology*, Institute for Research in Construction, 2009, pp. 1–12.

- [55] “Liquid Desiccants,” <http://air.com/liquid-desiccant/ld-tutorial/>.
- [56] D. Betts, M. R. Ally, S. Mudiraj, M. Tilghman, and M. Graham, “Small Business Voucher CRADA Report: Natural Gas Powered HVAC System for Commercial and Residential Buildings,” Oak Ridge National Lab.(ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States). Building ..., 2017.
- [57] L. Mei and Y. J. Dai, “A technical review on use of liquid-desiccant dehumidification for air-conditioning application,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 662–689, 2008.
- [58] X. Liu, Y. Jiang, S. Liu, and X. Chen, “Research progress in liquid desiccant air-conditioning devices and systems,” *Frontiers of Energy and Power Engineering in China*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 55–65, 2010.
- [59] E. Kozubal, J. Woods, J. Burch, A. Boranian, and T. Merrigan, “Desiccant enhanced evaporative air-conditioning (DEVap): evaluation of a new concept in ultra efficient air conditioning,” National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2011.
- [60] X. Chen, S. Riffat, H. Bai, X. Zheng, and D. Reay, “Recent progress in liquid desiccant dehumidification and air-conditioning: A review,” *Energy and Built Environment*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 106–130, 2020.
- [61] X. H. Liu, Y. Jiang, and X. Q. Yi, “Effect of regeneration mode on the performance of liquid desiccant packed bed regenerator,” *Renew Energy*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 209–216, 2009.
- [62] A. Zuber, R. F. Checoni, R. Mathew, J. P. L. Santos, F. W. Tavares, and M. Castier, “Thermodynamic properties of 1: 1 salt aqueous solutions with the electrolyte equation of state,” *Oil & Gas Science and Technology–Revue d’IFP Energies nouvelles*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 255–270, 2013.
- [63] J. Sun, X. L. Gong, and M. H. Shi, “Study on vapor pressure of liquid desiccants solution,” *J Refrig*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 28–30, 2004.
- [64] S. Y. Ahmed, P. Gandhidasan, and A. A. Al-Farayedhi, “Thermodynamic analysis of liquid desiccants,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 11–18, 1998.
- [65] T. Elmer, M. Worall, S. Wu, and S. Riffat, “An experimental study of a novel integrated desiccant air conditioning system for building applications,” *Energy Build*, vol. 111, pp. 434–445, 2016.
- [66] G. A. Longo and A. Gasparella, “Experimental and theoretical analysis of heat and mass transfer in a packed column dehumidifier/regenerator with liquid desiccant,” *Int J Heat Mass Transf*, vol. 48, no. 25–26, pp. 5240–5254, 2005.
- [67] X. H. Liu, Y. Zhang, K. Y. Qu, and Y. Jiang, “Experimental study on mass transfer performances of cross flow dehumidifier using liquid desiccant,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 47, no. 15–16, pp. 2682–2692, 2006.
- [68] W. Z. Gao, Y. R. Shi, Y. P. Cheng, and W. Z. Sun, “Experimental study on partially internally cooled dehumidification in liquid desiccant air conditioning system,” *Energy Build*, vol. 61, pp. 202–209, 2013.
- [69] P. Bansal, S. Jain, and C. Moon, “Performance comparison of an adiabatic and an internally cooled structured packed-bed dehumidifier,” *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 14–19, 2011.

- [70] A. H. Abdel-Salam and C. J. Simonson, "State-of-the-art in liquid desiccant air conditioning equipment and systems," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 58, pp. 1152–1183, 2016.
- [71] P. Bansal, S. Jain, and C. Moon, "Performance comparison of an adiabatic and an internally cooled structured packed-bed dehumidifier," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 14–19, 2011.
- [72] X. H. Liu and Y. Jiang, "Handling zone dividing method in packed bed liquid desiccant dehumidification/regeneration process," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 3024–3034, 2009.
- [73] J. Woods and E. Kozubal, "A desiccant-enhanced evaporative air conditioner: Numerical model and experiments," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 65, pp. 208–220, 2013.
- [74] X. She, Y. Yin, and X. Zhang, "Thermodynamic analysis of a novel energy-efficient refrigeration system subcooled by liquid desiccant dehumidification and evaporation," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 78, pp. 286–296, 2014.
- [75] A. Khalil, "An experimental study on multi-purpose desiccant integrated vapor-compression air-conditioning system," *Int J Energy Res*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 535–544, 2012.
- [76] M. M. Bassuoni, "Experimental performance study of a proposed desiccant based air conditioning system," *J Adv Res*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 87–95, 2014.
- [77] B. S. Mohan, M. P. Maiya, and S. Tiwari, "Performance characterisation of liquid desiccant columns for a hybrid air-conditioner," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 28, no. 11–12, pp. 1342–1355, 2008.
- [78] L. Mucke, D. Fleig, K. Vajen, and U. Jordan, "Hybrid liquid desiccant air-conditioning systems: A conceptual study with respect to energy saving potentials," *International Journal of refrigeration*, vol. 69, pp. 64–73, 2016.
- [79] K. Mansuriya, V. K. Patel, B. D. Raja, and A. Mudgal, "Assessment of liquid desiccant dehumidification aided vapor-compression refrigeration system based on thermo-economic approach," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 164, p. 114542, 2020.
- [80] Y. J. Dai, R. Z. Wang, H. F. Zhang, and J. D. Yu, "Use of liquid desiccant cooling to improve the performance of vapor compression air conditioning," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 1185–1202, 2001.
- [81] A. Capozzoli, P. Mazzei, F. Minichiello, and D. Palma, "Hybrid HVAC systems with chemical dehumidification for supermarket applications," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 26, no. 8–9, pp. 795–805, 2006.
- [82] Y. Li, L. Lu, and H. Yang, "Energy and economic performance analysis of an open cycle solar desiccant dehumidification air-conditioning system for application in Hong Kong," *Solar Energy*, vol. 84, no. 12, pp. 2085–2095, 2010.
- [83] B. Su, W. Qu, W. Han, and H. Jin, "Feasibility of a hybrid photovoltaic/thermal and liquid desiccant system for deep dehumidification," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 163, pp. 457–467, 2018.
- [84] M. Tu, C.-Q. Ren, L.-A. Zhang, and J.-W. Shao, "Simulation and analysis of a novel liquid desiccant air-conditioning system," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 29, no. 11–12, pp. 2417–2425, 2009.
- [85] R. M. Lazzarin and F. Castellotti, "A new heat pump desiccant dehumidifier for supermarket application," *Energy Build*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 59–65, 2007.

- [86] X. Niu, F. Xiao, and Z. Ma, "Investigation on capacity matching in liquid desiccant and heat pump hybrid air-conditioning systems," *international journal of refrigeration*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 160–170, 2012.
- [87] K. Zhao, X.-H. Liu, T. Zhang, and Y. Jiang, "Performance of temperature and humidity independent control air-conditioning system in an office building," *Energy Build*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 1895–1903, 2011.
- [88] Y. Chen, Y. Yin, and X. Zhang, "Performance analysis of a hybrid air-conditioning system dehumidified by liquid desiccant with low temperature and low concentration," *Energy Build*, vol. 77, pp. 91–102, 2014.
- [89] L. Zhang, E. Hihara, and M. Saikawa, "Combination of air-source heat pumps with liquid desiccant dehumidification of air," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 57, pp. 107–116, 2012.
- [90] L. Zhang, C. Dang, and E. Hihara, "Performance analysis of a no-frost hybrid air conditioning system with integrated liquid desiccant dehumidification," *International journal of refrigeration*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 116–124, 2010.
- [91] A. Gasparella, G. A. Longo, and R. Marra, "Combination of ground source heat pumps with chemical dehumidification of air," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 25, no. 2–3, pp. 295–308, 2005.
- [92] S. Shen, W. Cai, X. Wang, Q. Wu, and H. Yon, "Hybrid model for heat recovery heat pipe system in Liquid Desiccant Dehumidification System," *Appl Energy*, vol. 182, pp. 383–393, 2016.
- [93] S. Sanaye and M. Taheri, "Modeling and multi-objective optimization of a modified hybrid liquid desiccant heat pump (LD-HP) system for hot and humid regions," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 129, pp. 212–229, 2018.
- [94] A. H. Abdel-Salam and C. J. Simonson, "Optimal design, sizing and operation of heat-pump liquid desiccant air conditioning systems," *Sci Technol Built Environ*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 161–176, 2020.
- [95] M. Jradi and S. Riffat, "Experimental investigation of a biomass-fuelled micro-scale tri-generation system with an organic Rankine cycle and liquid desiccant cooling unit," *Energy*, vol. 71, pp. 80–93, 2014.
- [96] K. Gommed and G. Grossman, "Experimental investigation of a liquid desiccant system for solar cooling and dehumidification," *Solar energy*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 131–138, 2007.
- [97] T. Katejanekarn and S. Kumar, "Performance of a solar-regenerated liquid desiccant ventilation pre-conditioning system," *Energy Build*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 1252–1267, 2008.
- [98] A. K. Mohaisen and Z. Ma, "Development and modelling of a solar assisted liquid desiccant dehumidification air-conditioning system," in *Building Simulation*, Springer, 2015, pp. 123–135.
- [99] N. Fumo and D. Y. Goswami, "Study of an aqueous lithium chloride desiccant system: air dehumidification and desiccant regeneration," *Solar energy*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 351–361, 2002.
- [100] L. Crofoot and S. Harrison, "Performance evaluation of a liquid desiccant solar air conditioning system," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 30, pp. 542–550, 2012.
- [101] D. Peng, X. Zhang, and Y. Yin, "Theoretical storage capacity for solar air pretreatment liquid collector/regenerator," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 28, no. 11–12, pp. 1259–1266, 2008.
- [102] S. Alizadeh, "Performance of a solar liquid desiccant air conditioner—An experimental and theoretical approach," *Solar Energy*, vol. 82, no. 6, pp. 563–572, 2008.

- [103] R. Qi, L. Lu, and Y. Huang, “Energy performance of solar-assisted liquid desiccant air-conditioning system for commercial building in main climate zones,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 88, pp. 749–757, 2014.
- [104] G.-P. Li and L.-Z. Zhang, “Investigation of a solar energy driven and hollow fiber membrane-based humidification–dehumidification desalination system,” *Appl Energy*, vol. 177, pp. 393–408, 2016.
- [105] L.-Z. Zhang and G.-P. Li, “Energy and economic analysis of a hollow fiber membrane-based desalination system driven by solar energy,” *Desalination*, vol. 404, pp. 200–214, 2017.
- [106] Y. Chen, H. Yang, and Y. Luo, “Investigation on solar assisted liquid desiccant dehumidifier and evaporative cooling system for fresh air treatment,” *Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 114–127, 2018.
- [107] A. Hawkes, I. Staffell, D. Brett, and N. Brandon, “Fuel cells for micro-combined heat and power generation,” *Energy Environ Sci*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 729–744, 2009.
- [108] T. Elmer, M. Worall, S. Wu, and S. Riffat, “Assessment of a novel solid oxide fuel cell tri-generation system for building applications,” *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 124, pp. 29–41, 2016.
- [109] T. Elmer, M. Worall, S. Wu, and S. Riffat, “Experimental evaluation of a liquid desiccant air conditioning system for tri-generation/waste-heat-driven applications,” *International Journal of Low-Carbon Technologies*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 110–125, 2017.
- [110] T. Elmer, M. Worall, and S. Wu, “A novel solid oxide fuel cell tri-generation system for low carbon buildings,” in *12th International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies (SET 2013)*, 2013.
- [111] S. A. Klein and F. L. Alvarado, “Engineering Equation Solver (EES), FChart Software.” 2011.
- [112] E. Kozubal, J. Woods, and R. Judkoff, “Development and analysis of desiccant enhanced evaporative air conditioner prototype,” National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2012.